

1 **SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL**

2 **for the report**

3 ***"The Status of Biological Invasions and their Management in South Africa in 2019"***

4

5 This supplementary material contains additional information chapter by chapter on the methods
6 used and discussion points, as well as additional figures, tables, and text boxes to the report "*The*
7 *Status of Biological Invasions and their Management in South Africa in 2019*"

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9 For citations in the scientific literature

10 Zengeya, T.A. & Wilson, J.R. (Eds.) 2020. Supplementary Material to "The Status of Biological Invasions
11 and their Management in South Africa in 2019". South African National Biodiversity Institute,
12 Kirstenbosch and DSI-NRF Centre of Excellence for Invasion Biology, Stellenbosch.
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14 For citations in policy documents

15 SANBI and CIB 2020. SANBI and CIB 2020. Supplementary Material to "The Status of Biological
16 Invasions and their Management in South Africa in 2019". South African National Biodiversity Institute,
17 Kirstenbosch and DSI-NRF Centre of Excellence for Invasion Biology, Stellenbosch.
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19 The contributing authors are as per the main report.

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76 **Supplementary Material to Chapter 1: Introduction**

77 **S1.1 Editorial conventions**

78 *Acronyms.* All acronyms are defined at first use in every chapter and are also defined in table headings
79 and in the legends of figures. Acronyms that are used on multiple occasions or in multiple places in
80 the report are listed at the beginning of the report.

81 *Currency.* South African rands are denoted as ZAR, and not R.

82 *Naming species.* Both scientific and common names are provided when referring to species.
83 Authorities for scientific names are provided in the species list. They are not provided in the main
84 report, although are in some cases used in the supplementary table. Each species is assigned only one
85 vernacular (i.e., common) name. The vernacular name used is in English, recognising that more than
86 one English vernacular name may exist, and that vernacular names in other South African official
87 languages also exist. Exceptions are made when a non-English vernacular name is predominantly or
88 exclusively used to describe a species (e.g. *Acacia cyclops*, the vernacular name 'rooikrans' is used in
89 preference to the English 'red eye').

90 *Quotation marks.* Quotes are indicated with double quotation marks and italicised. Where a specific
91 term is indicated, single quotation marks are used and the text is not italicised.

92 *References.* All references for the text and for appendices are provided in a single list at the end of the
93 report. In the bibliography, references with more than ten authors only have the first four authors
94 listed, followed by 'et al.'

95 *Terminology.* To assist the reader who may not be familiar with commonly used terms in invasion
96 biology, a glossary of terms is provided at the beginning of the report. The terms used do not entirely
97 align with the definitions in the NEM:BA or the corresponding A&IS Regulations because some terms
98 in the regulations do not align with the terms in the Act, are inconsistent in how they are used, are
99 ambiguous, are not how the terms are generally used, or do not align with international conventions.
100 To list a few examples:

- 101 • the regulations list two groups of species 'listed invasive species' and 'prohibited alien
102 species'. However, some 'prohibited alien species' are present in the country and some 'listed
103 invasive species' are absent or are not 'invasive' as defined in this report. To avoid confusion
104 the term 'listed alien species' is defined in the glossary and used throughout;

- 105 • the term 'control' is defined in the regulations, but is defined in terms of a second term
106 'combat' which is not defined. The term 'combat' is therefore avoided and the term 'control'
107 is defined without reference to 'combat';
- 108 • the term 'invasive species' a subset of 'alien species', as such the term 'invasive alien species'
109 is avoid as the word alien is redundant;
- 110 • 'Invasive Species Monitoring, Control and Eradication Plans' referred to in the regulations are
111 referred to as 'site management plans'. This is distinct from 'species management
112 programmes' which focus on controlling particular species; and
- 113 • the definitions for 'risk analysis' and 'risk assessment' are taken from the CBD rather than
114 from the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations, see Supplementary Material section S5.4 for a discussion
115 on this.

116 *The name (and acronym) of Government Departments.* While writing the report some government
117 departments were either renamed or the process had been initiated. In particular as of July 2020,
118 the Minister for Forestry, Fisheries, and the Environment was in charge of the Department of
119 Environment, Forestry and Fisheries. This was taken to mean that the department was in the process
120 of being renamed. It was not clear what the acronym would be, and DFFtE was used.

121 **S1.2 The second report as an update to the first report and the need for a long-term strategy**

122 The first report was released in 2018. After discussion with the Reference and Advisory Committee
123 (RAC, see below), it was decided that producing a comprehensive status report every three years
124 would be impractical as insufficient new data would have been collected, the current report format
125 needs to be tested over time, and it would be difficult to detect significant changes in values. At the
126 same time, it was felt that reporting should become a continuous process that highlights important
127 developments timeously. Therefore, the longer-term plan is to develop a regularly updated dashboard
128 on the status of biological invasions that is supplemented by detailed comprehensive reports every
129 decade or so. The intention of this second report is thus largely to provide an update to the first report.

130 There is an ongoing initiative to develop a long-term strategy (e.g. over the next twenty years or more)
131 to guide the production of national status reports on biological invasions. The envisaged contents of
132 such a strategy include issues such as the need for a regular review of the indicators so that they
133 remain salient, responsive, relevant, and sufficient. There is also a need to develop scenarios for future
134 reports in terms of funding and capacity, and to review if the current reporting timeframes are
135 appropriate. The strategy will also need to propose interventions that are required to address
136 substantial data gaps identified in previous reports. It also needs to address the need to maintain
137 legitimacy, saliency, and credibility of the report [e.g. by ensuring the report is of value and is valued

138 by SANBI and key stakeholders such as the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment
139 (DFFtE) and Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development (DALRRD)]. In addition,
140 a regular review of the scope and content of the report can help increase the saliency of future reports.
141 For example, socio-economic problems caused by biological invasions (e.g. human health) and the
142 interactions between biological invasions with other drivers of global change are not covered by the
143 reports to date. These topics could be included in future to increase the societal relevance. There is
144 also a need to link the current process to other national assessments such as the National Biodiversity
145 Assessment (SANBI, 2019), and global assessments such as the Intergovernmental Science-Policy
146 Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES)'s global assessment on invasive species
147 <https://ipbes.net/invasive-alien-species-assessment>. Finally, the strategy will need to identify
148 potential risks and possible mitigation measures.

149 **S1.3 Updates to the indicators**

150 The first report had 21 indicators and 4 high-level indicators. During discussions while drafting the first
151 report, and while publishing a paper describing the indicators (Wilson et al. 2018), one of the
152 indicators—relative alien species richness—was removed. There is substantial uncertainty in
153 estimates of both alien and native species richness due to instability in taxonomy, survey effort, and
154 underlying ecological, evolutionary, and invasion processes. As such relative alien species richness can
155 change for reasons that are very difficult to interpret. However, relative invasive abundance has been
156 retained as this indicator gives an easy to measure estimate of the degree to which invasive species
157 are dominating ecosystems. Some of the names of the indicators have been changed [e.g. the term
158 'site' is preferred over the term 'area' as per McGeoch et al. (2016); and the high-level indicator 'rate
159 of introduction of new unregulated species' has been reworded as 'rate of unregulated introduction
160 of new species' for clarity, as the indicator considers species listed in the regulations that are
161 accidentally (or intentionally but illegally) introduced]. However, these indicators still measure the
162 same properties, and the numbering aligns with that used in the first status report once the removal
163 of one of the indicators is taken into account.

164 During the compilation of the second report a few changes were made to clarify some issues (in
165 particular around applying confidence levels). These changes are logged in the metadata for the
166 respective data files. A complete revised set of indicator factsheets will be produced as part of the
167 next comprehensive report, at which time the value of the indicators themselves can be more
168 appropriately appraised.

169 Separate to this report, there are several on-going initiatives to develop indicators for biological
170 invasions, notably through an the iDiv working group (sTWIST—Theory and Workflows for Alien and

171 Invasive Species Tracking, <https://www.idiv.de/en/stwist.html>). The status report team have been
172 involved in the sTWIST process, and the thinking has influenced the report (e.g. by improving the data
173 standards for the species lists). Consideration will be given to incorporating the proposed sTWIST
174 indicators and those developed through other processes, e.g. as part the IPBES's global assessment
175 on invasive species <https://ipbes.net/invasive-alien-species-assessment>, once they have been
176 finalised.

177 **S1.4 Updating the species list and tracking change**

178 The second report attempts to adhere to the FAIR data principles. Specifically: data are Findable and
179 Accessible through publication on the SANBI web-site; Interoperable by adapting fields to ensure,
180 where possible, they confirm to the Darwin Core data standards; and Reusable in terms of ensuring
181 that it is easy to determine who generated the original data and obtaining permission for others to
182 use the data. The associated data files were also produced in line with recommendations to make the
183 data tidy (Wickham 2014). Each row refers to a taxonomic unit that is used in the analysis; each column
184 a particular variable with consistent units. For example, in the first report, very different types of data
185 on range size were incorporated into one column [occupancy of large-scale national subdivisions (e.g.
186 provinces); occupancy of quarter-degree-grid cells; specific estimates of range size (e.g. in ha); and
187 text descriptions of ranges]. These were disaggregated to form four columns each of which is internally
188 consistent. And, unlike the first status report which contained three separate species lists, the second
189 report contains a single unified list (Appendix 2).

190 In cases where a species has several traits for a given variable (e.g. it is found in several habitats or has
191 been introduced through multiple pathways), values are separated in the database using a pipe-
192 delimiter '|'. The decision as to whether both traits are included, or they are reduced proportionally
193 is specified in the relevant analysis.

194 The process proposed in this report tracks several reasons why indicators values can change between
195 the first and second report, including: 1) data collected in the first report are no longer relevant; 2)
196 data collected in the first report need to be reinterpreted; 3) there were changes but these do not
197 affect the value of any of the indicators (e.g. some changes in nomenclature); 4) new information is
198 available that indicates the value has changed since the first report; and 5) new information is available
199 that was not available in the first report (Table S1.1). There are several other schemes, e.g. see
200 guidelines for using the proposed IUCN standard classification of the impact of invasive taxa (IUCN
201 2019), but the intention is to trial the scheme in Table S1.1 at least until the next comprehensive
202 report.

203 **Table S1.1** Different reasons for why values might have changed from one report to the next and
 204 proposed actions based on these including how this will affect the baseline. If errors are found there
 205 should be a process of feedback to the data holders regardless of whether such errors impact on the
 206 indicator values.

Reason for difference		Action
1. Data were collected in the first report but these are not relevant for the second report	1.1 There has been a change in the indicators so that the data are no longer relevant	Assess whether the change in the indicator means that data are no longer used in the analysis, suggesting additional changes to the indicators are needed. Previous baseline is obsolete.
	1.2 There were errors in the data, such that they cannot map on to the second report	Provide feedback to data holder and find out if data are correctly interpreted. Use a revised baseline if possible.
2. Data were collected in the first report but need to be reinterpreted for the second report	2.1 A change in indicators means that the data used do not align perfectly	Develop a mapping methodology and assess its validity (vs. random) using that to inform confidence levels. Use a revised baseline if possible (potentially by adapting the previous baseline)
	2.2 There has been a change in the data (e.g. a species has split into two taxonomic units, new geographical boundaries, or regulations are developed)	Develop a mapping methodology and clearly indicate the assumptions made. Use a revised baseline if possible (potentially by adapting the previous baseline)
3. Data were collected in the first report but there was no change in the values for the second report	3.1 No new data were found	There is no evidence in support of 'no change'—assess whether the lack of new data affects confidence level and need for monitoring. No change to the baseline.
	3.2 New data support the previous data	There is evidence in support of no change, with confidence levels potentially increasing. No change to the baseline.
	3.3 The new data changes something that does not affect the indicators (e.g. there is a change to the species name, but all the rest of the data stay the same)	No action needed beyond the update. No change to the baseline.
	3.4 New data do not support a change to previous data, but question previous values	Consider improved monitoring and reducing confidence levels in current estimates. Consider whether the baseline needs to be revised.
4. Data collected for the second report indicate the value has changed since the first report	4.1 Data were collected between the two reports (i.e. 2017, 2018, or 2019)	There has been a genuine change in the value. No change to the baseline.
	4.2 Data were collected 2016 or earlier but not included in past report	The updated value should be used as the value in the first report for the purpose of tracking change, i.e. use a revised baseline.
	4.3 See a continuous change over time	Test to see if there is a statistically significant trend.
5. Data collected for the second report where no data were available in the first report	5.1 Data not available previously were collected during 2017, 2018, or 2019	Data used to establish a baseline
	5.2 Data were collected 2016 or earlier but not included in the first report	A baseline is created retrospectively and changes with more recent data can be analysed
	5.3 There is a new indicator	Data used to establish a baseline

208 **S1.5 What exactly does the cut-off date for inclusion of data of Dec 2019 mean?**

209 The second report set the end of December 2019 as a cut-off after which no new data would be
210 considered for the report. Of course, however, some data published in 2019 or earlier were only
211 discovered by the team after Dec 2019, highly relevant material was published early in 2020, and the
212 authors of this report were aware of on-going research that will not be published until 2020 or later.
213 Therefore we needed to codify some principles of what to include. If an article was published on-line
214 in 2019, but not allocated to a specific journal issue, then it was included. However it had to be clearly
215 specified as available in 2019. For example, the paper by Hassan & Mahlathi (2020) in WaterSA, was
216 not considered, as although on the pdf it states it was accepted in December 2019, it was only
217 published in 2020 (and not obviously available previous to this). Of course, if data concerned a
218 particular status (e.g. a new record of introduction) the date of data collection was used when
219 calculating the indicator values. This publication delay is an important issue in biodiversity science and
220 a major limitation to the responsiveness of the indicators to change. In cases where papers discuss
221 particular ideas rather than data, it was possible to still include such considerations. But the analyses
222 performed were explicitly based on the state of the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations as at December 2019
223 (i.e., the proposed changes published in the Government Gazette in 2018 were only considered to the
224 extent to which they were proposals, and the regulatory status used here is as it was in 2016). The
225 major exemption to this rule was the book on Biological Invasions in South Africa (van Wilgen et al.
226 2020a). This report was compiled in parallel to the book, and so the book was very influential in
227 shaping this report. It was also unclear whether the book would be published late in 2019 or early in
228 2020 until very late in the process. Therefore the book is included as a data source. Unpublished data
229 sent to the reporting team was also included, although if it had not undergone peer-review such data
230 would generally be ascribed as a lower confidence than studies published in peer-reviewed journals.

231 **S1.6 Aspects of biological invasions that are not covered**

232 Given the report is an update, the aspects not covered in the second report are largely the same as
233 those not covered in the first report, viz Sect. 1.4, Chap. 1, SANBI and C·I·B 2018: *“First, as the status*
234 *report’s primary function is to report on environmental issues, this initial report has a limited focus on*
235 *the socio-economic problems caused by biological invasions. The most damaging invasive species are*
236 *human diseases. These are not included in this report. Similarly, pests and weeds that affect*
237 *agricultural crops are a major threat to sustainable development, but are not within this report’s remit*
238 *unless such taxa also impact on, or threaten, natural ecosystems. Secondly, there is a suite of*
239 *indigenous species that can have undesirable impacts that are similar to the impacts caused by alien*
240 *species, but which are precipitated by changes in land use or other aspects of global change. Examples*
241 *include bush encroachment by indigenous plants, and the spread of many indigenous bird species into*

242 *urban areas. These can present particular problems, but their management needs to be in the context*
243 *of them as indigenous to the region and as pests within their native ranges.”*

244 **S1.7 Process for developing the status report**

245 The status report process (Fig. 1.2) was also codified as a standard operating procedure within SANBI
246 (see below, note this procedure is still to be formally approved).

247

249 **DFFtE-SANBI APP STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE OBJECTIVE 8**

250 **Indicator: 8.1 Implementation of the plan to develop the 2nd National Status report in 2020**
 251

Background

- The South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) is required by the National Environment Management: Biodiversity Act (NEM:BA) (Act No 10 of 2004) and the Alien and Invasive Species Regulations of 2014 to compile and submit to the Minister a report on the status on biological invasions in South Africa within three years of the date the regulations came into effect and every three years thereafter. The report must contain a summary and assessment of (a) the status of listed invasive species and other species that have been subjected to a risk assessment; and (b) the effectiveness of the regulations and control measures. SANBI is also expected to carry out research and monitoring necessary to determine status and effectiveness. The regulations came into effect on 1 October 2014 and the first report was completed in March 2018.
- This document sets out the standard operating procedure to guide the production of national status reports on biological invasions.

Process

- The status report must adhere to the requirements of section 11 of the Alien and Invasive Species (A&IS) Regulations of 2014 that were promulgated under the National Environmental Management: Biodiversity Act (NEM:BA) (Act 10 of 2004).
- The process of compiling the status report is as outlined in Annexure 1¹ and as otherwise specified in the process document.
- This process follows international best practices for scientific assessments (Ash et al. 2010²; Scholes et al. 2017³).
- The status report is structured around an indicator framework for assessing biological invasions at a national scale (Wilson et al. 2018⁴).

Reporting of actual achievements

- The Director responsible for the status report on biological invasions, verifies progress by reviewing quarterly progress reports against a project plan and submitted evidence.
- The Chief Director who is responsible for Programme 4 (currently the CD for BRAM) checks the evidence and compiles a quarterly report (in terms of reporting on the APP objectives). The report is submitted to the Director: CEO Office and Board Secretary who consolidates these reports.
- SANBI's Branch Head(s), and eventually the CEO, will review these reports electronically and edit variances and summarise the reports for submission to DFFtE.
- Reporting against relevant APP indicators is reported on an annual basis through SANBI's Annual Report and by SANBI Senior Management to the Portfolio Committee on Environmental Affairs (PCEA).

¹As per Figure 1.2 of the report

²Ash N, Blanco H, Brown C, Garcia K, Henrichs T, Lucas N., et al. (eds.). 2010. Ecosystem and human well-being: A manual for assessment practitioners, Island Press, Washington, DC, USA.

³Scholes RJ, Schreiner GO, Snyman-Van der Walt L. 2017. Scientific assessments: Matching the process to the problem', *Bothalia* 47(2), a2144. <https://doi.org/10.4102/abc.v47i2.2144>

⁴Wilson JRU, Faulkner KT, Rahlao SJ, Richardson DM, Zengeya TA, van Wilgen BW. 2018. Indicators for monitoring biological invasions at a national level. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 55: 2612-2620. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13251>

253 **Supplementary Material to Chapter 2: Pathways**

254 **S2.1 Background notes**

255 The chapter on pathways reports on how alien taxa can be introduced to South Africa and how these
256 taxa can disperse within the country. In the chapter, the term ‘pathways of introduction’ refers to the
257 processes that could facilitate the introduction of alien taxa to the country, while the term ‘pathways
258 of dispersal’ refers to the processes that could facilitate the movement of alien taxa within the
259 country.

260 Four indicators were used to evaluate the pathways of introduction and dispersal: (1) Introduction
261 pathway prominence; (2) Introduction rates; (3) Within-country pathway prominence; and (4) Within-
262 country dispersal rates. A high-level indicator (the Rate of unregulated introduction of new species)
263 was also evaluated. Introduction and Within-country pathway prominence consider the size of the
264 pathways of introduction and dispersal, but do not take into account their importance for the
265 introduction or dispersal of organisms. Introduction rates considers the importance of the pathways
266 for the introduction of new alien organisms, and Within-country dispersal rates considers the
267 importance of the pathways of dispersal for alien organisms, and native taxa that have been
268 introduced to parts of the country where they are not native.

269 **S2.2 Updates since the first report**

270 In the first report the pathway categorisation scheme adopted by the Convention on Biological
271 Diversity was used (CBD, 2014). Recently, guidelines for the scheme have been produced which
272 provide definitions for the categories and subcategories and propose small revisions to the scheme
273 (see Harrower, Scalera, Pagad, Schönrogge, & Roy, 2018). The pathway categorisation scheme, with
274 the proposed revisions, is used in the second report and is shown in Table S2.1. To assess how the
275 pathways of introduction and dispersal have changed since the first report, updated data were
276 obtained from databases where available, and other datasets were updated by consulting the
277 literature and experts (see below for further details). All data sources are shown in [Appendix 1](#). In
278 addition, as far as possible data on pathways of introduction have been added to the species list
279 (Appendix 2), however, further work is required, and so the data used to assess Introduction rates are
280 presented in Appendix 5.

281

282 **Table S2.1** Changes to the pathway categories used in the first report as compared the second report.
 283 Changes are shown in bold.

CBD pathway of introduction categorisation scheme used in the first report		CBD pathway of introduction categorisation scheme used in the second report	
RELEASE IN NATURE	Biological control	Biological control	RELEASE
	Erosion control/dune stabilisation	Stabilisation & barriers	
	Fishery in the wild	Fishery in the wild	
	Hunting	Hunting	
	Landscape/flora/fauna "improvement" in the wild	Aesthetic release	
	Introduction for conservation purposes or wildlife management	Conservation in wild	
	Release in nature for use other than above		
	Other intentional release	Other release	
ESCAPE FROM CONFINEMENT	Agriculture	Agriculture	ESCAPE
	Aquaculture/mariculture	Aquaculture	
	Botanical garden/zoo/aquaria	Botanical gardens & zoos	
	Pet/aquarium/terrarium species	Pet	
	Farmed animals	Farmed animals	
	Forestry	Forestry	
	Fur farms	Fur farms	
	Horticulture	Horticulture	
	Ornamental purpose other than horticulture	Ornamental	
	Research and ex-situ breeding	Research	
	Live food and live baits	Live food and live bait	
	Other escape from confinement	Other escape	
TRANSPORT-CONTAMINANT	Contaminant nursery material	Nursery material contaminant	CONTAMINANT
	Contaminated bait	Bait contaminant	
	Food contaminant	Food contaminant	
	Contaminant on animals	Contaminant of animals	
	Parasites on animals	Parasites of animals	
	Contaminant on plants	Contaminant of plants	
	Parasites on plants	Parasites of plants	
	Seed contaminant	Seed contaminant	
	Timber trade	Timber trade contaminant	
	Transportation of habitat material	Habitat material contaminant	
	NA	Other contaminant	
	TRANSPORT-STOWAWAY	Angling/fishing equipment	
Container/bulk		Container & bulk cargo	
Hitchhikers in or on airplane		Airplane	
Hitchhikers on ship/boat		Ship excluding ballast water or hull fouling	
Machinery/equipment		Machinery & equipment	
People and their luggage/equipment		People & luggage	
Organic packing material, in particular wood packaging		Packing material	
Ship/boat ballast water		Ballast water	
Ship/boat hull fouling		Hull fouling	
Vehicles		Land vehicles	
Other means of transport		Other stowaway	
CORRIDOR		Interconnected waterways/basins/seas	Canals & artificial waterways
	Tunnels and land bridges	Tunnels & bridges	
UNAIDED	Natural dispersal across borders of invasive alien species that have been introduced through pathways 1 to 5	Natural dispersal	UNAIDED

285 **S2.3 Estimation of Introduction pathway prominence**

286 South Africa has 72 official ports of entry: eight maritime ports, ten airports and 54 land border posts
287 (Figure S2.1). A high amount of people, goods and transport vessels enter the country through these
288 ports of entry, potentially providing many opportunities for the introduction of alien taxa. In the first
289 report socio-economic information collected from a wide range of sources was used by an expert to
290 classify the size of the pathways into five categories of Introduction pathway prominence. For the
291 second report, the datasets used in the first report were examined to determine if the data had been
292 updated, and these updated datasets, as well as other recently published socio-economic data were
293 used in the second report to estimate Introduction pathway prominence. [Appendix 1](#) provides the list
294 of sources used. In the first report, confidence in the overall assessment of Introduction pathway
295 prominence was estimated, and in the second report, confidence in the overall assessment as well as
296 that for each pathway was estimated (see Appendix 3). The expert that classified the data for the first
297 report, classified the data for the second report. If no new data were collected, Introduction pathway
298 prominence was rated as in the first report. If new data were collected these data were compared to
299 those obtained for the first report. As a rule of thumb, a change in the assessment was made if there
300 was a greater than 30% difference between the values for the most recent year for which data were
301 available in comparison to the values for the first report. However, a change of 30% does not necessarily
302 mean that the prominence of a pathway has changed. For example, the Introduction pathway
303 prominence of pathways related to the importation of live plants was rated as 'moderate' in the first
304 report. The value of live plant imports has increased since the first report by ~70% (Figure S2.6).
305 However, even with this increase the value of this trade is not in the same range as that of the pathways
306 that are rated as 'major', for which imports are worth billions of US dollars, and so no change was made
307 to the rating for the pathways related to live plant imports. Therefore, the values for the different
308 pathways were additionally considered when making the assessment. Appendix 3 provides the socio-
309 economic data used to assess Introduction pathway prominence, as well as the ratings for each
310 pathway, and below are graphical representations of some of the data used in the assessments. See
311 Table S2.6 for a summary of the values for the indicator for the first and second report.

312

313

314 **Figure S2.1** South Africa's 72 ports of entry. There has been no change to these ports of entry since
 315 the first report. Information was obtained from the South African Department of Home Affairs (2017).

316

317

318 **Figure S2.2** While the area harvested for crops in South Africa (in black) has declined since the early
 319 1990s, crop production (in grey) has increased. These data were used to assess the Introduction
 320 pathway prominence of the agriculture pathway. Crop production changed very little (~5% increase)
 321 since the first report (production in 2014 vs 2017) and so there was no change to the assessment for
 322 this pathway. Data were obtained from the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations
 323 (FAO, 2019).

324

325 **Figure S2.3** Aquaculture production in South Africa has increased since the 1990s. These data were
 326 used to assess the Introduction pathway prominence of the aquaculture pathway in the first report.
 327 Data were obtained from the FishstatJ database of the Food and Agricultural Organization of the
 328 United Nations (FAO, 2016). No updated data were available from this database for the second report,
 329 and for the second report data for this pathway were obtained from another source (see Appendix 3).

330

331

332 **Figure S2.4** The number of animals farmed in South Africa has in general increased over time, but
 333 there have been recent declines, possibly due to drought. These data were used to assess the
 334 Introduction pathway prominence of the farmed animals pathway. The number of animals farmed
 335 changed very little (~5% increase) since the first report (number farmed in 2014 vs 2017) and so there
 336 was no change to the assessment for this pathway. Data were obtained from the Food and Agricultural
 337 Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2019).

338

339

340 **Figure S2.5** Forestry production in South Africa has declined since it peaked in 2006, but there has
 341 been little change in the past five years. These data were used to assess the Introduction pathway
 342 prominence of the forestry pathway. Forestry production changed very little (~5% decrease) since the
 343 first report (production in 2015 vs 2017) and so there was no change to the assessment for this
 344 pathway. Data were obtained from the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO,
 345 2019).

346

347 **Figure S2.6** The value of live plant imports to South Africa has increased over fourfold since 2000, with
 348 a particularly large increase since 2016. These data were used to assess the Introduction pathway
 349 prominence of the horticulture, ornamental, nursery material contaminant, contaminant of plants,
 350 and parasite of plants pathways. The value of live plant imports increased by ~70% since the first
 351 report (imports in 2016 vs 2018), however, as the value of these imports is still not in the same range
 352 as those for pathways that are rated 'major', these pathways were rated as 'moderate' (as they were
 353 in the first report). Data were obtained from the United Nations Comtrade database (UN-Comtrade,
 354 2019). Values were converted to 2017 US dollars.

355

356 **Figure S2.7** The quantity of food imported into South Africa has increased, particularly since 2000.
 357 These data were used to assess the Introduction pathway prominence of the food contaminant
 358 pathway. Data were obtained from the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO,
 359 2017). No updated data were available for the second report, and so there was no change to the
 360 assessment for this pathway.

361

362 **Figure S2.8** The number of animals imported into South Africa has fluctuated over time. In the early
 363 2000s a relatively high number of animals were imported, but since then animal imports have
 364 declined. These data were used to assess the Introduction pathway prominence of the contaminant
 365 of animals and parasite of animals pathways. The number of animals imported changed very little
 366 (decrease of ~6%) since the first report (imports in 2013 vs 2016), and so there was no change to the
 367 assessments for these pathways. Data were obtained from the Food and Agricultural Organization of
 368 the United Nations (FAO, 2019).

369

370 **Figure S2.9** The volume of agronomic seeds imported into South Africa has fluctuated over time. These
 371 data were used to assess the Introduction pathway prominence of the seed contaminant pathway.
 372 The volume of agronomic seeds imported increased by ~70% since the first report (imports in 2013 vs
 373 2017). However, the volume imported is much less than for pathways that are rated 'major' (e.g. 7
 374 million tons of food), and so the pathway was rated as 'moderate', as it was in the first report. Data
 375 were obtained from the South African Department of Agriculture Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF, 2018).

376

377 **Figure S2.10** The value of forestry products imported into South Africa began to increase in the 1990s,
 378 but recently there has been a slight decline. These data were used to assess the Introduction pathway
 379 prominence of the timber trade contaminant pathway. The value of forestry imports decreased by
 380 ~11% since the first report (imports in 2015 vs 2018), and so there was no change to the assessment
 381 for this pathway. Data were obtained from the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United
 382 Nations (FAO, 2019) and were converted to 2017 US dollars.

383

384 **Figure S2.11** The quantity of freshwater and marine fish caught in South Africa has declined over time.
 385 These data were used to assess the Introduction pathway prominence of the fishing equipment
 386 pathway for the first report. Data were obtained from the FishstatJ database of the Food and
 387 Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2016a). No updated data were available from
 388 this database for the second report, and for the second report data were obtained from another
 389 source.

390

391 **Figure S2.12** The number of South African (in black) and foreign (in grey) fishing vessels visiting South
 392 African ports has declined since 2014. Data for 2017 were not obtained. These data were used to
 393 assess the Introduction pathway prominence of the fishing equipment pathway. In 2018 there were
 394 757 fishing vessels in South African waters, in comparison to 1245 vessels in 2016, this represents a
 395 decline of ~40% since the first report (data for 2016 vs 2018), and so this pathway was rated
 396 'moderate' (the pathway was rated 'major' in the first report). These data were obtained from the
 397 Transnet National Ports Authority (2017, 2019a).

398

399 **Figure S2.13** The number of deep sea containers landed at South African ports has remained relatively
 400 consistent since 2009. Data for 2017 were not obtained. These data were used to assess the
 401 Introduction pathway prominence of the container and bulk cargo pathway. The number of containers
 402 landed increased by ~12% since the first report (data for 2016 vs 2018), and so there was no change
 403 to the assessment for this pathway. These data were obtained from the Transnet National Ports
 404 Authority (2017, 2019a).

405

406 **Figure S2.14** The number of scheduled aircraft arriving in South Africa from international and regional
 407 destinations has remained consistent over the last few years. The South African financial year starts
 408 on 1 April and ends on 31 March. These data were used to assess the Introduction pathway
 409 prominence of the airplane pathway. The number of aircraft changed very little (~4% increase) since
 410 the first report (data for 2015/2016 vs 2018/2019), and so there was no change to the assessment for
 411 this pathway. These data were obtained from Airports Company South Africa (2019).

412

413 **Figure S2.15** The number of ocean-going vessels arriving at South African ports has been fairly
 414 constant over time, if anything declining slightly. Data for 2010-2012 and 2017 were not obtained.
 415 These data were used to assess the Introduction pathway prominence of the ship excluding ballast
 416 water or hull fouling, hull fouling, and ballast water pathways. The number of vessels decreased by
 417 ~11% since the first report (data for 2016 vs 2018), and so there was no change to the assessments
 418 for these pathways. These data were obtained from Transnet National Ports Authority (2017, 2019a),
 419 and do not include the fishing vessel data presented in Figure S2.12.

420

421 **Figure 2.16** The contribution of travel and tourism to South Africa's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has
 422 increased over time. These values have been adjusted for inflation. These data were used to assess
 423 the Introduction pathway prominence of the people and luggage pathway. The contribution of travel
 424 and tourism to South Africa's GDP has changed very little (<1% decrease) since the first report (data
 425 for 2016 vs 2019), and so there was no change to the assessment for this pathway. Data were obtained
 426 from the World Tourism and Travel Council (2019). Please note these data include future projections.

427

428

429 **Figure S2.17** The number people arriving in South Africa by (A) air, (B) road and (C) sea transport in
 430 2016, 2017 and 2018. These data were used to assess the Introduction pathway prominence of the
 431 people and luggage, and land vehicles pathways. The total number of people entering South Africa
 432 changed very little (~1% increase) since the first report, as did the number entering via road transport
 433 (2% decrease) (data for 2016 vs 2018), and so there was no change to the assessments for these
 434 pathways. Data were obtained from Statistics South Africa (2019).

435

436 **Figure S2.18** The value of vehicles imported into South Africa has decreased since 2013. These data
 437 were used to assess the Introduction pathway prominence of the land vehicles pathway. The value of
 438 imported vehicles increased by ~11% since the first report (data for 2016 vs 2018), and so there was
 439 no change to the assessment for this pathway. Data were obtained from the United Nations Comtrade
 440 database (UN-Comtrade, 2019). Values have been converted to 2017 US dollars.

441

442 **Figure S2.19** (A) The value of merchandise imports to mainland African countries has increased over
 443 time, and (B) the volume of goods imported into this region is expected to increase in the future. South
 444 African imports were not included. These data were used to assess the Introduction pathway
 445 prominence of the unaided pathway. The value of merchandise imports changed very little (decrease
 446 of ~4%) since the first report (data for 2015 vs 2018), and so there was no change to the assessment
 447 for this pathway. Data were obtained from the World Trade Organisation (2019) and International
 448 Monetary Fund (2019). Values were converted to 2017 US dollars.

450 S2.4 Changes made to Introduction pathway prominence

451 Changes to Introduction pathway prominence were tracked using the process detailed in Table S1.1.
 452 See Table S2.2 for a summary of the types of changes made and Figure S2.20 for details on how these
 453 changes have influenced the indicator. For 37 pathways there was no change to Introduction pathway
 454 prominence, but for one pathway Introduction pathway prominence changed due to data collected
 455 for the second report. Data collected for the second report led us to question the assessment made

456 for one pathway in the first report. For two pathways the data collected had to be reinterpreted due
 457 to the implementation of new methods, namely the guidelines for the CBD pathway framework
 458 (Harrower et al., 2018), and for three pathways Introduction pathway prominence was estimated for
 459 the first time.

460 **Table S2.2** A summary of the type of changes made to the data for the indicator Introduction pathway
 461 prominence for South Africa, 2017 – 2019.

Reason for difference	Number of changes
Data were collected in the first report but these are not relevant for the second report	1
Data were collected in the first report but need to be reinterpreted for the second report	2
Data were collected in the first report but there was no change in the values for the second report	37
Data collected for the second report indicate the value has changed since the first report	1
Data collected for the second report where no data were available in the first report	3
Grand Total	44

462

463

464 **Figure S2.20** A diagram showing how the changes made to the data for Introduction pathway
 465 prominence have influenced the indicator.

466 **S2.5 Estimation of Introduction rates**

467 In the first report, information on the pathways of introduction, date of introduction/first record and
468 native range for taxa introduced to South Africa were used to assess Introduction rates. These data
469 were obtained from the dataset developed by Faulkner et al. (2015), which was created by extracting
470 information from selected alien species databases that were published in papers, books and reports
471 up until December 2012 (Faulkner et al., 2015). For the second report recently published alien species
472 databases that update the information in the databases used to develop the Faulkner et al. (2015)
473 dataset were identified. These databases were published in papers, books or as reports between 2014
474 and December 2019 (note that some of the publications used are dated 2020, but these were available
475 to the authors before January 2020), and care was taken to ensure that they spanned a wide range of
476 taxonomic groups. For five of the taxa that were recently introduced (2017-2020) information on
477 pathways of introduction was obtained from experts. Data from the identified, recently published
478 databases and from the experts were used to update the Faulkner et al. (2015) dataset, and this
479 updated dataset was used in the second report to estimate Introduction rates. See Appendix 1 for full
480 details of the sources used.

481 For the first report, the pathways of introduction were classified using the framework adopted by the
482 Convention on Biological Diversity into six pathway categories and 44 subcategories (CBD, 2014). Taxa
483 introduced through more than one pathway were assigned to multiple pathway categories, and
484 consequently the number of taxa across the pathways was greater than the total number of taxa
485 included in the analysis. At the time of the analysis limited information on the CBD framework was
486 available, and descriptions of the subcategories of the framework had not yet been provided.
487 Consequently, in the first report the pathways of introduction were classified based on an
488 interpretation of the subcategories, and it was noted that there was uncertainty in some of the
489 classifications. For example, it was difficult to distinguish between some of the subcategories and in
490 some instances the data that were available were not of sufficient quality or detail to designate
491 pathways of introduction with certainty. To account for this in the first report, confidence in pathway
492 classifications was estimated using the methods detailed in Box S2.1. Subsequent to the first report,
493 guidelines for the CBD framework were produced (i.e. Harrower et al., 2018) and, in an effort to deal
494 with areas of uncertainty and confusion, small cosmetic adjustments were proposed – the
495 nomenclature of the categories was changed, two overlapping pathways were merged, and a catch-
496 all pathway subcategory was added for contaminant introductions that do not fit into any of the
497 detailed subcategories (see Table S2.1). The guidelines provided detailed descriptions of the
498 categories and subcategories of the framework, and made recommendations on how confidence in
499 classifications could be estimated (Harrower et al., 2018). In the second report two sets of methods

500 were used to classify pathways and estimate confidence in classifications. Firstly, the methods used in
501 the first report were implemented. Secondly, pathways were reclassified using the guidelines provided
502 by Harrower et al. (2018), and confidence in these classifications was estimated using a new method
503 based on the recommendations of Harrower et al. (2018) (details in Box S2.2). The implementation of
504 the two methods allowed change to be tracked more clearly. Only the results using the latter methods
505 are presented in the second report, and all changes made to the data are presented in Table S2.3.

506 As in the first report the earliest date of introduction/first record was utilised in instances where
507 multiple introduction events occurred or if, due to uncertainty, a period of time was given. However,
508 in the second report confidence in date of first record was estimated for each taxon using the method
509 detailed in Box S2.3.

510 As in the first report, excluded from the analysis in the second report were hybrid taxa, dubious
511 records [e.g. the mollusc *Vertigo antivertigo* which has only been found as a subfossil (Herbert, 2010)],
512 taxa that have not yet escaped from confinement, and those whose native range extends into South
513 Africa. Taxa for which the native range is uncertain were excluded unless currently believed to be alien
514 to the whole of South Africa. Taxa which were listed as alien but for which no information on native
515 range was provided were assumed to be alien and were included in the analyses.

516 Appendices 3 and 5 provide the data used to assess Introduction rates and estimates of confidence,
517 and Table S2.6 provides a summary of the values for the indicator for the first and second report.

518

519 **Box S2.1 The methods followed in the first report to estimate confidence in pathway of introduction**
520 **classifications.**

521 In instances where pathway of introduction was unknown, where these data were not provided in the
522 selected databases, or where insufficient information were provided to make a categorisation, the
523 pathway category and subcategory were classified as 'Pathway unknown'. In some instances a
524 pathway category could be categorised but there was insufficient information for categorisation at
525 the pathway subcategory level (e.g. the pathway of introduction for some alien bird taxa was
526 described as 'escape', with no further detail provided). In these instances, a pathway category was
527 assigned and the pathway subcategory was classified as 'Not enough detail provided'.

528 In some instances pathway descriptions were vague and as a result it was difficult to make definite
529 categorisations. Furthermore, during categorisation the similarity of some of the pathway
530 subcategories (e.g. 'Contaminant nursery material' and 'Contaminant on plants') caused uncertainty.

531 In an effort to account for these uncertainties, certainty in the pathway category and subcategory
532 assignments for each taxon were rated.

533 If more than one pathway category was equally likely due to a vague description, all possible pathways
534 were listed but certainty was rated low [e.g. cornflower (*Centaurea cyanus*) may have been introduced
535 as either an ornamental plant (i.e. Escape from confinement) or as a seed impurity (i.e. Transport -
536 Contaminant)]. In instances where a specific pathway could easily be assigned but there was some
537 doubt as to whether an additional pathway was applicable, only the definite pathway category was
538 listed but confidence was rated medium and the possible additional pathway was noted [e.g. the
539 common garden snail (*Cornu aspersum*) was introduced to South Africa as a food item (i.e. Escape
540 from confinement) but this is also a 'traveller' mollusc and thus might also have been introduced
541 accidentally (i.e. Transport – contaminant and/or Transport – stowaway)]. If a taxon's pathway of
542 introduction could easily be categorised, certainty was rated high.

543 If multiple pathway subcategories were equally likely due to a vague pathway of introduction
544 description, all possible pathway subcategories were listed but certainty was rated low. For example,
545 'shipping' for marine taxa could refer to a Transport-stowaway introduction through the 'ballast
546 water' and/or 'hull fouling' pathways. If the similarity of pathway subcategories led to uncertainty in
547 categorisation, the most likely or more specific subcategory was listed, the other possibility was noted,
548 and confidence was rated medium. For example, Argentine ant (*Linepithema humile*) was introduced
549 as a contaminant of horse fodder (i.e. Transport - contaminant), the pathway subcategory was
550 categorised as 'Contaminant on plants (except parasites, species transported by host/vector)', the
551 similar alternative ('Transportation of habitat material (soil, vegetation...') was noted and certainty
552 was rated medium. If a taxon's pathway subcategory could easily be categorised, certainty was rated
553 high.

554

555 **Box S2.2 The methods followed in the second report to estimate confidence in pathway of**
556 **introduction classifications.**

557 Three aspects were considered when estimating confidence in pathway classifications – the quality of
558 the evidence, the quality of the source, and the quality of the description. Harrower et al. (2018)
559 recommended that the quality of the evidence and the quality of the source be considered when
560 estimating confidence in pathway classifications. However, in the first report it was noted that the
561 data available often did not map onto the CBD framework as, for example, the data were not detailed
562 enough to make classifications with certainty. Therefore, an estimate of the quality of the description
563 was additionally included.

564 The quality of the evidence was rated as high, medium or low as recommended in Harrower et al.
565 (2018). The quality of the evidence was high if there was direct evidence that the species was
566 introduced through the pathway, medium if there was indirect evidence that the species was
567 introduced through the pathway, and low if the pathway was based on information on the life history
568 of the species or data from similar species, or if the quality of the evidence was unclear.

569 The quality of the source was rated as high, medium or low as recommended in Harrower et al. (2018).
570 The quality of the source was high if the source of the data was a peer-reviewed journal article or grey
571 literature from a respectable source, medium if the data source was grey literature from a known
572 source or from expert opinion, and low if the source of the data was grey literature from an
573 unknown/non-expert source or if the source was unspecified.

574 The quality of the description was rated as high, medium or low. The quality of the description was
575 high if the pathway was clearly described by one category of the CBD pathway scheme, medium if the
576 pathway was described by more than one category of the CBD scheme, but one pathway was more
577 applicable and this pathway was assigned, and low if the pathway was described equally by more than
578 one category of the CBD pathway scheme.

579 If a taxon had more than one pathway of introduction then the quality of the evidence, source and
580 description were estimated for all pathways, and for each aspect the lowest estimate across the
581 pathways was assigned.

582 Overall confidence in pathway classification was determined by combining the estimates for the
583 quality of the evidence, the quality of the source and the quality of the description. The overall
584 confidence is the lowest estimate across the quality of the evidence, the quality of the source and the
585 quality of the description.

586 In instances where pathway of introduction was unknown, where these data were not provided in the
587 selected sources, or where insufficient information were provided to make a categorisation, the
588 pathway was classified as 'Unknown' and confidence was NA (Not Applicable). In some instances,
589 there was sufficient information for classification at the category level, but not at the subcategory
590 level (e.g. the pathway of introduction for some alien bird taxa was described as 'escape', with no
591 further detail provided). In these instances, the data were classified at the category level, but not at
592 the subcategory level, and the quality of the description was rated low.

593

594 **Box S2.3 The methods followed in the second report to estimate confidence in date of first record.**

595 Confidence in the date of first record for each taxon was estimated by considering three factors: the
596 taxon's pathway of introduction, whether date of introduction or date of first record data were
597 available, and whether the information obtained was ambiguous (e.g. a period of time was given as
598 opposed to a specific date).

599 Confidence in date of first record was rated high, medium or low. Confidence was high if the species
600 was intentionally released into the natural environment (the pathway falls under the 'Release'
601 category) and the year the species was first introduced was clearly specified, with no ambiguity.
602 Confidence was medium if the species was not intentionally released into the natural environment
603 (the pathway does not fall under the 'Release' category) and the year the species was first introduced
604 was clearly specified with no ambiguity. Confidence was low in any other instance (e.g. date of first
605 record is used).

606

607 **S2.6 Changes made to Introduction rates**

608 Changes to Introduction rates were tracked using the process detailed in Table S1.1. See Table S2.3
609 for a summary of the types of changes made, and Table S2.4 for details on how these changes
610 influenced the indicator. For the majority of the taxa (1319 taxa), there was no change to the pathways
611 reported in the first report (Table S2.3), however, for 271 taxa the pathways had to be reinterpreted
612 due to the implementation of new methods, namely the guidelines for the CBD pathway framework
613 (Harrower et al., 2018). For 512 taxa, new data were collected that led to a change in the pathways of
614 introduction, and for 115 of these taxa the pathways assigned differed based on the method
615 implemented (i.e. the methods used in the first report vs new methods). Included in the first report
616 were 66 taxa which were excluded in the second report due to errors (e.g. the misidentification of a
617 species). Only new taxa added to the dataset based on data published since 2016 were regarded as a
618 genuine change, all other changes were considered when calculating a revised baseline for the first
619 report. Results presented in the second report for the assessment of Introduction rates at a moderate
620 level (i.e. number of taxa introduced in the last full decade in comparison to the previous decade) are
621 not comparable to those presented in the first report, as the decades compared in the second report
622 (2000-2009 and 2010-2019) differ from those compared in the first report (1900-1999 and 2000-
623 2009).

624

625 **Table S2.3** A summary of the type of changes made to the data for the indicator Introduction rates
 626 for South Africa, 2017 – 2019.

Reason for difference	Number of changes
Data were collected in the first report but these are not relevant for the second report	66
Data were collected in the first report but need to be reinterpreted for the second report	271
Data were collected in the first report but there was no change in the values for the second report	1319
Data collected for the second report indicate the value has changed since the first report	512
Data collected for the second report where no data were available in the first report	0
Grand Total	2168

627 **Table S2.4** Details of how the changes made to the data for Introduction rates have influenced the
 628 indicator. Presented are the Introduction rates (i.e. number of taxa introduced through the
 629 pathways over all time) as reported in the first report, and the revised baseline for the first report
 630 due to the implementation of new methods and the incorporation of data that were available in
 631 2016 or earlier, but that were not included in the first report. Also presented are the Introduction
 632 rates for the pathways presented in the second report based on information that has become
 633 available since the first report, and changes to introduction rates since the first report, as calculated
 634 based on the revised baseline. Please note, the values given for biological control include all known
 635 introductions for biological control and not only those agents that were released against invasive
 636 plants.

Pathway of Introduction		Introduction rates reported in first report	Revised baseline	Introduction rates reported in second report	Change
Release	Biological control	111	127	157	30
	Stabilisation and barriers	68	91	93	2
	Fishery in wild	15	17	17	0
	Hunting	30	32	33	1
	Aesthetic release	8	8	8	0
	Conservation in wild	0	3	3	0
	Other release	8	8	8	0
Escape	Agriculture	91	103	104	1
	Aquaculture	12	15	15	0
	Botanical gardens & zoos	3	6	6	0
	Pet	22	52	54	2
	Farmed animals	5	15	16	1
	Forestry	30	38	38	0
	Fur farms	1	1	1	0
	Horticulture	237	290	302	12
	Ornamental	1	265	276	11
	Research	4	10	10	0
	Live food and live bait	5	2	2	0
	Other escape	72	1	1	0
Contaminant	Nursery material contaminant	3	11	11	0
	Bait contaminant	0	15	15	0
	Food contaminant	7	14	15	1
	Contaminant of animals	9	9	9	0

Pathway of Introduction		Introduction rates reported in first report	Revised baseline	Introduction rates reported in second report	Change
	Parasite of animals	13	14	35	21
	Contaminant of plants	20	23	24	1
	Parasite of plants	2	3	26	23
	Seed contaminant	8	15	37	22
	Timber trade contaminant	10	10	11	1
	Habitat material contaminant	6	5	5	0
	Other contaminant	NA	NA	0	NA
Stowaway	Fishing equipment	0	0	0	0
	Container & bulk cargo	0	13	13	0
	Airplane	5	3	3	0
	Ship excluding ballast water or hull fouling	21	22	24	2
	Machinery & equipment	0	1	1	0
	People & luggage	0	0	0	0
	Packing material	1	1	1	0
	Ballast water	51	55	61	6
	Hull fouling	68	68	76	8
	Land vehicles	1	1	1	0
	Other stowaway	0	2	2	0
Corridor	Canals & artificial waterways	0	0	0	0
	Tunnels & bridges	0	0	0	0
Unaided	Natural dispersal	9	9	13	4

637

638 **S2.7 Estimation of Within-country pathway prominence**

639 In the first report, Within-country pathway prominence was not assessed as socio-economic data
640 related to the pathways of dispersal could only be obtained for a few pathways. This was again the
641 case for the second report. See Appendix 3 and below for the data that were collected, and Table S2.6
642 for a summary of the values for the indicator for the first and second report.

643
 644 **Figure S2.21** The total number of scheduled aircraft arriving at South African airports from domestic
 645 destinations has remained relatively constant since the 2012/2013 financial year. The South African
 646 financial year starts on 1 April and ends on 31 March. These data were collected for the airplane
 647 pathway. The number of aircraft traveling between South African airports has changed very little
 648 (decreased by 4%) since the first report (data for 2015/2016 vs 2018/2019). These data were obtained
 649 from Airports Company South Africa (2019).

650
 651 **Figure S2.22** The number of scheduled aircraft arriving at each major South African airport from
 652 domestic destinations. The South African financial year starts on 1 April and ends on 31 March. These
 653 data were collected for the airplane pathway. These data were obtained from Airports Company South
 654 Africa (2019).

655 **Figure S2.23** The number of passengers arriving at South African airports from domestic destinations.
 656 The South African financial year starts on 1 April and ends on 31 March. These data were collected for
 657 the people and luggage pathway. The number of people traveling between South African airports has
 658 changed very little (increased by 8%) since the first report (data for 2015/2016 vs 2018/2019). These
 659 data were obtained from Airports Company South Africa (2019).
 660

661 **S2.8 Estimation of Within-country dispersal rates**

662 As in the first report, data on Within-country dispersal rates has not yet been collated country-wide
 663 and only a few examples were obtained. Therefore, Within-country dispersal rates were not assessed.
 664 However, recently research has been done on the pathways of dispersal for alien plant species in
 665 South African National Parks (Table S2.5). See Appendix 3 for the data that were collected and Table
 666 S2.6 for a summary of the values for the indicator for the first and second reports.

667 **Table S2.5** The pathways through which 137 transformer alien plant species have dispersed into and
 668 within South African National Parks. Many species dispersed through multiple pathways. Data were
 669 obtained from Foxcroft et al. (2019).

Pathway of dispersal	Percentage of species
Ornamental plants	78
Rivers	63
Animal dispersed	48
Roads, paths, trails and tracks	~40
Agriculture	~30
Contaminated construction equipment, materials or soils	~30
Clothing	< 10
Food or produce	< 10

670
 671 **S2.9 Estimation of high-level indicator—Rate of unregulated introduction of new species**

672 There were 32 known unregulated introductions of new taxa to South Africa between 2010 and
 673 2019, an average of 3.2 per year (Figure 2.2B in the main report).

674 As in the first report, the data used to determine Introduction rates were used to calculate the number
675 of unregulated introductions of new taxa introduced to South Africa each year during the last full
676 decade (2010-2019). The average rate of introduction for the decade was then calculated. This
677 indicator includes all known alien taxa introduced to South Africa in the last full decade, except
678 biological control agents.

679 Other than biological control releases, between November 2014 and September 2019, import permits
680 were issued for six taxa that were not listed under the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations as present in the
681 country [Mediterranean Green Crab (*Carcinus aestuarii*); St Paul rock lobster (*Jasus paulensis*);
682 barramundi (*Lates calcarifer*); coho salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*); Chinook salmon (*Oncorhynchus*
683 *tshawytscha*); Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*); see Appendix 6]. Of these *S. salar* was already recorded
684 as present in the country, and the permit for *C. aestuarii* was to import samples for genetic research
685 (and not live individuals). It is not known if the import permits for the other four species have been
686 used [*J. paulensis* (permits issued in 2016), *L. calcarifer* (permit issued in 2016), *O. kisutch* (permits
687 issued in 2015, 2016, and 2018), *O. tshawytscha* (permit issued in 2015)].

688 See Table S2.6 for a summary of the values for the indicator for the first and second reports. Important
689 to note that results presented in the second report for this high-level indicator are not comparable to
690 those presented in the first report. This is as the decade assessed in the second report (2010-2019)
691 differs from that assessed in the first report (2000-2009).

692

693 **Table S2.6** A summary of the values for the indicators for reporting on the status of the introduction and dispersal pathways in South Africa, 2017-2019. The
694 values presented for the first report have been revised based on data that were available in 2016 or earlier but that were not included in the first report.
695 Please note that Introduction rates at a moderate level (i.e. Indicator 2.2) was calculated for the first report by comparing the number of introductions that
696 occurred during the decades 1990-1999 and 2000-2009, but in the second report introductions during the decades 2000-2009 and 2010-2019 were compared.
697 Similarly, the high-level indicator Rate of unregulated introduction of new species, was calculated for the first report for the period 2000-2009, and for the
698 period 2010-2019 for the second report.

Indicator		2016 value (revised baseline)	2019 value	Confidence	Notes
1. <i>Introduction pathway prominence</i>	1.1. Five categories demonstrating the size of each pathway	Not known: 12 pathways Pathway not present: 1 pathway Minor: 6 pathways Moderate: 13 pathways Major: 12 pathways	Not known: 9 pathways Pathway not present: 1 pathway Minor: 7 pathways Moderate: 16 pathways Major: 11 pathways	Medium	Evaluation by one expert
2. <i>Introduction rates</i>	2.1. The total number of alien taxa introduced through each pathway over all time	0 taxa: 5 pathways 1 – 50 taxa: 31 pathways 51 – 100 taxa: 4 pathways > 100 taxa: 4 pathways	0 taxa: 5 pathways 1 – 50 taxa: 31 pathways 51 – 100 taxa: 4 pathways > 100 taxa: 4 pathways	Low	Pathway of introduction data are not available or have not been collated for many alien taxa in South Africa
	2.2. Five categories demonstrating changes in the number of taxa introduced through each pathway in the last full decade in comparison to the previous decade	Increase: 1 pathway Decrease: 1 pathway Minimal change: 13 pathways No introductions: 10 pathways Not known: 19 pathways	Increase: 2 pathway Decrease: 1 pathway Minimal change: 9 pathways No introductions: 10 pathways Not known: 22 pathways	Low	Pathway and date of introduction data are not available or have not been collated for many alien taxa in South Africa
3. <i>Within-country pathway prominence</i>	3.1. Five categories demonstrating the size of each pathway	Data not available	Data not available	Not Applicable	Data were only collected for a few pathways

Indicator		2016 value (revised baseline)	2019 value	Confidence	Notes
<i>4. Within-country dispersal rates</i>	4.1. The total number of alien taxa dispersing through each pathway over all time	Data not available	Data not available	Not Applicable	Pathway of dispersal data have not been collated for alien and native taxa at a country level and examples were only collected for 22 of the 44 pathways
<i>A. Rate of unregulated introduction of new species</i>	Number of unregulated introductions of new species per year	5 per year	3 per year	Low	Date of introduction data are not available for many alien taxa in South Africa, and there are time delays between the introduction of a taxon, when it is detected, and the publication of a report of the introduction

700 **Supplementary Material to Chapter 3: Species**

701 **S3.1 Background notes**

702 This chapter provides an assessment of alien species that are known to occur in South Africa. It
 703 provides an update of the number and status of alien species that were published in the first report.
 704 The indicators used are *Number and status of alien species* (i.e. whether they are known to be present
 705 in South Africa and their stage of invasion); the *Extent of alien species* (at national, provincial, biome,
 706 or other scales); the *Abundance of alien species status* (in terms of their cover, biomass, or population
 707 sizes); and the *Impact of alien species* (the degree to which alien species have impacts). See Wilson et
 708 al. 2018 for further details. Data for updating the indicators was obtained from various sources and
 709 these include: research papers and reviews, books, academic theses, published following the release
 710 of the first status report; and databases and atlases of alien species occurring in the country (see
 711 Appendices 1 and 2)

712 The focus of this chapter is on administrative and biogeographical regions, however, it is also valuable
 713 to consider other more thematic methods of dividing sites, e.g. invasions in wetlands, harbours,
 714 agricultural systems, or urban sites (see Box 4.1 in the report).

715 **Table S3.1** A summary of the reasons for changes made to the indicator values on the number and
 716 status of alien species in South Africa, 2017 – 2019.

Reason for difference	Number of changes
Data were collected in the first report but these are not relevant for the second report	32
Data were collected in the first report but need to be reinterpreted for the second report	8
Data were collected in the first report but there was no change in the values for the second report	14
Data collected for the second report indicate the value has changed since the first report	38
Data collected for the second report where no data were available in the first report	64
Grand Total	218

717

718 **Introduction status**

719 **Table S3.2** The introduction status categories used in this report based on the unified framework of
 720 Blackburn et al. (2011) and grouped into four high level descriptors

Presence in South Africa	High level introduction status	Detailed description according to the Blackburn et al. 2011
Absent	Not introduced or eradicated	A0-A1: there is no indication of any individuals in what would be considered an alien range OR if it is not evaluated

Presence in South Africa	High level introduction status	Detailed description according to the Blackburn et al. 2011
Present	Present as alien but not naturalised	B1–C2: includes a range of species from those in quarantine to those that are reproducing outside of captivity or cultivation but where there is no clear evidence of having formed self-sustaining populations
	Naturalised but not invasive	C3–D1: species where there is naturalisation
	Invasive	D2–E: populations are self-sustaining a significant distance from the introduction site

721

722 **S3.2 Extent of alien species**

723 There have been some changes in the extent of alien species that has been noted from alien species
724 databases (e.g. SAPIA 2019) and literature (e.g., for crayfish (Nunes et al. 2017a, b, c) and fish species
725 (Khosa et al. 2018, Marr et al. 2018) between 2016 and 2019, but these are not included here as they
726 are not yet reflected in the GBIF records. For example several plant species have expanded their range,
727 for example eight-seeded prostrate starbu (*Acanthospermum austral*) and field bindweed
728 (*Convolvulus arvensis*). For some species the observed increase in range might be the result of under
729 reporting prior to 2016 e.g. Kikuyu grass (*Pennisetum clandestinum*) or as occurrence data needed to
730 be reinterpreted [e.g. there was a taxonomic revision such that *Azolla cristata* (= *A. microphylla*, *A.*
731 *mexicana*)]. There are a few plant species whose ranges have probably decreased due to biological
732 control e.g. azolla (*Azolla filiculoides*) and boxing-glove cactus (*Cylindropuntia fulgida* var. *mamillata*).
733 Such decreases were not considered in the first report, and so it cannot be inferred that such declines
734 happened in the period 2017–2019.

735 **S3.3 Abundance**

736 Two sources of data were used to estimate the abundance of terrestrial plants in the first report — a
737 1998 report to the Water Research Commission (Versfeld et. al. 1998) and the National Invasive Alien
738 Plant Survey (NIAPS) (Kotzé et al. 2010). A major limitation of the Versfeld et al. (1998) survey was
739 that it was based on expert knowledge, data sources of different spatial scales were combined, and
740 final results not having any form of accuracy assessment. These concerns still hold, and so the
741 estimates have a low degree of confidence associated with them.

742 The objective of NIAPS was to establish a scientific rigorous and practical implementable monitoring
743 system of major invasive plant species at a national level. The NIAPS approach and survey results were
744 initially published as a report (Kotzé et al. 2010) and spatial distribution data were made available to

745 the public the same year on the Working for Water Planning website
 746 (<https://sites.google.com/site/wfwplanning/assessment>) and the SANBI's Biodiversity Geographic
 747 Information System website (<http://bgis.sanbi.org/Projects/Detail/162>). However, the first report
 748 noted that NIAPS had partial coverage that did not include large proportions of the country, and the
 749 methodology on which the survey was based was not adequately documented.

750 **Table S3.3** The number and occurrence status of alien species in South Africa as of December 2019.
 751 Occurrence status was grouped into four categories using the following descriptors: 1) absent—a
 752 reasoned analysis of the evidence suggests the taxon is not present in South Africa; 2) present—there
 753 is evidence to document the presence of the taxon in South Africa as of December 2019; and 3) not
 754 evaluated—there has been no specific attempt to ascertain if the taxon is in (or has been in) South
 755 Africa.

Regulatory grouping	Absent	Present	Not evaluated
Amphibians	9	21	0
Birds	26	94	0
Freshwater fish	72	32	0
Marine fish	1	0	0
Freshwater invertebrates	8	49	2
Marine invertebrates	11	89	0
Terrestrial invertebrates	124	439	183
Mammals	16	51	0
Microbes	6	114	0
Freshwater and terrestrial plants	237	927	3
Marine plants	3	8	
Reptiles	42	56	72
Total	597	1880	260

756 **Table S3.4** Species alien to South Africa (not necessary present in South Africa) that have global or
 757 national (South African) Environmental Impact Classification for Alien Taxa (EICAT) assessments.

Geographic scope	Taxon	Data deficient	Minimal Concern	Minor	Moderate	Major	Massive	Total
Global	Grasses	3	3	17	21	2	1	47
	Invertebrates	27	0	9	0	0	0	36
	Gastropods	8	2	12	8	4	0	34
	Amphibians	15	3	0	1	2	0	21
	Birds	13	6	3	9	2	0	33
	Mammals	1	0	0	0	3	8	12
South Africa	Fish	16	0	0	0	4	1	21
	Grasses	5	0	2	2	2	0	11
Total		88	14	43	41	19	10	215

758

759

760 **Table S3.5** Species alien to South Africa (not necessary present in South Africa) that have global or
 761 national (South African) Socio-Economic Classification of Alien Taxa Scheme (SEICAT) assessments.
 762 84 species have been assessed and 43% have been found to be data deficient

Geographic scope	Taxon	Data deficient	Minimal Concern	Minor	Moderate	Major	Massive	Total
Global	Amphibians	2	0	1	0	0	0	3
	Invertebrates	22	2	10	2			36
South Africa	Gastropods	12	2	17	3	0	0	34
	Mammals	0	0	3	7	1	0	11
Total		36	4	31	12	1	0	84

763

764 **S3.4 Methodology for developing a national checklist of alien species and obtaining associated**
 765 **occurrence data**

766 The method for developing a national checklist was adapted from the Tracking Invasive Alien Species
 767 Project (TriAS, <https://osf.io/7dpgr/>) (Oldoni 2020).

768 *Study extent.* This checklist includes all alien species that have evidence to document their presence
 769 in South Africa as of December 2019 as per the sources in Table S3.6. It covers 2717 unique taxa from
 770 five kingdoms: Plantae (1176 taxa), Animalia (1409), Fungi (107 taxa), Chromista (19 taxa), Protozoa
 771 (2 taxa), and Viruses (1 taxon). This number of species is expected to increase with future updates. All
 772 taxonomic information is provided by the GBIF Backbone Taxonomy
 773 (<https://doi.org/10.15468/39omei>).

774 **Table S3.6** Sources used as evidence that a species is present in South Africa. The full references are
 775 not provided in this document (unless they are cited elsewhere). They are, however, available in
 776 Appendix 2.

Regulatory Category	References
Various	Listed as an invasive species on the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations of 2016; is recorded on the first report (SANBI & CIB 2018); a permit has been issued by DFFtE permitting importation (see Appendix 6)
Amphibians	van Rensburg et al. 2011; Grève et al. 2017; Measey et al. 2020; John Measey (personal communication);
Birds	Southern Africa Bird Atlas Project 2 (SABAP2) (http://sabap2.birdmap.africa/); Macdonald et al. 1986; Dyer et al. 2017; Faulkner et al. 2017a; Picker and Griffiths 2017; Rob Little (personal communication), John Measey (personal communication).
Freshwater fish	De Moor & Bruton 1988; Picker & Griffiths 2011; van Rensburg et al. 2011; Ellender and Weyl 2014; Marr et al. 2017; Weyl et al. 2020.
Freshwater invertebrates	Albany Museum 2019; Appleton 1986; Appleton 2003; Kaiser et al. 2006; De Moor & Bruton 1988; Klein 2011; Picker & Griffiths 2011; du Preez and Smit 2013; Appleton & Miranda 2015; Bush et al. 2016; Janion- Scheepers et al. 2016; Nunes et al. 2017; Smit et al. 2017; Tavakol 2017; Zachariades 2018; Faulkner et al. 2020a; Weyl et al. 2020.
Marine invertebrates	Mead et al. 2011; Picker & Griffiths 2011; Griffiths 2018; Peters & Robinson 2018; Robison et al. 2020; Tamara Robinson (personal communication).

Regulatory Category	References
Terrestrial invertebrates	Agricultural Research Council-Plant Protection Research Institute 2017; Tooke 1955; Gess 1964; De Moor and Bruton 1988; Appleton 2003; Nofemela & Kfir 2005; Hurley et al. 2007; Cervera et al. 2010; Herbert 2010; Klein 2011; Mead et al. 2011; Picker and Griffiths 2011; Treasure and Chown 2013; Appleton & Miranda 2015; Manrakhan et al. 2015; Minnaar et al. 2014; Nesamari et al. 2015; Prinsloo & Uys 2015; Janion-Scheepers et al. 2016; Rowson et al. 2016; Greeve et al. 2017; Hurley et al. 2017; Janion-Scheepers et al. 2017; Visser et al. 2017; Zachariades et al. 2017; Bromilow 2018; Griffiths et al. 2018; Paap et al. 2018; Wood 2017; Visser et al. 2018; Zachariades 2018; Zachariades 2019; Davies et al. 2020; Faulkner et al. 2020a; Hill et al. 2020; Janion-Scheepers & Griffiths 2020; Robinson et al. 2020; Schroder et al. 2020; Weyl et al. 2020; Dai Herbert (personal communication), Ruan Veldtman (personal communication).
Mammals	Deacon 1986; Watkins & Cooper 1986; Blench 2004; Huffman 2007; van Rensburg et al. 2011; Greeve et al. 2017; Picker & Griffiths 2017; Faulkner et al. 2020a.
Microbes	Ndlovu et al. 2013; Julius et al. 2015a, b; Janion-Scheepers et al. 2016; Haelewaters et al. 2016; Greeve et al. 2017; Janion-Scheepers et al. 2016; Le Roux et al. 2016; Zengeya et al. 2017; Zachariades et al. 2017; Wood 2017; Paap et al. 2018; Warrington et al. 2019.
Terrestrial and Freshwater plants	Botanical Database of Southern Africa (BODATSA) (http://posa.sanbi.org/); Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas (SAPIA); Henderson 1983; Deacon 1986; Avis 1989; Steinschen et al. 1996; Milton & Dean 2010; Mead et al. 2011; Klein 2011; Nesamari et al. 2015; Prinsloo & Uys 2015; Greeve et al. 2017; Geerts et al. 2017; Faulkner et al. 2017a; Henderson and Wilson 2017; Visser et al. 2017; Bromilow 2018; Holmes et al. 2018; Magona et al. 2018; Potgieter et al. 2020; Robinson et al. 2020; Van Wilgen et al. 2020a.
Marine plants	Mead et al. 2011; Robinson et al. 2016; Robinson et al. 2020; Tamara Robinson (personal communication).
Reptiles	Picker and Griffiths 2011; van Rensburg et al. 2011; Greeve et al. 2017; Rebelo et al. 2019; Measey et al. 2020; Measey data?

777

778 These sources record the presence of alien species in South Africa for a specific taxon group or habitat
779 and are maintained by their respective authors. The data processing consists of the extraction of all
780 alien taxa in South Africa from these sources and the unification of their taxonomy (using the GBIF
781 Backbone Taxonomy, <https://doi.org/10.15468/39omei>) and related information.

782 As far as possible pathway of introduction and date of first record data, as well as the sources for these
783 data, have been added to the species list (Appendix 2), however, further work is required (see
784 Appendix 1 for all data sources).

785 *Quality control.* Several steps were taken to verify checklists that were used to compile the checklist
786 of alien species that are known to occur in South Africa. These include:

787 *Steps*

- 788 1. Compile a list of alien species that are known to be present in South Africa based on
789 documented evidence.
- 790 2. Retrieve the GBIF Backbone Taxonomy information assigned for each taxon, as well as their
791 originally published distribution, species profile and description information.

- 792 3. Any taxon names that are returned as synonyms by the GBIF Backbone Taxonomy are then
 793 manually processed, i.e. accepting or rejecting the lumping of taxa that differ in their scientific
 794 name but can be considered the same within or across checklists. A record of these decisions
 795 is on file.
- 796 4. Unify taxa within and across checklists to get a list of unique taxa and append higher
 797 classification information using the GBIF Backbone Taxonomy.
- 798 5. Retrieve occurrence records of alien species in South Africa from the GBIF API based on the
 799 alien species list developed. We acknowledge that not all documented occurrence records of
 800 alien species in South Africa are yet reflected on the GBIF platform. SANBI is in the process of
 801 developing a national registry of alien species in the country and as part of the process,
 802 distribution records of alien species in the country will be documented and this will then be
 803 used to update the information on the GBIF platform.

804 **S3.5 Indicators**

805 Currently as per the executive summary

	Indicator	Current status	Trend	Confidence
Species	5. Number and status of alien species	Increase in the number of alien species in the country but their status (invasiveness) needs to be assessed	↗	Low
	6. Extent of alien species	6.1. 59- 281 alien species per province; 6.2 Many species have limited distribution (qdg-scale) and a few are widespread 6.3 Range size for each species: No data	↗	Low
	7. Abundance of alien	7.1. No data 7.2. No data 7.3. No data	Not assessed	
	8. Impact of alien species	8.1. Data deficient: 28; Minimal Concern: 14; Minor: 42; Moderate: 41; Major: 20; Massive: 10. 8.2. No data	→	Medium

806

807 **S3.6 Estimation of high-level indicator—Number of invasive species that have major impacts**

808 Currently as per the executive summary

Trend	Current Status
Not assessed	Few studies have formally measured impact, and this remains a major gap where detailed research is needed. Only about 5% of the alien species recorded in this report have been assessed in a manner similar to that of the IUCN’s Environmental Impact Classification of Alien Taxa (EICAT) scheme, of which only 7 species are reported to cause major to severe impacts in South Africa. These numbers will increase as more impact assessments are conducted.

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810

811 **Supplementary Material to Chapter 4: Sites**

812 **S4.1 Alien species richness**

813 Alien species richness can be tracked at a range of scales, e.g. for the country as a whole, or at
814 increasingly finer scales for subdivisions of the country. While it is important to get an accurate
815 inventory of the distribution of alien species across the country [not least as this is essential to
816 estimate the invasion threat that South Africa faces, i.e. invasion debt, Rouget et al. (2014)], such
817 inventories only exist for small areas and for particular taxa [e.g. recent efforts to compile
818 comprehensive lists of alien plants in a small town (McLean et al. 2018) and in National Parks (Baard
819 and Kraaij 2019; Cheney et al. 2019)]. Therefore, species richness can only be reliably estimated for
820 invasive species. Nonetheless, estimates from the first report included all alien species. As such, a new
821 baseline had to be calculated for 2016 that shows the number of species present as of 2016 that are
822 invasive.

823 *Invasive species richness*

824 Terrestrial invasive species richness was calculated for large administrative regions (provinces of
825 mainland South Africa, and the Prince Edward Islands), as well as for large biogeographical regions
826 (i.e. biomes of mainland South Africa, not including the biomes of the Prince Edward Islands). The
827 richness of freshwater invasive species was calculated for the Water Management Areas (WMAs) as
828 defined by the Department of Water and Sanitation (RSA 2016), and the marine ecoregions as defined
829 by Sink et al. (2011) were used for marine invasive species. The species list on which the estimates of
830 richness are based has been carefully checked, and only species for which a reliable record and a
831 collection date are available have been included. This has resulted in a new baseline from which
832 change can be tracked (e.g. more care has been taken to ensure that the listing of species as invasive
833 is based on sound information, resulting in the removal of some species from the inventory of invasive
834 species recorded in the first report). Additional species have also been added to the list, and these
835 additions may either reflect genuine changes (i.e. the species is a new arrival), or they may be species
836 that have been present for some time, but that have been overlooked.

837 **Table S4.1** Invasive species richness per province for different regulatory groupings. The totals for each group are not the same as the total for South Africa
 838 as a whole because: 1) taxa are in multiple provinces; 2) data might be available at a South Africa level, but they not at a provincial level; and 3) not all data
 839 available on invasive species present in South Africa have been incorporated into GBIF or SAPIA.

	Eastern Cape	Free State	Gauteng	KwaZulu-Natal	Limpopo	Mpumalanga	North West	Northern Cape	Western Cape
Amphibians	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Birds	5	3	7	8	6	9	2	2	5
Terrestrial invertebrates	19	10	15	21	8	28	7	5	25
Microbe	0	0	1	2	1	2	0	0	0
Mammals	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Freshwater and terrestrial plants	123	74	108	152	90	170	72	56	153
Reptiles	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Total	148	88	133	184	106	210	81	64	186

840 **Table S4.2** Invasive species richness per biome for different regulatory groupings. The totals for each group are not the same as the total for South Africa as
 841 a whole because: 1) taxa are in multiple biomes; 2) data might be available at a South Africa level, but they not at a provincial level; and 3) not all data available
 842 on invasive species present in South Africa have been incorporated into GBIF or SAPIA.

	Albany Thicket	Desert	Forests	Fynbos	Grassland	Indian Ocean Coastal Belt	Nama-Karoo	Savanna	Succulent Karoo
Amphibians	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1
Birds	4	0	1	6	10	8	1	12	3
Terrestrial invertebrates	9	0	0	31	22	14	7	25	4
Mammals	1	0	0	1	2	1	1	2	0
Microbes	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	2	0
Freshwater and terrestrial plants	94	9	9	210	194	132	67	199	47
Reptiles	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
Total	108	9	10	251	230	156	76	241	55

843

844 **Table S4.3** Invasive species richness per Water Management Area. Note that catchment areas
 845 arguably have more biogeographical meaning than the Water Management Areas (WMA), and while
 846 most of the primary catchments fall within a single WMA, some primary catchments fall within several
 847 WMAs.

Water Management Areas	Freshwater Fish	Freshwater invertebrate	Total
A- Limpopo	3	1	4
B-Olifants North	2	0	2
C-Vaal	2	0	2
D-Orange	2	1	3
E-Olifants West	2	0	2
F-Buffels	0	0	0
G-Berg	3	0	3
H-Breede	1	0	1
J-Gouritz	1	0	1
K-Kroom	2	0	2
L-Gamtoos	2	0	2
M-Swartkops	2	0	2
N-Sundays	1	0	1
P-Bushmans	0	0	0
Q-Great Fish	1	1	2
R-Keiskamma	2	0	2
S-Kei	3	1	4
T-Mzimvubu	2	0	2
U-Mkomazi	2	0	2
V-Tugela	3	1	4
W-Mfolozi	3	0	3
X-Komati	3	1	4

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850 **A) Invasive birds**

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853 **B) Invasive plants**

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855

856 **Figure S4.1** Invasive species richness for A) birds and B) plants up to end 2016, up to end 2019, and the change 2017–2019. A map of invasive animal species
 857 richness was presented in the first report based on Picker & Griffiths (2017), but no update of these data was available, and so this is not presented here.

858 **Supplementary Material to Chapter 5: Interventions**

859 **S5.1 Background notes**

860 SANBI is required to provide an assessment of the effectiveness of regulations based on section
861 11(2)(b) of the Alien and Invasive Species Regulations of 2014 that were promulgated under the
862 National Environmental Biodiversity Act (NEM:BA) (Act 10 of 2004) (see Section 1.3, Chapter 1). While
863 the term ‘effectiveness’ is not defined, it is clear from the context that at least part of the summary
864 and assessment of the effectiveness of the regulations entails an analysis of how the A&IS Regulations
865 have been interpreted. In other words, SANBI is required to give a summary and assessment of the
866 outputs yielded from the implementation of the A&IS Regulations.

867 The use of the term ‘inter alia’ in regulation 11(2)(b) suggests that the summary and analysis of the
868 effectiveness of the regulations entails more than just tracking how the A&IS Regulations have been
869 implemented. Ordinarily, measuring the effectiveness of a regulatory regime entails an analysis of
870 how that regulatory regime has changed behaviour in order to achieve certain outcomes. In other
871 words, it requires evidence of causal links between the promulgation of the regulations and
872 behavioural change, and between behavioural change and the current state of affairs. Such an analysis
873 would be a complex undertaking requiring a multidisciplinary team of natural and social scientists, as
874 well as the development of indicators for measuring success. Since there are no indicators in law or
875 policy for measuring the success of the A&IS Regulations, and no literature on the effectiveness of
876 those regulations, no attempt was made in Chapter 5 to discuss the outcomes attributed to the
877 implementation of the A&IS Regulations.

878 However, comments are made on the quality of the regulatory framework in this chapter. The quality
879 of a regulatory regime is determined with reference to comparative legal studies and judicial
880 precedent. There is no jurisprudence or comparative legal studies that are directly applicable to the
881 A&IS Regulations, but analogous jurisprudence, Acts and academic literature have been drawn from
882 to inform the comments.

883 Given that the A&IS Regulations form part of the National Environmental Management: Biodiversity
884 Act, 2004 (Act 10 of 2004) (NEM:BA) (the definition of ‘this Act’ in section 1 of NEM:BA), relevant
885 provisions of NEM:BA are also considered as part of the assessment in this chapter. The Alien and
886 Invasive Species Lists, 2016 (published under Government Notice 864 in Government Gazette 40166
887 of 29 July 2016) (A&IS Lists) also form part of the assessment. No changes were made to NEM:BA, the
888 A&IS Regulations or the A&IS Lists between the first and second reports. However, the Minister
889 published her notice of intention to amend the A&IS Regulations and A&IS Lists (published under

890 Government Notices 112 and 115 in Government Gazette 41445 of 16 February 2018) (Proposed
891 Amended A&IS Regulations). Proposed changes to the provisions dealing with the alien and invasive
892 species are also proposed in the National Environmental Management Laws Amendment Bill, 2017
893 (B14-2017) (NEMLAB), which, as of July 2020, is being processed by Parliament.

894 This chapter is limited in scope to the NEM:BA and the A&IS Regulations, i.e. the effectiveness of other
895 legislation that deals with the management of alien and invasive species is not considered, but the
896 role of the Department of Agriculture, Rural Development and Land Reform, the Department of Water
897 and Sanitation and the Department of Transport in the management of alien and invasive species will
898 be discussed briefly below. Regulation 11(2)(b) of the A&IS Regulations provides that an assessment
899 and summary of the effectiveness of the A&IS Regulations must be based on *inter alia* notifications
900 received from owners of land regarding listed alien species occurring on their land; permits issued for
901 listed alien species; Invasive Species Monitoring, Control and Eradication Plans from organs of state
902 and management authorities of protected areas; and emergency interventions and enforcement
903 actions involving listed alien species issued by the Minister. Most of those sources of data were
904 obtained from the Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries (DFFtE) and are considered as
905 part of the assessment in this chapter. Notifications received from owners of land regarding listed
906 alien species occurring on their land and information regarding emergency interventions were not
907 available at the time of writing. Additional sources of information were also considered, including
908 relevant government publications, academic literature, and court papers.

909 The NEM:BA Invasive & Alien Species Regulations (section 11) also call for “*a summary and assessment*
910 *of [inter alia] the effectiveness of ... control measures*”. Control measures are understood to be any
911 active intervention aimed at prevention, eradication, containment (or more generally reducing rates
912 of spread), and impact reduction. The effectiveness of control needs to be assessed for pathway-
913 related control measures, species-specific control measures, and site-specific control measures.

914 Chapter 5 provides an update of the assessment made in the first report (SANBI and CIB 2018). The
915 assessment is based on new information that has become available since the compilation of the first
916 report, or from sources that were not included in the first report. In the first report, it was found that
917 the required monitoring data to make reliable assessments were largely absent, so that the
918 assessment had to rely heavily on a limited number of research projects or published reviews. This
919 situation has not changed.

920 **S5.2 Quality of the regulation framework**

921 The legal listing categories of the NEM:BA Invasive & Alien Species Regulations are:

- 922 ● Category 1a species are those targeted for national eradication
- 923 ● Category 1b species must be controlled as part of a national management programme, and
924 cannot be traded or otherwise allowed to spread
- 925 ● Category 2 species are the same as category 1b species, except that permits can be issued for
926 their usage (e.g. invasive tree species can still be used in commercial forestry provided that a
927 permit is issued that specifies where they may be grown and that permit holders “*must ensure*
928 *that the specimens of the species do not spread outside of the land or the area specified in the*
929 *permit*”).
- 930 ● Category 3 are invasive species that can be kept without permits, although they may not be
931 traded or further propagated, and must be controlled if they occur in protected areas or
932 riparian zones. In essence, this is for species that are being phased out—e.g., feature trees can
933 be kept (as it is too costly and unpopular to remove them), but they may not be replaced.

934 The term ‘pathway’ is defined in regulation 1 of the A&IS Regulations as “*the route by which a*
935 *specimen of an alien or listed invasive species is transported, introduced into, dispersed or spread*
936 *within the Republic, whether by natural, unnatural, deliberate or inadvertent means or by an act of*
937 *omission*” (cf. the Glossary to this report).

938 Notably the lists largely rely on the species concept. But, for example, taxonomists have raised
939 concerns about the implementation of laws relating to the management of alien ‘species’ in nurseries
940 (e.g. Spencer and Cross, 2004) and the pet trade (Nelufule, 2018). Horticulturalists and those in the
941 pet trade often apply naming conventions that differ from conventional scientific names. As a result,
942 listed alien species may be traded to the unsuspecting public. In addition, different naming
943 conventions are also applied to hybrid taxa. The term ‘species’ is defined in section 1 of NEM:BA to
944 include “*any... hybrid*”. Where a label of a hybrid plant species does not specify the hybrid species’
945 parentage, it is difficult for most purchasers to determine whether or not a particular hybrid species
946 is a listed alien species. This can be addressed by requiring sellers to inform buyers that a plant is a
947 listed alien species, including a hybrid species with listed alien species parentage.

948 **S5.3 National Environmental Management Laws Amendment Bill, 2017 [B14-2017]**

949 The Legislature proposes to address the problem of fairness and justness in NEM:BA by making some
950 changes to the Act. The proposed amendments are: 1) remove the provisions requiring landowners to
951 notify the competent authority of the presence of listed alien species on his or her property; 2) the
952 general duty to take steps to “*control and eradicate the listed invasive species and to prevent it from*
953 *spreading*” is circumscribed to taking steps to “*control or eradicate the listed invasive species as*
954 *prescribed by the Minister [in regulations]*”; and 3) to insert a provision requiring the Minister to
955 “*provide for education and awareness of listed invasive species*”. It is envisaged that education and
956 awareness may improve the perception of fairness of the law as it has the potential to apprise

957 landowners of their duties in relation to invasive species on their property and to raise awareness of
958 the dangers invasive species pose to biodiversity.

959 **S5.4 Risk analysis, risk assessment, and evaluations of risk**

960 Throughout this report the definitions concerning risk align with those of the Convention on
961 Biodiversity (CBD) and the International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC) (Kumschick et al. 2020;
962 Figure S5.1). However, the NEM:BA and its A&IS Regulations use the terms ‘analysis’ and ‘assessment’
963 inconsistently, in places confounding risk assessment and risk analysis.

964

965 **Figure S5.1** The components of risk analysis. ‘Hazard identification’ frames the problem that is being
966 addressed (with respect to biological invasions this is often in terms of pathways, species, or sites, it
967 is not shown in the figure). ‘Risk assessment’ focuses on the likelihood and consequences of the
968 hazard occurring. ‘Risk management’ considers ways to mitigate the risks while maintaining any
969 benefits. And finally ‘risk communication’ aims to ensure effective communication and sharing of
970 relevant information between stakeholders and assessors during the process of risk assessment and
971 management, both to improve the information available for the risk analysis and to try to ensure
972 that everyone ultimately agrees to abide by the outcome of the process. Figure and legend
973 reproduced from Figure 20.1 of Kumschick et al. (2020).

974 The risk analysis of alien taxa framework (Kumschick et al. 2018) and the Alien Species Risk Analysis
975 Panel (ASRARP) adopted the definitions of the CBD given the inconsistencies in terms used in the Act
976 and the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations. The evaluations of risk are highlighted in terms of the court case
977 “*Fly-fishers Association of Southern Africa v Minister of Environmental Affairs*”, which included
978 information required by the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations. However, it was not clear in these evaluations
979 how the likelihood and consequences (i.e. the risk) of an invasion was determined, so they were not
980 obviously a risk analysis as contemplated in the CBD’s definition (cf. Figure S5.1).

981 The specific reasons for the mismatches between the recommendations of the risk analyses and the
982 current listings (Table S5.1) are because of: uncertainty as to whether the species is present in South

983 Africa [coypu (*Mycocastor coypus*), and Dwarf Yellow-striped Bamboo (*Sasa ramosa*)]; field
 984 evaluations that have found the species to be unsuitable targets for eradication (i.e. they should be in
 985 category 1b and not 1a) because they are either widespread or are in people's gardens [tickseed
 986 (*Coreopsis lanceolata*), yellow flag (*Iris pseudacorus*), red-flowering tea tree (*Melaleuca hypericifolia*),
 987 tussock paspalum (*Paspalum quadrifarium*), and delta arrowhead (*Sagittaria platyphylla*)]; the species
 988 is native [e.g. Indian prawn (*Penaeus indicus*)]; there is provision for regulating the species but no
 989 permits have been issued and the benefit the species provide to South Africa are unclear [physic nut
 990 (*Jatropha curcas*)]; and contested species where the likelihood that regulatory interventions will be
 991 effective in limiting future impacts is low [rose-ringed parakeet (*Psittacula krameri*), and red-vented
 992 bulbul (*Pycnonotus cafer*)]. One species that is currently not listed was recommended to be listed
 993 [Australian tree fern (*Sphaeropteris cooperi*)]. This mismatch between the recommendations and the
 994 lists is of concern, although it in part reflects which species were chosen to complete risk analyses on
 995 (there was a focus on contested species or where it was felt that a change in listing was required).

996 **Table S5.1** Risk analyses (as per the definition in Figure S5.1) approved by the Alien Species Risk
 997 Analysis Review Panel as of end December 2019 and their current and recommended listings. Current
 998 listing is as per the NEM:BA A&IS Lists of 2014 as revised in 2016. Details of permit conditions
 999 (including cases where the listing varies depending on specific conditions, e.g. for *Oreochromis*
 1000 *niloticus*) are not shown.

Scientific Name	Current listing	Recommended listing
<i>Acarapis woodi</i> (Rennie, 1921)	1b	1b
<i>Ageratina adenophora</i> (Spreng.) R.M.King & H.Rob. (= <i>Eupatorium adenophorum</i> Spreng.)	1b	1b
<i>Carausius morosus</i> Sinety, 1901 [listed under Phasmatodea species (Jacobson and Blanchi, 1902)]	1b (as all Phasmatodea species (Jacobson and Blanchi, 1902))	1b (as <i>Carausius morosus</i> Sinety, 1901)
<i>Chondrilla juncea</i> L.	1a	1a
<i>Coreopsis lanceolata</i> L.	a. 1a b. Sterile cultivars or hybrids are not listed	a. 1b [Whether sterile cultivars or hybrids should not be listed was not analysed in this report]
<i>Crassostrea gigas</i> (Thunberg 1793)	2	2
<i>Iris pseudacorus</i> L.	1a	1b
<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	2	1b
<i>Lilium formosanum</i> Wallace (= <i>L. longiflorum</i> Thunb. var. <i>formosanum</i> Baker)	1b	1b
<i>Melaleuca hypericifolia</i> Sm.	1a	1b
<i>Myocastor coypus</i> (Molina, 1872)	2	Prohibited
<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i> Lamarck, 1819	2	2
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	2	2
<i>Paspalum quadrifarium</i> (Lam 1791)	1a	1b
<i>Penaeus indicus</i> H. Milne-Edwards, 1837 [listed as <i>Fenneropenaeus indicus</i> (H. Milne-Edwards, 1837)]	2	Delist
<i>Psidium cattleianum</i> Afzel. ex Sabine	1b	1b

Scientific Name	Current listing	Recommended listing
<i>Psittacula krameri</i> (Scopoli, 1769)	2	1b
<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	2	1a
<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	2	2
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L.	1b	1b
<i>Sagittaria platyphylla</i> (Engelmann) J.G Smith	1a	1b
<i>Sasa ramosa</i> (Makino) Makino & Shibata	3	Delist
<i>Senna bicapsularis</i> (L.) Roxb	1b	1b
<i>Sphaeropteris cooperi</i> (F. Muell.) R.M. Tryon	Not listed	1b
<i>Vespula germanica</i> (Fabricius, 1973)	1b	1b

1001

1002 Evaluations of risk were provided by DFFtE in 2018 in support of the proposed changes to the
1003 regulatory lists for eleven taxa—four out of the 39 new taxa proposed for listing and an additional
1004 seven taxa which were already listed [species already listed indicated by an asterisk, note *Cestrum* is
1005 listed as a genus: giant African snail (*Achatina fulica*), *night cestrum (*Cestrum nocturnum*), *day
1006 cestrum (*Cestrum diurnum*), * early cestrum (*Cestrum fasciculatum*), * Madagascar red fody (*Foudia*
1007 *madagascariensis*), *diamond Phytton (*Morelia spilota*), * white mulberry (*Morus alba*), black mulberry
1008 (*Morus nigra*), rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), * Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), signal
1009 crayfish (*Pacifastacus leniusculus*), and brown trout (*Salmo trutta*)]. The evaluations provide similar
1010 regulatory recommendations to those that were formally proposed although the scope of exemptions
1011 differed in some cases and no recommendation was provided for *P. leniusculus*.

1012

1013 **S5.5 Permit and enforcement activities**

1014 A total of 1 784 permits have been issued for restricted activities between the promulgation of the
1015 regulations in 2014 and September 2019. The number issued per month has remained fairly constant
1016 (Figure S5.2). Of these most are for commercial or personal purposes. Only 61 have been for research,
1017 10 for biocontrol, 17 for display purposes (i.e. in a zoo or botanic gardens), and none for inter-basin
1018 transfers.

1019

1020 **Figure S5.2** Number of permits issued each month by the DFFtE for restricted activities on listed alien
 1021 taxa (including importation) from May 2015 until the start of September 2019. This includes permits
 1022 issued for research or biocontrol purposes.

1023 Of the 116 listed alien species for which permits may be issued (as of the 2016 regulations), permits
 1024 have been issued for 77 taxa (Table S5.2). This means that no permits were issued for just over a third
 1025 of taxa for which permits could be issued. It is not clear whether there is sufficient demand for such
 1026 taxa to warrant listing as category 2, or that the requirement for permitting is not being adhered to.
 1027 For example, mallard duck (*Anas platyrhynchos*) is listed as category 2 and is widely farmed to produce
 1028 duck meat. However, only three permits were issued for this taxon. Of concern is that permits seem
 1029 to have been issued for a few taxa where there is no provision for a permit to be issued (i.e. not for
 1030 the purposes of research, biocontrol, display, or during an inter-basin transfer scheme)—permits were
 1031 issued to possess *Cortaderia selloana* and *Tamarix ramosissima* which are listed as 1b; and *Python*
 1032 *molurus* (Linnaeus, 1758) which is listed as prohibited. Notably, however, the applications for permits
 1033 change with the listing. Several permits were issued to breed with *Crotalus* spp. in 2014–2016, but
 1034 these were removed from the list in 2016. Finally import permits were granted for some species not
 1035 on the lists [*Lates calcarifer*; *Oncorhynchus kisutch*; *O. tshawytscha*; and *Salmo salar*].

1036 **Table S5.2** Taxa listed as category 2 noting where permits have been issued. For details on the purpose for which permits were issued and the number of
 1037 permits see Appendix 6. Permits issued for research, biocontrol, or display purposes are not included here.

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Permits issued		Notes
		2014–2016	2017–Sep 2019	
<i>Acacia dealbata</i> Link	silver wattle	yes	yes	
<i>Acacia decurrens</i> Willd.	green wattle	yes	yes	
<i>Acacia mearnsii</i> De Wild.	black wattle	yes	yes	
<i>Acacia melanoxylon</i> R.Br.	Australian blackwood	yes	yes	
<i>Acridotheres cristatellus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Crested Mynah	no	no	
<i>Acridotheres fuscus</i> Wagler, 1827	Jungle Mynah	no	no	
<i>Addax nasomaculatus</i> (de Blainville, 1816)	addax	yes	yes	
<i>Aepyceros melampus petersi</i> Bocage, 1879	black-faced impala	yes	yes	
<i>Agave sisalana</i> Perrine	sisal hemp, sisal	yes	yes	
<i>Alectoris chukar</i> (J. E. Gray, 1830)	Chukar partridge	yes	no	2 on mainland, 1b on off-shore islands.
<i>Ammotragus lervia</i> (Pallas, 1777)	barbary sheep	yes	yes	
<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Mallard	yes	yes	
<i>Anolis carolinensis</i> Voigt, 1832	green anole	no	no	2 in EC, KZN, L, M; not listed elsewhere
<i>Antilope cervicapra</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Indian blackbuck	yes	yes	
<i>Apalone</i> species (unidentified)	soft-shell terrapins	no	no	
<i>Atriplex nummularia</i> subsp. <i>nummularia</i> Lindl. 1848	old man saltbush	no	no	
<i>Axis axis</i> (Erleben, 1777)	chital	yes	yes	
<i>Axis porcinus</i> (Zimmermann, 1780)	hog deer	yes	yes	
<i>Basiliscus plumifrons</i> Cope, 1876	plumed basilisk	yes	yes	2 in EC, KZN, L, M; not listed elsewhere
<i>Basiliscus vittatus</i> Wiegmann, 1828	brown basilisk	no	no	
<i>Bitis gabonica rhinoceros</i> (Schlegel, 1855)	rhinoceros viper	yes	yes	2 in EC, KZN, L, M; not listed elsewhere
<i>Bitis nasicornis</i> (Shaw, 1802)	rhinoceros viper	yes	yes	2 in EC, KZN, L, M; not listed elsewhere
<i>Boa constrictor</i> Linnaeus, 1758	common boa	yes	yes	2 in EC, KZN, L, M; not listed elsewhere
<i>Boselaphus tragocamelus</i> (Pallas, 1766)	nilgai	no	yes	
<i>Carduelis carduelis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	European goldfinch	no	no	
<i>Carduelis chloris</i> Linnaeus, 1758	European greenfinch	no	no	
<i>Carduelis flammea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Common redpoll	no	no	
<i>Casuarina cunninghamiana</i> Miq.	beefwood	yes	yes	2; 1b within 100 metres of riparian areas or untransformed land

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Permits issued		Notes
		2014–2016	2017–Sep 2019	
<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i> L.	horsetail tree	no	Yes	
<i>Centrochelys sulcata</i> Miller, 1779	spur-thighed tortoise	yes	yes	
<i>Cervus elaphus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	red deer	yes	yes	
<i>Cervus nippon</i> Temminck, 1838	sika deer	no	no	
<i>Chelydra serpentina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common snapping turtle	yes	yes	
<i>Cherax cainii</i> Austin & Ryan, 2002	smooth marron	no	no	
<i>Cherax tenuimanus</i> Smith, 1912	hairy marron	yes	yes	
<i>Colinus virginianus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Northern bobwhite quail	no	no	
<i>Columba palumbus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Common wood-pigeon	no	no	
<i>Columba livia</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	Rock dove	yes	yes	3; 2 for all restricted activities relating to racing and showing of pigeons
<i>Crassostrea gigas</i> (Thunberg, 1793)	Japanese oyster, Pacific oyster	no	yes	
<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	grass carp	yes	yes	2 for breeding of triploid grass carp; see regulations for more details of the listing
<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i> (Valenciennes, 1844)	triploid grass carp	yes	yes	2 for release of triploid grass carp into dams in discrete catchment systems in which it does not occur OR for release into rivers, wetlands, lakes and estuaries in which it occurs; see regulations for more details on the listing
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common carp	yes	yes	2 for release into a dam within a discrete catchment system in which it does not occur; see regulations for more details on the listing.
<i>Dama dama</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	fallow deer	yes	yes	
<i>Dendrobates auratus</i> (Girard, 1855)	poison arrow frog	yes	yes	
<i>Dendrobates leucomelas</i> Steindachner, 1864	poison arrow frog	yes	yes	Listed under the genus
<i>Dendrobates tinctorius</i> (Schneider, 1799)	poison arrow frog	no	yes	
<i>Diceros bicornis michaeli</i> Zukowsky, 1965	black rhinoceros (Kenya)	yes	yes	
<i>Duranta erecta</i> L.	forget-me-not-tree	yes	yes	2 for breeding in nurseries in G, KZN, L, M, NW, but may not be transferred within these Provincial boundaries; see regulations for more details on the listing
<i>Elaphurus davidianus</i> Milne-Edwards, 1866	Père David's deer	yes	yes	

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Permits issued		Notes
		2014–2016	2017–Sep 2019	
<i>Erythrocebus patas</i> (Schreber, 1774)	Patas monkey	yes	yes	1a in KZN; 1b elsewhere; 2 if bred for export
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> Dehnh.	river red gum	yes	yes	2 for plantations, woodlots, bee-forage areas, wind-rows and the lining of avenues (includes hybrids, varieties and selections); see the regulations for details of the rest of the listing
<i>Eucalyptus cladocalyx</i> F.Muell.	sugar gum	yes	yes	2 for plantations, woodlots, bee-forage areas, wind-rows and the lining of avenues (includes hybrids, varieties and selections); see the regulations for details of the rest of the listing
<i>Eucalyptus conferruminata</i> D.J.Carr & S.G.M.Carr	spider gum	no	yes	2 for plantations, woodlots, bee-forage areas, wind-rows and the lining of avenues (includes hybrids, varieties and selections); see the regulations for details of the rest of the listing
<i>Eucalyptus diversicolor</i> F.Muell.	karri	no	no	2 for plantations, woodlots, bee-forage areas, wind-rows and the lining of avenues (includes hybrids, varieties and selections); see the regulations for details of the rest of the listing
<i>Eucalyptus grandis</i> W.Hill ex Maiden	saligna gum	yes	yes	2 for plantations, woodlots, bee-forage areas, wind-rows and the lining of avenues (includes hybrids, varieties and selections); see the regulations for details of the rest of the listing
<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i> Sm.	forest red gum	yes	yes	2 for plantations, woodlots, bee-forage areas, wind-rows and the lining of avenues (includes hybrids, varieties and selections); see the regulations for details of the rest of the listing
<i>Fenneropenaeus indicus</i> (Milne-Edwards, 1837)	Indian prawn	no	no	2 in all provinces except KZN; indigenous to KZN and therefore not listed there.
<i>Fringilla coelebs</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Chaffinch	no	no	
<i>Furcifer oustaleti</i> (Mocquard, 1894)	Oustalet's chameleon	no	no	
<i>Furcifer pardalis</i> (Cuvier, 1829)	panther chameleon	yes	yes	
<i>Gambusia affinis</i> (Baird & Girard, 1853)	mosquito-fish	yes	no	2 for breeding for the purpose of feeding stock for zoos and animal breeders; see regulations for further details on the listing
<i>Gekko gecko</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Tokay gecko	yes	yes	
<i>Hippotragus equinus koba</i> (Gray, 1872)	western roan	no	no	Include hybrids with other taxa for back-breeding purposes.
<i>Hydrochaeris hydrochaeris</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	capibara	yes	yes	
<i>Hylocereus undatus</i> (Haw.) Britton & Rose	night-blooming cereus	no	yes	2; the fruit of night-blooming cactus is not listed if used for human consumption
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i> L.	St. John's wort	no	no	

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Permits issued		Notes
		2014–2016	2017–Sep 2019	
<i>Iguana iguana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	green iguana	yes	yes	1b in KZN, EC; 2 in M, EC, L; not listed elsewhere.
<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	physic nut	no	no	
<i>Kobus ellipsiprymnus</i> crawshayi (P. L. Sclater, 1894)	Crawshay's waterbuck	yes	yes	
<i>Kobus ellipsiprymnus</i> defassa (Ruppell, 1835)	Defassa waterbuck	yes	no	
<i>Kobus leche kafuensis</i> Haltenorth, 1963	Kafue lechwe	yes	yes	
<i>Kobus leche leche</i> Gray, 1850	red lechwe	yes	yes	
<i>Kobus vardonii</i> (Livingstone, 1857)	puku	no	no	
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i> (Lam.) De Wit.	leucaena	yes	no	
<i>Macaca fascicularis</i> Raffles, 1821	crab-eating macaque	no	no	
<i>Macrochelys temminckii</i> (Troost in Harlan, 1835)	alligator snapper turtle	yes	yes	
<i>Micropterus floridanus</i> Lesueur, 1822	Florida bass	no	no	2 in National Parks, Provincial Reserves, Mountain Catchment Areas and Forestry Reserves declared in terms of the Protected Areas Act; see regulations for further details of the listings
<i>Micropterus floridanus</i> (LeSueur, 1822) x <i>M. salmoides</i>	hybrid bass	no	no	2 in National Parks, Provincial Reserves, Mountain Catchment Areas and Forestry Reserves declared in terms of the Protected Areas Act; see regulations for further details of the listings
<i>Micropterus punctulatus</i> (Rafinesque, 1819)	spotted bass	no	no	2 in National Parks, Provincial Reserves, Mountain Catchment Areas and Forestry Reserves declared in terms of the Protected Areas Act; see regulations for further details of the listings
<i>Micropterus salmoides</i> (Lacépède, 1802)	large-mouth bass	yes	yes	2 in National Parks, Provincial Reserves, Mountain Catchment Areas and Forestry Reserves declared in terms of the Protected Areas Act; see regulations for further details of the listings
<i>Morelia amethystina</i> (Schneider, 1801)	amethystine python	no	no	2 in EC, KZN, L, M; not listed elsewhere
<i>Morelia spilotes</i> (Lacépède, 1804)	diamond python	yes	yes	
<i>Murraya paniculata</i> (L.) Jack.	orange jasmine	yes	yes	1b in KNZ, L, M; 2 for breeding in nurseries in KNZ, L, M but may not be transferred within these Provincial boundaries; not listed elsewhere; sterile cultivars or hybrids are not listed
<i>Myocastor coypus</i> (Molina, 1782)	coypu	no	yes	
<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i> Lamarck, 1819	Mediterranean mussel	no	no	Permits issued by marine authorities?

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Permits issued		Notes
		2014–2016	2017–Sep 2019	
<i>Nasturtium officinale</i> R.Br.	watercress	yes	yes	
<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Nile tilapia	yes	yes	1b in National Parks, Provincial Reserves, Mountain Catchment Areas and Forestry Reserves specified in terms of the Protected Areas Act; 2 for aquaculture facilities in the rest of the country; 3 in all other discrete catchment systems in which it occurs.
<i>Oryx dammah</i> Cretzschmar, 1826	scimitar-horned oryx	yes	yes	
<i>Ovis aries musimon</i> Pallas, 1811	mouflon	yes	yes	
<i>Passiflora edulis</i> Sims.	purple granadilla	yes	yes	2 in EC, G, KZN, M, L, NW; Not listed in urban areas in EC, G, KZN, M, L, NW; not listed elsewhere; the fruit of the purple granadilla is not listed if used for human consumption
<i>Penaeus monodon</i> Fabricius, 1798	giant tiger prawn	no	no	2 in all provinces except KZN; indigenous to KZN and therefore not listed there.
<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i> Schumach.	elephant grass	no	no	
<i>Pinus elliottii</i> Engelm.	slash pine	yes	yes	2 for sterile specimens; 1b for non-sterile specimens; listing includes hybrids, varieties and selections
<i>Pinus patula</i> Schiede ex Schltldl. & Cham.	patula pine	yes	yes	
<i>Pinus pinaster</i> Aiton	cluster pine	yes	yes	2 for plantations and wind-rows listing includes hybrids, varieties and selections; see the regulations for details of the rest of the listing
<i>Pinus radiata</i> D.Don	Monterey pine	yes	yes	2 for plantations and wind-rows listing includes hybrids, varieties and selections; see the regulations for details of the rest of the listing
<i>Pinus roxburghii</i> Sarg.	chir pine	no	no	
<i>Pinus taeda</i> L.	loblolly pine	no	no	
<i>Populus × canescens</i> (Aiton) Sm.	grey poplar	yes	yes	
<i>Populus alba</i> L.	white poplar	no	yes	
<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	guava	no	yes	2 for plantations in EC, KZN, L, M, NW; 3 elsewhere in EC, KZN, L, M, NW; the fruit of the guava is not listed if used for human consumption; not listed elsewhere
<i>Psittacula krameri</i> Scopoli, 1769	Rose-ringed parakeet	yes	yes	
<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i> Linnaeus, 1766	Red-vented bulbul	no	no	
<i>Pycnonotus jocosus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Red-whiskered bulbul	no	no	

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Permits issued		Notes
		2014–2016	2017–Sep 2019	
<i>Python bivittatus</i> (Kuhl, 1820)	Burmese python	yes	yes	
<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	castor-oil plant	no	yes	
<i>Rubus fruticosus</i> Lour.	European blackberry	no	no	a. 2 b. The fruit of the European blackberry is not listed if used for human consumption.
<i>Rusa unicolor</i> (Kerr, 1792)	sambar deer	yes	yes	
<i>Sicalis flaveola</i> Linnaeus, 1766	Saffron finch	no	no	
<i>Sorghum halepense</i> (L.) Pers.	johnson grass	no	no	
<i>Syngonium podophyllum</i> Schott	goose foot	no	no	1b in EC, KZN, L, M; 2 for breeding in nurseries in EC, KZN, L, M, but may not be transferred within these Provincial boundaries. Not listed elsewhere.
<i>Trachemys scripta elegans</i> (Wied, 1838)	red-eared slider	yes	yes	
<i>Tragelaphus derbianus</i> Gray, 1847	Derby eland	no	yes	
<i>Tragelaphus spekii</i> Speke, 1863	sitatunga	yes	yes	
<i>Trioceros jacksonii</i> (Boulenger, 1896)	Jackson's chameleon	no	no	2 in EC, KZN, L, M; not listed elsewhere
<i>Trioceros melleri</i> (Gray, 1865)	Meller's chameleon	no	no	2 in EC, KZN, L, M; not listed elsewhere

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1039 Regulation 4(3) of the A&IS Regulations provide that the landowners are responsible for ensuring that
 1040 the specimens of Category 2 species occurring on their land do not spread outside of their properties.
 1041 It is problematic that this duty of care falls squarely on landowners and not also on persons in control
 1042 of land. Where the spread of invasive species from land that is not under the control of the landowner
 1043 is not the fault of the landowner, liability on the landowner for the transgression would be faultless
 1044 (Lukey and Hall, 2020). In the Amendment Regulations however, it is proposed that Regulation 4(3) is
 1045 amended by deleting the reference to ‘landowner’ and replacing it with the term ‘a person in control
 1046 of a Category 2 Listed Invasive Species’ The proposed amendment would address the issue identified
 1047 in the paragraph above.

1048 **Table S5.3** The number of permits issued or refused between January 2017 and August 2019 for listed
 1049 alien species as per the regulatory groupings of the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations. No permits were
 1050 applied for marine fish, terrestrial invertebrates, microbes, or marine plants. Details of the specific
 1051 taxa for which permits were granted are indicated in Appendix 6.

Regulatory Grouping	Permits granted	Permits refused
Amphibian	2	0
Bird	84	0
Freshwater fish	281	3
Freshwater invertebrate	7	3
Marine invertebrate	4	0
Mammal	247	0
Terrestrial and freshwater plant	98	0
Reptile	71	0
TOTAL	794	6

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1053 **Table S5.4** The number of permits issued or refused between January 2017 and August 2019 for a
 1054 range of restricted activities associated with five categories of intended use of listed alien species.
 1055 ‘Conveying’ refers to moving or otherwise translocating any specimen of a listed alien species, ‘import’
 1056 refers to new introductions into the country of listed alien species, ‘possession’ refers to exercising
 1057 physical control over any specimen of a listed alien species, ‘Breeding and growing’ refers to
 1058 propagating any specimen of a listed alien species, or causing it to multiply, ‘releasing’ refers to
 1059 releasing any specimen of a listed alien species into the environment. Most permit applications
 1060 submitted involved more than one activity.

Activities covered by the permit (most permit applications submitted involved more than one activity)	Permits granted	Permits refused
Conveying within the Republic	436	6
Importing into the Republic	46	0
Trade	319	5
Research	12	0
Possession	634	6
Breeding and growing	239	6
Releasing	152	0

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1062 NEM:BA and the A&IS Regulations provide that a designated environmental management inspector
1063 (EMI) may issue a person who has failed to fulfil his or her duty of care in relation to listed alien species
1064 or conducted a restricted activity in relation to a listed alien species with a directive directing him or
1065 her to take specified steps that may be necessary to manage the invasive species concerned. A failure
1066 to fulfil the duty of care or conducting a restricted activity involving a listed alien species without a
1067 permit are also criminal offences in terms of NEM:BA.

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1069 **Table S5.5** A summary of factors used to assess the quality of the regulations pertaining to biological invasions in South Africa, 2017–2019

Aspect of regulations	Aspect of biological invasions		
	Pathways	Species	Sites
Is there a mandate for management interventions?	<p>Partial</p> <p>NEM:BA and the A&IS Regulations authorise the Minister or her delegate to implement management interventions in relation to pathways. However, there is no policy guiding the implementation of the intervention provisions. Furthermore, there are still very few pathways-focussed management measures in NEM:BA and the A&IS Regulations.</p>	<p>Partial</p> <p>NEM:BA and the A&IS Regulations authorise the Minister or her delegate to implement management interventions in relation to species. The species-related interventions are arguably the strongest out of the three aspects. However, the absence of a policy hampers the implementation of those measures significantly, and there is a mismatch between the listing of species and those recommended by an independent scientific advisory body.</p>	<p>Partial</p> <p>NEM:BA and the A&IS Regulations authorise the Minister or her delegate to implement management interventions in relation to sites. However, there is no policy guiding the implementation of the intervention provisions.</p>
Is there provision for enforcement of non-compliance?	<p>Partial</p> <p>Both NEM:BA and the A&IS Regulations make provision of the enforcement of obligations and duties. Those provisions are, however, largely ineffective in a policy vacuum. Furthermore, neither the Act nor the regulations make provision for administrative penalties. Administrative penalties could supplement the criminal remedies in the Act, especially since prosecution of environmental crimes in South Africa is a slow and cumbersome process with a relatively high standard of proof.</p>		

Aspect of regulations	Aspect of biological invasions		
	Pathways	Species	Sites
Is there a requirement for regular assessment of performance and review?	<p>Partial</p> <p>The A&IS Regulations require SANBI to complete a status report every three years that includes an assessment of the effectiveness of the regulations. The A&IS Regulations also provide for the keeping of various registers that can be used to track performance. However, many of those registers have not been established and the one that has been established does not comply with the A&IS Regulations.</p> <p>There is also no clarity on how programmes for the prevention, control or eradication of invasive species should be adopted and implemented by the Minister.</p> <p>Moreover, without a policy framework in terms of which performance indicators are set, it is difficult to assess performance in the first place.</p>		<p>Partial</p> <p>Largely as for pathways and species although NEM:BA requires organs of state and private landowners to submit Invasive Species Monitoring, Control, and Eradication Plans. Those plans can be used to assess performance. However, very few private landowners and organs of state have submitted those plans to the competent authority and many of the plans that have been submitted largely do not comply with the Guidelines published in terms of NEM:BA. It is also not clear if there has been follow-up at any of the sites subject to plans to see that the plans are being implemented.</p> <p>NEM:BA also provides for monitoring the implementation of invasive species control and eradication strategies in the management plans of protected areas. Unfortunately, there are no data on how many protected areas in South Africa have such plans. It is also not clear if performance against those plans are being monitored by the Minister or her delegate.</p>

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1075 **S5.6 Money spent**

1076 As was the case with the first report, it is not possible to quantify how much money was spent on the
1077 management of biological invasions in South Africa across all government agencies, NGOs, and the
1078 private sector. The only estimate for annual government spending is for DFFtE's Natural Resource
1079 Management programme. This programme funds alien species control projects by contracting
1080 implementing agencies, research into biological control at the Centre for Biological Control and the
1081 Agricultural Research Council, and incursion response projects managed by the South African National
1082 Biodiversity Institute. However, there is significant uncertainty even in this figure because the DFFtE
1083 does not differentiate in its records between money spent on biological invasions and money spent
1084 on other programs. This also means that comparing the money spent over time is likely to be an
1085 unreliable estimate of actual trends in expenditure. Notably the value presented in the first status
1086 report for 2015/2016 (ZAR 1805M per year) is significantly higher than that reported here (ZAR 1145M
1087 per year, Figure 5.1), but the values reported here represent a revised baseline.

1088 Available information regarding money spent on the management of individual species where
1089 available is summarised in Table S5.9.

1090 **S5.7 Planning coverage**

1091 NEM:BA and the A&IS Regulations provide for the management of invasive species on State and
1092 private land. In relation to State land, NEM:BA requires the management authority of each protected
1093 area to prepare an Invasive Species Monitoring, Control, and Eradication Plan (Area Management
1094 Plans) for the area of which it has been assigned the management authority and for that Area
1095 Management Plan to be incorporated into the management plan for that protected area and a copy
1096 must be submitted to the Minister and SANBI. All organs of state are also required to prepare Area
1097 Management Plans for the State land they administer. Guidelines for preparing Area Management
1098 Plans were published on DEA's (as it was then) website in 2015 in terms of Regulation 8 of the A&IS
1099 Regulations. Municipalities are further required in terms of section 76(2)(b) to integrate their Area
1100 Management Plans into their integrated development plans.

1101 As in the first report, planning coverage for pathways was determined based on the number of
1102 pathways that are currently managed and those for which plans have been developed, but for which
1103 management is not yet in place. According to the first report, 35 of the 44 pathways (79.5%) had
1104 management plans in place. As the pathway classification scheme of the Convention on Biological
1105 Diversity (CBD, 2014) has been revised since the first report (Harrower et al., 2018), the data collected
1106 for the first report has been reinterpreted and a revised baseline calculated. Two pathways for which

1107 management plans were in place at the time of the first report were combined, and a new pathway,
1108 which also had management plans in place at the time of the first report, was added. Therefore, the
1109 revised baseline is that 35 pathways had plans in place at the time of the first report. Based on the
1110 data collected for the second report, there has been no change to this estimate, and so 79.5% of
1111 pathways have management plans in place. Of the 44 pathways of introduction, 19 involve the
1112 intentional import of organisms, 11 involve the accidental introduction of organisms as contaminants
1113 of imported commodities, 11 involve the accidental introduction of alien species as stowaways on
1114 transport vectors, 2 involve human built corridors (which are of low importance South Africa) and one
1115 involves natural dispersal from neighbouring countries (which is increasingly important). There is
1116 currently national legislation [e.g., the National Environment Management: Biodiversity Act (Act No.
1117 10 of 2004), Agricultural Pests Act (Act No. 36 of 1983), Animal Diseases Act (Act No. 35 of 1984)] and
1118 international agreements (e.g., the IPPC) in place that aim to prevent the introduction of potentially
1119 harmful species through pathways where species are intentionally imported or imported as
1120 contaminants of commodities. Under international agreements and regulations (the IPPC and
1121 International Health Regulations) wood packaging should be treated to prevent the spread of timber
1122 pests, and aircraft should be sprayed to kill insect disease vectors (e.g. mosquitos). Cargo and
1123 passengers entering South Africa are also searched for alien organisms, and legislation to prevent the
1124 introduction of species through the release of ballast water by ships has been drafted, as have ballast
1125 water management plans for some ports. Therefore, five of the 11 stowaway pathways currently have
1126 management plans in place. Of the nine pathways that did not have management plans in place at the
1127 time of the first report, eight still do not have management plans in place, but the other one pathway
1128 (hull fouling) is being considered, specifically the Transnet Ports Authority plans to introduce in-water
1129 hull cleaning, however, it is unclear whether a plan has been developed and implemented. As this
1130 assessment is largely based on the knowledge of experts, our confidence in the assessment is low. See
1131 Appendix 3 for the data used in this assessment and for our confidence in the assessment for each
1132 pathway.

1133 Of the 57 taxa that are listed as category 1a on at least part of the mainland, plans have been
1134 developed for 36 of these (Table S5.6a). Of the 21 taxa where no plans were received, management
1135 is known to be ongoing for many of them, but in several cases the species have not been found and in
1136 one case field surveys suggest the species is no longer present in South Africa (Mabin et al. 2015).
1137 Project plans are in place for a further 21 plant taxa (Table S5.6b). There is no indication that any of
1138 these plans had been formally approved by the DFFtE as of June 2020, or if these documents actually
1139 constitute adequate species-specific eradication management plans, though it is unclear if there is a
1140 process to formally approve plans. A further 11 taxa are listed as category 1a on off-shore islands

1141 although the plans for eradicating these (if such exist) were not assessed for this report, however it
 1142 was noted that during 2017–2019 a plan was in development for eradicating the house mouse (*Mus*
 1143 *musculus*) from Marion Island (currently listed as 1b) (Table S5.6c). At the time of writing, criteria for
 1144 the assessment of eradication plans had not yet been developed (as they have for site management
 1145 plans), and there has been no assessment of the status of each plan, although a scheme for such
 1146 assessment has been developed (Table S5.7, Holmes et al. 2019).

1147 **Table S5.6.** Invasive species for which species-specific eradication management plans are required (i.e.
 1148 category 1a) or where a plan has been drawn up to assess it. A) for taxa listed as category 1a on
 1149 mainland South Africa; B) for other taxa on the mainland (including SUSPECT species, i.e. Species
 1150 Under Surveillance for Possible Eradication or Containment Targeting), but also species where the
 1151 potential for listing was considered in the past but which will not necessarily ever be considered for
 1152 eradication, Wilson et al. 2013]; and C) for taxa listed either on offshore islands, i.e. the Prince Edward
 1153 Islands (PEIs = Prince Edward Island and Marion Island) or other offshore islands (note, there might be
 1154 plans for the PEIs but these were not sourced as part of this report). Data on how much money has
 1155 been spent on each taxon were not available, the quality of the plans have not yet been assessed (they
 1156 are to be rated as adequate, partially adequate, or inadequate), nor are data on the status of the
 1157 project available [see Holmes et al. (2019) for a proposed scheme]. RA refers to a risk analysis that has
 1158 been conducted and approved by ASRARP as of the end of December 2019 (see Table S5.1).

1159 A)

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Date of plan	Notes
<i>Acacia adunca</i> A.Cunn. ex G.Don	cascade wattle	2016 or earlier	
<i>Acacia fimbriata</i> A.Cunn. ex G.Don	fringed wattle	2016 or earlier	
<i>Acacia implexa</i> Benth.	screw pod wattle	2016 or earlier	
<i>Acacia paradoxa</i> DC.	kangaroo thorn	2016 or earlier	
<i>Acacia stricta</i> (Andrews) Willd.	hop wattle	2016 or earlier	
All hybrids of mammal species or sub-species listed in this Notice	NA	Not known	Hybrids of western roan for back-breeding purposes are listed as category 2
<i>Astacus leptodactylus</i> Eschscholtz, 1823	Danube crayfish	NA	
<i>Austrocylindropuntia cylindrica</i> (Juss. ex Lam.) Backeberg.	cane cactus	NA	
<i>Bactrocera invadens dorsalis</i> (Drew, Tsuruta and White, 2005)	Asian fruit-fly	NA	
<i>Billardiera heterophylla</i> (Lindl.) L.W.Cayzer & Crisp	bluebell creeper	2016 or earlier	
<i>Cabomba caroliniana</i> A.Gray	cabomba	2016 or earlier	has not been found
<i>Campuloclinium macrocephalum</i> (Less.) DC.	pompom weed	2015	
<i>Cherax destructor</i> Clark, 1936	yabby	NA	
<i>Chondrilla juncea</i> L.	skeleton weed	2016 or earlier	RA suggests keeping as 1a
<i>Coreopsis lanceolata</i> L.	tickseed	2016 or earlier	RA suggests relisting as 1b

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Date of plan	Notes
<i>Corvus splendens</i> Vieillot, 1817	House crow	No date, but estimate of 2 000 000 spent	Control measures ongoing in several municipalities
<i>Cylindropuntia pallida</i> (DC.) F.M.Knuth	pink-flowered sheathed cholla	2016 or earlier	
<i>Cylindropuntia spinosior</i> (Engelm.) F.M.Knuth	cane cholla	NA	
<i>Cytisus scoparius</i> (L.) Link	Scotch broom	2016 or earlier	
<i>Diplocyclos palmatus</i> L.	lollipop-climber	2016 or earlier	
<i>Equisetum hyemale</i> L.	rough horsetail	NA	
<i>Erythrocebus patas</i> (Schreber, 1775)	Patas monkey	Not known	1a in KZN, 1b elsewhere, 2 if bred for export
<i>Euphorbia esula</i> L.	leafy spurge	NA	has not been found
<i>Fallopia sachalinensis</i> (F. Schmidt) Ronse Decr.	giant knotweed	2016 or earlier	has not been found
<i>Furcraea foetida</i> L.	Mauritian hemp	2016 or earlier	
<i>Genista monspessulana</i> (L.) L.A.S.Johnson	Montpellier broom	2016 or earlier	
<i>Harrisia balansae</i> (K.Schum.) N.P.Taylor & Zappi	strangler prickly apple	2016 or earlier	
<i>Harrisia pomanensis</i> F.A. C. Webber ex Schum.	midnight lady	2016 or earlier	
<i>Hydrilla verticillata</i> (L.f.) Royle.	hydrilla	2016 or earlier	
<i>Hydrocleys nymphoides</i> Buchenau (Humb. & Bonpl. ex Willd.)	water poppy	2016 or earlier	
<i>Iris pseudacorus</i> L.	yellow flag	2016 or earlier	RA suggests relisting as 1b
<i>Kunzea ericoides</i> (A.Rich.) Joy Thomps.	burgan, white teatree	NA	
<i>Ludwigia peruviana</i> (L.) H.Hara	water-primrose	2016 or earlier	
<i>Lythrum salicaria</i> L.	purple loosestrife	2016 or earlier	
<i>Marsilea mutica</i> Mett.	Australian waterclover	NA	
<i>Melaleuca hypericifolia</i> Sm.	red-flowering tea tree	2016 or earlier	RA suggests relisting as 1b
<i>Metrosideros excelsa</i> Sol. ex Gaertn. (= <i>M. tomentosa</i> A.Rich.)	New Zealand christmas tree	2016 or earlier	1a in the Overstrand District, not listed elsewhere and sterile cultivars or hybrids are not listed.
<i>Myrtillocactus geometrizans</i> (Mart.) Console	bilberry cactus	2016 or earlier	
<i>Nuphar lutea</i> (L.) Sm.	yellow water-lily	NA	
<i>Nymphoides peltata</i> (S.G.Gmel.) Kuntze	gringed water lily	2016 or earlier	Subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Opuntia pubescens</i> J.C.Wendl. ex Pfeiff.	velvet bur cactus	2016 or earlier	
<i>Opuntia robusta</i> J.C.Wendl.	blue-leaf cactus (spiny form)	NA	
<i>Opuntia salmiana</i> J.Parm. ex Pfeiff.	bur cactus	2016 or earlier	Biological control assessed as substantial

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Date of plan	Notes
<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	parthenium weed	2016	
<i>Paspalum quadrifarium</i> Lam.	tussock paspalum	2016 or earlier	RA suggests relisting as 1b
<i>Paulownia tomentosa</i> (Thunb.) Steud.	empress tree	2016 or earlier	
<i>Prostephanus truncatus</i> (Horn, 1878)	larger grain borer		
<i>Pueraria montana</i> (Lour.) Merr. var. <i>lobata</i> (Willd.) Maesen & S.M.Almeida	kudzu vine	2016 or earlier	
<i>Python natalensis</i> x <i>molurus</i> (Smith, 1840)	Southern African python x Burmese python	NA	
<i>Rubus ellipticus</i> Smith	Asian wild raspberry	2016 or earlier	
<i>Sagittaria platyphylla</i> (Engelm.) J.G.Sm.	delta arrowhead	2016 or earlier	RA suggests relisting as 1b
<i>Sciurus carolinensis</i> Gmelin, 1788	grey squirrel	Not known	1a in KZN, 3 elsewhere
<i>Spartina alterniflora</i> Loisel.	smooth cordgrass	NA	Eradication efforts have been documented
<i>Tephrocactus articulatus</i> (Pfeiff.) Backeb	pine cone cactus	2016 or earlier	
<i>Tetrapygus niger</i> (Molina, 1782)	black sea-urchin	Not required	Has been documented as absent
<i>Tragelaphus eurycerus</i> Ogilby, 1837	bongo	NA	
<i>Tragelaphus imberbis</i> Blyth, 1869	lesser kudu	NA	
<i>Triplaris americana</i> L.	ant tree	2016 or earlier	
<i>Ulex europaeus</i> L.	European gorse	2016 or earlier	

1160 B)

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Date of plan
<i>Acacia cultriformis</i> A.Cunn. ex G.Don	knife-leaved wattle	2016 or earlier
<i>Acanthus polystachius</i> Delile var. <i>pseudopubescens</i> Cufod.	spiny bear's breeches	2017–2019
<i>Asphodelus fistulosus</i> L.	onion weed	2016 or earlier
<i>Banksia integrifolia</i> L.f.	coast banksia	2016 or earlier
<i>Banksia serrata</i> L.f.	saw banksia	2016 or earlier
<i>Bauhinia forficata</i> Link	thorny orchid tree	2017–2019
<i>Berberis aristata</i> DC.	Indian barberry	2016 or earlier
<i>Callistemon linearis</i> (Schrad. & J.C. Wendl.) Colv. Ex Sweet	stiff-leaved bottlebrush	2016 or earlier
<i>Callistemon rugulosus</i> (Schltdl. ex Link) DC.	scarlet bottlebrush	2017–2019
<i>Cistus ladanifer</i> L.	common gum cistus	2016 or earlier
<i>Desmodium uncinatum</i> (Jacq.) DC.	silverleaf desmodium	2017–2019
<i>Handroanthus chrysotrichus</i> (Mart. ex DC.) Mattos	yellow trumpet tree	2016 or earlier
<i>Ipomoea</i> species indet.	NA	2017–2019
<i>Lagerstroemia indica</i> L.	pride-of-India	2017–2019
<i>Mahonia oiwakensis</i> Hayata	mahonia	2016 or earlier
<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	mango	2017–2019
<i>Melaleuca diosmifolia</i> Andrews	green honey myrtle	2016 or earlier
<i>Melaleuca parvistaminea</i> Byrnes	rough-barked honey myrtle	2016 or earlier
<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	horse-radish tree	2017–2019

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Date of plan
<i>Tithonia tubaeformis</i> (Jacq.) Cass.	NA	2017–2019
<i>Zinnia peruviana</i> (L.) L.	Redstar zinnia	2017–2019

1161 C)

Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Notes
<i>Agrostis castellana</i> Boiss. & Reut.	bent grass	1a PEI, 1b Marion, not listed elsewhere
<i>Agrostis stolonifera</i> L.	creeping bent grass	1a PEI, 1b Marion, not listed elsewhere
<i>Alopecurus geniculatus</i> L. (= <i>A. australis</i> Nees)	marsh foxtail, water foxtail	1a on PEIs not listed elsewhere
<i>Capra hircus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	goat	1a for off-shore islands, not listed elsewhere
<i>Elytrigia repens</i> (L.) Desv. ex Nevski (= <i>Agropyron repens</i> (L.) P. Beauv., <i>Elymus repens</i> (L.) Gould)	couch grass	1a on PEIs not listed elsewhere
<i>Felis catus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	domestic cat	1a for off-shore islands, not listed elsewhere Eradicated from Marion Island; ongoing control on Robben Island
<i>Festuca rubra</i> L.	creeping red fescue	1a on PEIs not listed elsewhere
<i>Luzula cf. multiflora</i> (Ehrh) Lej.	woodrush	1a on PEIs not listed elsewhere
<i>Poa pratensis</i> L.	Kentucky bluegrass	1a PEI, 1b Marion Island, not listed elsewhere
<i>Rumex acetosella</i> L.	sheep sorrel, red sorrel	1a on PEIs not listed elsewhere
<i>Stellaria media</i> (L.) Vill.	common chickweed	1a PEI, 1b Marion Island, not listed elsewhere
<i>Mus musculus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	house mouse	1b for off-shore islands, not listed elsewhere, eradication planning underway for Marion Island during 2017–2019 The planned cost is ZAR 60 million

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1163 **Table S5.7** Criteria for the evaluation of the status of invasive species eradication attempts (after
1164 Holmes et al. 2019).

Status	Criteria
Successful	The operation to eradicate the invasive was successful and confirmed
Failed	The eradication operation was completed (there is an end date) yet it failed to remove the entire invasive population. Operational failure (as opposed to reinvasion). For rodent eradications, if there was uncertainty about why the invasive population remained (failure versus reinvasion), we assumed operational failure and classified data quality as 'poor'
To be confirmed	The eradication effort is complete, but the operation has yet to be 'confirmed' as successful or failed. This stage is typical for rodent eradication operations, with confirmation monitoring occurring 1–2 years after the eradication operation has ended
In progress	Eradication operation is currently in progress at time of reporting
Planned	Eradication is being planned at time of reporting. End year will be unknown accordingly
Incomplete	An eradication was started, but not followed through to completion

Trial or research only	The eradication was undertaken for trial or research purposes and the goal was to gain new knowledge, not eradicate invasive species
Unknown	Information does not allow allocation into one of the other mutually exclusive categories and an expert cannot do the same (e.g. unclear if an eradication took place or if the species 'died out' naturally). Selection of this category will often be aligned with poor data quality
Unknown pre-status	Eradication was undertaken but the status of the invasive species was unclear beforehand. Typically undertaken for precautionary measures for rodent eradications

1165

1166 Details of 26 site management plans submitted after the completion of the first report are provided
 1167 in Table S5.8. These were assessed using the guidelines for the drafting of such plans published by the
 1168 DFFtE⁵. See section 7.4.4 of the first report for details.

1169 **Table S5.8** Site Management Plans (referred to as Invasive Species Monitoring, Control and
 1170 Eradication Plans in the NEM:BA A&IS Regulations) received by the Department of Forestry, Fisheries
 1171 and the Environment during the period of the second status report. The scores are as per the
 1172 Guidelines for Monitoring, Control and Eradication Plans (Department of Environmental Affairs, 2015).
 1173 Each plan was assessed following the methodology outlined in the first report (see Wilson et al. 2018).
 1174 Excluding the Port of Durban and the Port of Richards Bay, these plans cover 648 294 ha.

Entity / person	Type	Hectares covered	Score	Evaluation
Buffalo City Metropolitan Municipality	Organ of state	250000	4.17	Adequate
City of Cape Town (Erf 7775 Kommetjie)	Organ of state	5.12	3.33	Partially adequate
Eskom (Aberdeen Wind Farm)	Organ of state	8302	3.67	Partially adequate
Eskom (Ankerlig Open Cycle Gas Turbine Facility)	Organ of state	94.1	1.5	Inadequate
Eskom (Bantamsklip Nuclear Site)	Organ of state	1708.83	2.83	Partially adequate
Eskom (Groot Oliphants Kop Farm: Sterrekus HV Yard)	Organ of state	663.9	2.83	Partially adequate
Eskom (Kleinzee Wind Farm)	Organ of state	15743.15	2.5	Partially adequate
Eskom (Matimba Power Station)	Organ of state	1756	4	Partially adequate
Knysna Local Municipality	Organ of state	1791	1.67	Partially adequate
La Plaisance Stud Farm	Private landowner	70	3.83	Partially adequate
Maloti Drakensberg Transfrontier Conservation and Development Programme	Protected area	312014.59	3.5	Partially adequate
Rheinmettal Denel Munition (Somerset West)	Organ of state	455.18	3.33	Partially adequate
Rheinmettal Denel Munition (Wellington Site)	Organ of state	3300	3.67	Partially adequate
Samancor Chrome Ltd (TC Smelter)	Private landowner	170	3	Partially adequate
Tongaat Hulett (Agricultural Operations)	Private landowner	19500	3.17	Partially adequate
Transnet (Port of Saldanha)	Organ of state	359.67	3.33	Partially adequate
Transnet (Salt River Region)	Organ of state	358	3.33	Partially adequate
Transnet National Ports Authority (Port of Durban)	Organ of state	Not provided	3.83	Partially adequate

⁵www.environment.gov.za/sites/default/files/legislations/nemba_invasivespecies_controlguideline.pdf

Transnet National Ports Authority (Port of East London)	Organ of state	230.57	2.83	Partially adequate
Transnet National Ports Authority (Port of Ngqura)	Organ of state	863	4.17	Adequate
Transnet National Ports Authority (Port of Port Elizabeth)	Organ of state	120	3.67	Partially adequate
Transnet National Ports Authority (Port of Richards Bay)	Organ of state	Not provided	4	Partially adequate
uMdoni Local Municipality	Organ of state	23800	3.83	Partially adequate
Wilderness Properties (Erf 65, Hoekwil)	Private landowner	3.8	4.17	Adequate
Witzenberg Local Municipality (Ceres Mountain Fynbos Reserve)	Protected Area	6985	3.67	Partially adequate

1175

1176 **S5.8 Pathways treated**

1177 Pathways treated is the number of pathways requiring management that are managed to some
1178 degree. As in the first report, all pathways should require management. Although organisms might
1179 not have been introduced through some pathways, changes to socio-economic trends could lead to
1180 introductions through these pathways. In the first report, it was reported that 77.3% of the 44
1181 pathways are managed, 31.8% with partial management and 45.5% with complete management. The
1182 data collected for the first report has been reinterpreted and a revised baseline calculated due to the
1183 proposed revisions of the pathway classification framework of the Convention on Biological Diversity
1184 (Harrower et al., 2018). Two pathways for which management was rated as ‘complete’ in the first
1185 report were combined, and a new pathway, which had ‘partial’ management at the time of the first
1186 report, was added. Therefore, the revised baseline is that 77.3% of pathways were managed, 34.1%
1187 with partial management and 43.2% with complete management. There has been no change to this
1188 estimate for the second report. Currently, all pathways with management plans in place are managed
1189 to some degree, except ballast water for which the legislation has not yet been passed and plans have
1190 not been implemented. As permits are required to import alien taxa, all pathways that involve the
1191 intentional introduction of alien taxa have complete management (43.2% of pathways). As
1192 interventions for pathways that involve the accidental introduction of alien taxa are not in place at all
1193 ports of entry and do not cover all imports, these pathways have partial management (34.1% of
1194 pathways). As this assessment is largely based on the knowledge of experts and data that are not
1195 pathway-specific, the confidence is low. See Appendix 3 for the data used in this assessment and for
1196 our confidence in the assessment for each pathway.

1197 **S5.9 Species treated**

1198 Information was supplied by various organisations that collectively contributed to the management
1199 of 175 invasive species where the goal is either containment or impact reduction (Table S5.9), 57 taxa

1200 where the goal is nation-wide eradication, 12 taxa targeted for eradication from South Africa's islands,
1201 and 21 taxa that are not currently listed, but were subjected to management for other reasons (for
1202 example the removal of non-invasive species from protected areas, or species for which the feasibility
1203 of management and regulation is still being assessed).

1204

1205 **Table S5.9.** Alien species listed as 1b, 2 or 3 that were subjected to management in South Africa in 2018 and 2019, with estimates of money spent where
 1206 available (for information on taxa listed as 1a or where eradication attempts are proposed or underway see Table S5.6). Data are from the Department of
 1207 Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment’s Natural Resource Management Programmes, CapeNature and South African National Parks; from Davies et al.
 1208 (2020) for control of vertebrate and invertebrate species; from the Centre for Biological Control, Rhodes University and the Agricultural Research Council for
 1209 the costs and target species for biological control. Costs are over two years, from the 2017/18 and 2018/19 financial years. Data on how budget was allocated
 1210 to specific species targeted for biological control are not known, though the total spending on such is. In cases where other money has been spent on some
 1211 taxa, average values for biocontrol, derived by dividing the budget allocation for these activities by the number of species being managed, have been included.
 1212 Categories follow the NEM:BA A&IS listings; context-specific refers to species that are listed in different categories depending on the area or ecosystem in
 1213 which they are found; ‘SUSPECT’ refers to Species Under Surveillance for Possible Eradication or Containment Targeting.

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Acacia baileyana</i> F.Muell.	Bailey’s wattle	Terrestrial plant	3	2429373	307 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes; biological control assessed as negligible; research ongoing
<i>Acacia cyclops</i> A.Cunn. ex G.Don	Rooikrans	Terrestrial plant	1b	24311570	8 840 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programme; biological control assessed as substantial; research ongoing
<i>Acacia dealbata</i> Link	Silver wattle	Terrestrial plant	2	32879486	2 310 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as negligible; research ongoing
<i>Acacia decurrens</i> Willd.	Green wattle	Terrestrial plant	2	6822252	583 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as negligible; research ongoing
<i>Acacia elata</i> A.Cunn. ex Benth.	Pepper tree wattle	Terrestrial plant	1b	227588	74 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Acacia longifolia</i> (Andrews) Willd.	Long-leaved wattle	Terrestrial plant	1b	5058100	1 475 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial
<i>Acacia mearnsii</i> De Wild.	Black wattle	Terrestrial plant	2	335299764	36 484 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial; research ongoing
<i>Acacia melanoxylon</i> R.Br.	Australian blackwood	Terrestrial plant	2	4494853	1 206 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial
<i>Acacia podalyriifolia</i> A.Cunn. ex G.Don	Pearl acacia	Terrestrial plant	1b	1643040	12 ha subjected to control operations in South African National Parks Research into biological control ongoing.

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Acacia pycnantha</i> Benth.	Golden wattle	Terrestrial plant	1b	2112790	48 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial
<i>Acacia saligna</i> (Labill.) H.L.Wendl.	Port Jackson	Terrestrial plant	1b	54236833	13 052 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial; research ongoing
<i>Acridotheres tristis</i> Linnaeus, 1766	Common Myna	Bird	3	Not known	No formal control, but occasional removal
<i>Agave americana</i> L. var. <i>americana</i>	American agave	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	188351	91 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Agave sisalana</i> Perrine	Sisal	Terrestrial plant	2	327304	48 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Ageratina adenophora</i> (Spreng.) R.M.King & H.Rob.	Crofton weed	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Biological control only, which was assessed as negligible.
<i>Ageratina riparia</i> (Regel) R.M.King & H.Rob	Mistflower	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Biological control only, which was assessed as negligible.
<i>Ageratum houstonianum</i> (Mill.) M.Sharma	Mexican ageratum	Terrestrial plant	1b	215896	7 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Alnus glutinosa</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Black elder	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Amsinckia retrorsa</i> Suksd	Fiddleneck	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i> Linnaeus, 1758	Mallard	Bird	2	Not known	Some control operations in Cape Town
<i>Anredera cordifolia</i> (Ten.) Steenis	Madeira vine	Terrestrial plant	1b	2107163	331 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes Subject of ongoing biological control research
<i>Antigonon leptopus</i> Hook. & Arn.1838	Coral creeper	Terrestrial plant	1b	15796	2 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Yellow-flowered Mexican poppy	Terrestrial plant	1b	529362	94 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Argemone ochroleuca</i> Sweet	White-flowered Mexican poppy	Terrestrial plant	1b	567152	72 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Arundo donax</i> L. 1753	giant reed	Terrestrial plant	1b	10210345	647 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes Subject of ongoing biological control research
<i>Atriplex lindleyi</i>	Lindley's saltbush	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Atriplex nummularia</i> subsp. <i>nummularia</i> Lindl. 1848	old man saltbush	Terrestrial plant	2	138948	363 ha subjected to control operations in South African National Parks
<i>Atriplex semibaccata</i> R.Br.	Australian saltbush	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Austrocylindropuntia subulata</i> subsp. <i>exaltata</i> (A.Berger) D.R.Hunt	long spine cactus	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Subject to biological control, effectiveness not yet determined
<i>Azolla filiculoides</i> Lam.	azolla	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Under complete biological control; research ongoing
<i>Caesalpinia decapetala</i> (Roth) Alston	Mauritius thorn	Terrestrial plant	1b	23988655	1 583 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as negligible; research ongoing
<i>Callistemon rigidus</i> R.Br.	stiff-leaved bottlebrush	Terrestrial plant	Context-specific	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Campuloclinium macrocephalum</i> (Less.) DC.	pompom weed	Terrestrial plant	1b	51847755	15 810 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Effectiveness of biological control not yet determined; research ongoing
<i>Canna indica</i> L.	Indian shot	Terrestrial plant	1b	177827	22 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Capra hircus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	goat	Terrestrial mammal	1a on offshore islands (not listed on the mainland)	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Carcinus maenus</i>	Mediterranean Green Crab	Marine invertebrate	1b	884632	Eradication trial (research project). Estimated cost from Mabin <i>et al.</i> 2020. Eradication was found to be an unfeasible goal, and the species regarded as not a priority for management.
<i>Cardiospermum grandiflorum</i> Swartz	balloon vine	Terrestrial plant	1b	4543944	489 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes Effectiveness of biological control not yet determined
<i>Casuarina cunninghamiana</i> Miq.	beefwood	Terrestrial plant	Context-specific	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Cereus hildmannianus</i> K.Schum.	queen of the night	Terrestrial plant	1b	0	Under complete biological control
<i>Cereus jamacaru</i> DC.	queen of the night	Terrestrial plant	1b	4691104	27 402 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Under complete biological control; research ongoing
<i>Cestrum laevigatum</i> Schltldl.	inkberry	Terrestrial plant	1b	1645238	235 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes Subject of ongoing biological control research
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> (L.) R.M.King & H.Rob.	triffid weed, Chromolaena	Terrestrial plant	1b	3841165	135 589 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Effectiveness of biological control not yet determined; research is ongoing
<i>Cirsium vulgare</i> (Savi) Ten.	spear thistle	Terrestrial plant	1b	1636359	100 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programme. Biological control assessed as negligible
<i>Cortaderia jubata</i> (Lemoine) Stapf.	pampas grass	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Cortaderia selloana</i> (Schult.) Asch. & Graebn.	pampas grass	Terrestrial plant	1b	9036	100 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Cryptostegia grandiflora</i> Roxb.	rubber vine	Terrestrial plant	1b	1354	38 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Cylindropuntia fulgida</i> (Engelm.) F.M.Knuth var. <i>fulgida</i>	chain-fruit cholla (previously known as rosea cactus)	Terrestrial plant	1b	1636847	22 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Under complete biological control
<i>Cylindropuntia fulgida</i> var. <i>mamillata</i> (Schott ex Engelm.) Backeb.	boxing-glove cactus	Terrestrial plant	1b	1634322	Under complete biological control

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Cylindropuntia imbricata</i> (Haw.) F.M.Knuth	imbricate cactus	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Biological control assessed as substantial; research ongoing
<i>Cylindropuntia leptocaulis</i> (DC.) F.M.Knuth	pencil cactus	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Under complete biological control
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	common carp	Freshwater fish	Context-specific	Not known	Has been controlled successfully in some areas
<i>Dama dama</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	fallow deer	Terrestrial mammal	2	Not known	Control ongoing on Robben Island
<i>Datura ferox</i> L.	large thorn apple	Terrestrial plant	1b	642	229 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Datura stramonium</i> L.	common thorn apple	Terrestrial plant	1b	116256	506 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Dolichandra unguis-cati</i> L. (A.Gentry)	cat's claw creeper	Terrestrial plant	1b	1634333	0.2 ha subjected to control operations in South African National Parks. Biological control assessed as negligible; research is ongoing
<i>Echinopsis spachiana</i>	white torch cactus	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	82015	406 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Echium plantagineum</i> L.	Patterson's curse	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (Mart.) Solms	water hyacinth	Freshwater aquatic plant	1b	4199973	156 092 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial; research ongoing
<i>Equus asinus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	donkey	Terrestrial mammal	Unlisted	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> Dehnh.	river red gum	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	1100039	42 320 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Eucalyptus cladocalyx</i> F.Muell.	sugar gum	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	311368	12 799 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Eucalyptus conferruminata</i> D.J.Carr & S.G.M.Carr	spider gum	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	21242	2 665 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Eucalyptus diversicolor</i> F.Muell.	karri	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	17982	468 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Eucalyptus ficifolia</i>	red flowering gum	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill.	blue gum	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	11845	333 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Eucalyptus grandis</i> W.Hill ex Maiden	saligna gum	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	2188278	62 701 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Eucalyptus paniculata</i> Sm.	grey ironbark	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	34264	1 353 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Eucalyptus sideroxylon</i> A.Cunn ex Woolls	swamp mahogany gum	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	32376	1 272 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i> Sm.	forest red gum	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	6537	409 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Euwallacea fornicatus</i>	polyphagous shot hole borer	Terrestrial invertebrate	Unlisted	2500000	Feasibility of biological control investigated at the Forestry and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute, Pretoria University
<i>Flaveria bidentis</i> (L) Kuntze	smelter's-bush	Terrestrial plant	1b	343	16 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i> A.W.Hill	fennel	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Gambusia affinis</i> (Baird & Girard, 1853)	mosquito-fish	Freshwater fish	Context-specific	Not known	Has been controlled successfully in one area
<i>Gleditsia triacanthos</i> L.	honey locust	Terrestrial plant	1b	1652822	494 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Effectiveness of biological control not yet determined; research ongoing
<i>Grevillea robusta</i> A.Cunn. ex R.Br	Australian silky oak	Terrestrial plant	3	21893	86 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Hakea drupacea</i> (C.F.Gaertn.) Roem. & Schult.	sweet hakea	Terrestrial plant	1b	538697	1 487 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Hakea gibbosa</i> Cav.	rock hakea	Terrestrial plant	1b	1895863	2 005 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as negligible; research is ongoing
<i>Hakea sericea</i> Schrad. & J.C.Wendl.	silky hakea	Terrestrial plant	1b	3061521	11 379 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial; research is ongoing

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Harrisia tortuosa</i> Britton & Rose.	spiny snake cactus	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Biological control assessed as substantial.
<i>Hemitragus jemlahicus</i> (C.H. Smith, 1826)	Himalayan tahr	Terrestrial mammal	1b	Not known	Ongoing control in Table Mountain National Park, with ultimate goal of eradication
<i>Hordeum murinum</i> L.	wild barley	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Hypericum androsaemum</i> L.	sweet-amber	Terrestrial plant	1b	3077	8 ha subjected to control operations in South African National Parks
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i> L.	St. John's wort	Terrestrial plant	2	1640265	416 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes Under complete biological control
<i>Ipomoea carnea</i> Jacq. subsp. <i>fistulosa</i> (Mart. ex Choisy) D.F.Austin	morning-glory bush	Terrestrial plant	1b	297419	10 600 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Ipomoea indica</i> (Burm.) Merr.	morning glory	Terrestrial plant	1b	251070	1 213 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Jacaranda mimosifolia</i> D.Don	jacaranda	Terrestrial plant	Context-specific	150447	7 367 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	lantana	Terrestrial plant	1b	12985178	501 759 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as negligible (Highveld) to substantial (coastal and Lowveld); research is ongoing
<i>Lepomis macrochirus</i> Rafinesque, 1819	bluegill sunfish	Freshwater fish	Context-specific	Not known	Has been controlled successfully in some areas
<i>Leptospermum laevigatum</i> (Gaertn.) F.Muell.	Australian myrtle	Terrestrial plant	1b	2519706	13 237 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as negligible; research is ongoing
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i> (Lam.) De Wit.	leucaena	Terrestrial plant	2	1639250	399 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes Biological control assessed as negligible
<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	seringa	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	749992	44 136 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Micropterus dolomieu</i> Lacepède, 1802	small-mouth bass	Freshwater fish	Context-specific	Not known	Has been controlled successfully in some areas
<i>Micropterus floridanus</i> Lesueur, 1822	Florida bass	Freshwater fish	Context-specific	Not known	Has been controlled successfully in some areas
<i>Micropterus punctulatus</i> (Rafinesque, 1819)	spotted bass	Freshwater fish	Context-specific	Not known	Has been controlled successfully in some areas
<i>Micropterus salmoides</i> (Lacepède, 1802)	large-mouth bass	Freshwater fish	Context-specific	Not known	Has been controlled successfully in some areas
<i>Myoporum montanum</i> R.Br.	manatoka	Terrestrial plant	3	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Myriophyllum aquaticum</i> (Vell.) Verdc.	parrot's feather	Freshwater aquatic plant	1b	Not known	Under complete biological control; research ongoing
<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	oleander	Terrestrial plant	1b	298563	713 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Nicotiana glauca</i>	wild tobacco	Terrestrial plant	1b	1723130	43 026 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i> (Walbaum, 1792)	rainbow trout	Freshwater fish	Unlisted	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Opuntia aurantiaca</i> Lindl.	jointed cactus	Terrestrial plant	1b	7403209	30 980 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial; research ongoing
<i>Opuntia engelmannii</i> Salm-Dyck ex Engelm.	small round-leaved prickly pear	Terrestrial plant	1b	1720681	1 156 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as negligible
<i>Opuntia ficus-indica</i> (L.) Mill.	mission prickly pear	Terrestrial plant	1b	3759391	27 122 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial; research ongoing
<i>Opuntia humifusa</i> Raf. (Raf.)	large-flowered prickly pear	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Under complete biological control; research ongoing
<i>Opuntia microdasys</i> (Lehm.) Pfeiff.	yellow bunny-ears	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Opuntia monacantha</i> Haw.	cochineal prickly pear	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Under complete biological control; research ongoing
<i>Opuntia spinulifera</i> Salm-Dyck.	saucepan cactus	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Biological control only; effectiveness not yet determined
<i>Opuntia stricta</i> (Haw.) Haw. var. <i>stricta</i> (Ker Gawl.) L.D.Benson	Australian pest pear	Terrestrial plant	1b	1639194	1733 ha managed by South African National Parks Biological control assessed as substantial; research ongoing
<i>Oreochromis mossambicus</i>	Mozambique tilapia	Freshwater fish	Not listed (native species with some extralimital populations)	Not known	Has been controlled successfully in one project
<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	European rabbit	Terrestrial mammal	1b on islands	Not known	Ongoing control on Robben Island
<i>Paraserianthes lophantha</i> (Willd.) I.C.Nielsen	Australian albizia	Terrestrial plant	1b	1821363	3 008 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial
<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	parthenium weed	Terrestrial plant	1b	16657749	224 810 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Effectiveness of biological control not yet determined; research is ongoing
<i>Peniocereus serpentinus</i> (Lag. & Rodr.) N.P.Taylor	serpent cactus	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Biological control only; effectiveness not yet determined
<i>Pennisetum clandestinum</i> Hochst. ex Chiov.	Kikuyu grass	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	12703	1 750 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i> Schumach.	elephant grass	Terrestrial plant	2	6917	387 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> (Forssk.) Chiov.	fountain grass	Terrestrial plant	1b	27120	453 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Pereskia aculeata</i> Mill.	pereskia	Terrestrial plant	1b	1637754	631 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes Effectiveness of biological control not yet determined; research ongoing

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Phytolacca icosandra</i>	tropical pokeweed	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	2589	51 ha subjected to control operations in South African National Parks
<i>Phytolacca octandra</i> L.	forest inkberry	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Pinus canariensis</i> C.Sm	canary pine	Terrestrial plant	3	22	32 ha subjected to control operations in South African National Parks; also controlled by CapeNature
<i>Pinus elliottii</i> Engelm.	slash pine	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	26 255	112 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Pinus halepensis</i> Mill.	aleppo pine	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	49267	3 013 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Pinus patula</i> Schiede ex Schlttdl. & Cham.	patula pine	Terrestrial plant	2	114712	5 357 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Pinus pinaster</i> Aiton	cluster pine	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	2106770	26 264 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Pinus pinea</i> L.	umbrella pine	Terrestrial plant	unlisted	9622	397 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Pinus radiata</i> D.Don	Monterey pine	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	1411244	26 294 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i> L.	water lettuce	Freshwater aquatic plant	1b	1749102	14 313 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as complete; research ongoing
<i>Pittosporum undulatum</i> Vent.	Australian cheesewood	Terrestrial plant	1b	5976	215 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Polistes dominula</i> (Christ, 1791)	European Paper Wasp	Terrestrial invertebrate	1b	Not known	Subject to control in local areas; eradication may be feasible.
<i>Populus × canescens</i> (Aiton) Sm.	grey poplar	Terrestrial plant	2	791623	43 348 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Populus alba</i> L.	white poplar	Terrestrial plant	2	525725	33 096 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Populus deltoides</i> Marshall	match poplar	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	28163	432 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Prosopis glandulosa</i> or <i>velutina</i>	mesquite	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	16721140	230 544 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as negligible; research ongoing

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Prosopis velutina</i> Wooton	velvet mesquite	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	1634584	26 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes Biological control assessed as negligible; research is ongoing
<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	guava	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	567382	26 954 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Pyracantha angustifolia</i> (Franch.) C.K.Schneid.	yellow firethorn	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Feasibility of biological control being investigated at Rhodes University
<i>Pyracantha rogersiana</i>	Asian firethorn	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	25886	613 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Quercus robur</i> L.	english oak	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	Not known	Subjected to control operations in CapeNature protected areas
<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	castor-oil plant	Terrestrial plant	2	148909	15 950 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i> L.	black locust	Terrestrial plant	1b	1696350	3 355 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Feasibility of biological control investigated at Rhodes University
<i>Rosa eglanteria</i>	sweetbriar rose	Terrestrial plant	Unlisted	47619	2 478 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Rosa rubiginosa</i> L.	eglantine, sweetbriar	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Feasibility of biological control investigated at Rhodes University
<i>Rubus cuneifolius</i> Pursh.	American bramble	Terrestrial plant	1b	2572472	111 415 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Rubus fruticosus</i> Lour.	European blackberry	Terrestrial plant	2	22293	669 ha subjected to control operations in South African National Parks; also controlled by CapeNature
<i>Salvinia molesta</i> D.S.Mitch.	Kariba weed	Freshwater aquatic plant	1b	1656267	3 158 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Under complete biological control; research ongoing
<i>Schefflera actinophylla</i> (Endl.) Harms	Australian cabbage tree	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	5	6 ha subjected to control operations in South African National Parks
<i>Schinus terebinthifolius</i> Raddi	Brazilian pepper tree	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	11542	1 332 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Sclerophrys gutturalis</i> (Power, 1927)	African common toad	Freshwater amphibian	Not listed (native species with some extralimital populations)	Not known	Control is ongoing in invaded areas in Cape Town
<i>Senna bicapsularis</i> (L.) Roxb.	rambling cassia	Terrestrial plant	1b	8049	256 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Senna didymobotrya</i> (Fresen.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	peanut butter cassia	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	132836	7 664 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Sesbania punicea</i> (Cav.) Benth.	red sesbania	Terrestrial plant	1b	1951730	10 864 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Under complete biological control
<i>Solanum chrysotrichum</i> Schlttdl.	giant devil's fig	Terrestrial plant	1b	35352	802 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Solanum elaeagnifolium</i> Cav.	silver-leaf bitter apple	Terrestrial plant	1b	1634879	4 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as substantial
<i>Solanum mauritianum</i> Scop.	bugweed	Terrestrial plant	1b	3755391	140 690 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Biological control assessed as negligible; research ongoing
<i>Solanum seafortianum</i> Andrews	potato creeper	Terrestrial plant	1b	57107	437 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Solanum sisymbriifolium</i> Lam.	wild tomato	Terrestrial plant	1b	3755391	Biological control assessed as substantial
<i>Spartium junceum</i> L.	Spanish broom	Terrestrial plant	Context specific	7338	1 492 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Sus scrofa</i> Linnaeus, 1758	domestic pig	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Ongoing control of two populations in the Western Cape
<i>Tamarix aphylla</i> (L.) H.Karst.	athel tree	Terrestrial plant	1b	7790	429 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Tamarix chinensis</i> Lour.	Chinese tamarisk	Terrestrial plant	1b	97298	4 808 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes

Scientific Name	Vernacular name	Regulatory Grouping	Regulatory Listing	Cost of control (ZAR)	Notes
<i>Tamarix ramosissima</i> Ledeb.	pink tamarisk	Terrestrial plant	1b	43974	6 309 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Tecoma stans</i> (L.) Juss. ex Kunth	yellow bells	Terrestrial plant	1b	1723231	3 555 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Effectiveness of biological control not yet determined; research is ongoing
<i>Thevetia peruviana</i> (Pers.) K.Schum.	yellow oleander	Terrestrial plant	1b	170982	3 683 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Tilapia sparrmanii</i>	banded tilapia	Freshwater fish	Not listed (native species with some extralimital populations)	Not known	Has been controlled successfully in one project
<i>Tinca tinca</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	tench	Freshwater fish	Context-specific	Not known	Has been controlled successfully in one project
<i>Tipuana tipu</i> (Benth.) Kuntze	tipu tree	Terrestrial plant	3	37697	2 450 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i> (Hemsl.) A.Gray	Mexican sunflower	Terrestrial plant	1b	1795390	3 613 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Subject of biological control research
<i>Tithonia rotundifolia</i> S.F.Blake (Mill.)	red sunflower	Terrestrial plant	1b	1681847	2 339 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes. Subject of biological control research
<i>Tradescantia fluminensis</i> Vell.	white-flowered wandering Jew	Terrestrial plant	1b	Not known	Eradication target managed by SANBI
<i>Verbena bonariensis</i> L.	wild verbena	Terrestrial plant	1b	133685	4 574 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Vespula germanica</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	European wasp	Terrestrial invertebrate	1b	Not known	Subject to control in some areas; eradication may be feasible
<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	large cocklebur	Terrestrial invertebrate	1b	397030	27 104 ha subjected to control operations by the DFFtE NRM programmes
<i>Xenopus laevis</i> x <i>gilli</i> (Daudin, 1802) Rose & Hewitt, 1927	African clawed toad x Cape (Gill's) platanna	Freshwater amphibian	1b	Not known	Subject to control in Table Mountain National Park

1215 *Biocontrol releases*. Seven biological control agents have been released against 10 invasive plants
 1216 species following the publication of the first report (Table S5.10).

1217 **Table S5.10.** Biological control agents released to control invasive plant species in South Africa during
 1218 2017–2019 or that were not reported in the first report (C. Zachariades, pers. comm. 2019).

Scientific name of target	Vernacular name of target	Scientific name of agent	Family or sub-family of agent	Feeding guild	Year released
<i>Acacia baileyana</i> & <i>A. decurrens</i> [also attacks <i>A. dealbata</i> , <i>A. podalyriifolia</i>]	Various (wattles)	<i>Dasineura pilifera</i>	Diptera: Cecidomyiidae	Flower galler	2016
<i>Anredera cordifolia</i>	Madeira vine	<i>Plectonycha correntina</i>	Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae	Leaf feeder	2016
<i>Egeria densa</i>	dense water weed	<i>Hydrellia egerieae</i>	Diptera: Ephydriidae	Leaf miner	2019
<i>Lantana camara</i>	lantana	<i>Puccinia lantanae</i>	Pucciniales: Pucciniaceae	Leaf- and stem-rust pathogen	2018
<i>Paraserianthes lophantha</i>	Australian albizia	<i>Uromycladium woodii</i>	Pucciniales: Pileolariaceae	Gall former	2016
<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Mexican sunflower	<i>Physonota maculiventris</i>	Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Cassidinae	Leaf feeder	2018
<i>Tradescantia fluminensis</i>	white-flowered wandering Jew	<i>Neolema abbreviata</i>	Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Criocerinae	Shoot-tip and leaf feeder	2019

1219

1220 *Eradication targets*. It is becoming increasingly clear that many of the alien species listed as category
 1221 1a are not appropriate as targets for nation-wide eradication. Several species have been found to be
 1222 present at many sites across the country [e.g. yellow flag (*Iris pseudacorus*) (Jaca and Mkhize 2015),
 1223 and Mauritian Hemp (*Furcraea foetida*)]. Several of the species [cabomba (*Cabomba caroliniana*) and
 1224 leafy spurge (*Euphorbia esula*)] have not been re-found, and might simply not be in the country, while
 1225 others are not known to have become invasive and were listed for precautionary purposes (Henderson
 1226 and Wilson 2017). Several of the species are found in private gardens e.g. ant tree (*Triplaris*
 1227 *americana*). While this does not preclude eventual eradication, it complicates both control efforts and
 1228 the confidence with which an eradication can be declared. A few of the Cactaceae species have (or
 1229 will likely in future have) effective biocontrol agents, such that nation-wide eradication would
 1230 probably not be required for adequate control to be achieved. Consequently, only around a third of
 1231 the species listed in category 1a are still the focus of on-going eradication efforts. By contrast, many
 1232 other taxa that are not yet listed in the regulations have been identified as eradication targets and are
 1233 subject to control efforts (e.g. sticky wattle (*Acacia viscidula*), and rough-barked honey myrtle
 1234 (*Melaleuca parvistaminea*). However, the formal process of documenting the evidence, conducting a

1235 risk analysis (that is approved through ASRARP), and the DFFtE consulting stakeholders and making a
1236 decision to transfer a species to more appropriate management categories has not been completed
1237 yet (the relevant decision making body at DFFtE was still to be constituted as of June 2020).

1238 In the decade that SANBI's unit [which has a focus on incursion response (Wilson et al. 2013)] has been
1239 active, no alien plants have been formally declared as eradicated. The project closest to achieving
1240 eradication is probably that against smooth cordgrass (*Spartina alterniflora*), a grass invading the
1241 Knysna estuary in the Western Cape. However, the conditions under which eradication can be
1242 declared have not been specified, nor is it clear how or why the plant was introduced in the first place,
1243 so the possibility of reintroduction has not been ruled out. Detailed point patterns have been
1244 produced for a number of species (Wilson et al. 2013), and insights have been gained in terms of
1245 efforts to delimit populations (Jacobs et al. 2014), producing risk maps (Kaplan et al. 2014), estimating
1246 the costs of eradication (Moore et al. 2011), and the continuing need for morphological and molecular
1247 taxonomy (Magona et al. 2018; Jacobs et al. 2017).

1248 The SANBI project has also made a significant contribution to funding postgraduate students that work
1249 on particular species or taxa, and has produced an increasing number of published eradication
1250 feasibility assessments. However, the programme has suffered from similar issues to other projects
1251 funded under the Working for Water umbrella. The onus has been to report on input indicators (e.g.
1252 person days of employment), and few or no data are routinely collected on output indicators (e.g. the
1253 number of plants present). When assessed against the requirements set by the first report, the project
1254 planning was evaluated as being inadequate across the board. These are solvable issues, but would
1255 require a shift in approach to ensure that dedicated teams focus on specific targets year on year, that
1256 data are collected, and that monitoring data feed back into decision-making both at a project level
1257 and as input to the regulatory changes. If the global best practices regarding alien plant incursion
1258 response are applied (e.g. Wilson et al. 2017), then we can expect to see an increasing number of
1259 declared alien plant eradications in the next decade. For some taxa, particularly those with long-lived
1260 seed-banks (Zenni et al. 2009; Wilson et al. 2011), eradication might only be achieved far in the future,
1261 but it is feasible given persistence and effective monitoring.

1262 **S5.10 Sites treated**

1263 A recent unpublished NRM programme report provided information on how frequently sites are
1264 treated for alien plants (Figure S5.3). Most sites require regular maintenance management to keep
1265 invasions in check, although these data suggest that more than half of sites (54%) have been managed
1266 three or fewer times in the past twenty years (i.e. a return interval of seven years or more), and no

1267 site has been managed annually. However, these data might not reflect recent trends as the first time
1268 many of these sites will have been managed will have been much later than 1998.

1269

1270

1271 **Figure S5.3** The number of times particular sites have been cleared of alien plants by management
1272 facilitated by the NRM programmes over the past twenty years. A site in this context is a spatial
1273 polygon as defined for management purposes by the NRM programmes. These data are based on a
1274 stratified random sample of 1130 sites out of 116,495 such sites (i.e., ~1% of all sites).

1275

1276 **Table S5.11** The number of notifications (pre-compliance notices, compliance notices, and warning letters) and directives (pre-directive and directive) that
 1277 were issued for activities with listed alien species in South Africa, 2014–2016. The data were obtained from the DFFtE. Most enforcement action involved the
 1278 contravention of more than one section or regulation, so the totals are less than the sums of each column. These data were not available for 2017 – 2019 at
 1279 the time of finalising this report but were reported in the first report. This table provides a framework for future reports.

Section / Regulation contravened	Pre-compliance notices		Compliance notices		Pre-directives		Directives		Prosecution		Convictions	
	2014–2016	2017–2019	2014–2016	2017–2019	2014–2016	2017–2019	2014–2016	2017–2019	2014–2016	2017–2019	2014–2016	2017–2019
Failure by a landowner to notify the Minister of a category 1a listed alien species occurring on his or her land (Reg 2(2) and Sec 73(2))	38	NA	3	NA	68	NA	5	NA	5	NA	0	NA
Failure to control a category 1b listed alien species in accordance with appropriate methods (Reg 3(2) and Sec 75(1), (2) and (3))	126	NA	6	NA	83	NA	6	NA	2	NA	0	NA
Conducting a restricted activity in relation to any listed alien species (Reg 4(2) and Sec 71(1))	25	NA	2	NA	51	NA	8	NA	5	NA	1	NA
Failure to ensure that listed alien species do not spread outside of the area specified in a permit or notice (Reg 4(3))	0	NA	0	NA	1	NA	0	NA	0	NA	0	NA
Failure to manage a category 3 listed alien species in accordance with appropriate methods (Reg 5(2) and Sec 75(1), (2) and (3))	2	NA	0	NA	0	NA	0	NA	0	NA	0	NA
Total	184	NA	10	NA	121	NA	12	NA	6	NA	1	NA

1280

1281 **Table S5.12** The number and type of properties served with notices and directives for restricted
 1282 activities with listed alien species in South Africa. The data were obtained from the DFFtE.

Contravener	Pre-compliance notices	Compliance notices	Pre-directives	Directives	Prosecution
Nurseries	126	2	0	0	0
Pet stores	21	3	0	0	0
Private landowners	36	5	115	11	6 (1 conviction)
Organs of state	1	0	6	1	0
TOTAL	184	10	121	12	6 (1 conviction)

1283

1284 **S5.11 Effectiveness of pathway treatments**

1285 The effectiveness of pathway treatments was determined, as in the first report, based on changes to
 1286 the rate of introduction in the last full decade in comparison to that of the previous decade, as well as
 1287 using additional, recently published data. The data collected for the first report has been reinterpreted
 1288 and a revised baseline calculated due to the collection of new data and due the proposed revision of
 1289 the pathway classification framework of the Convention on Biological Diversity (Harrower et al. 2018).
 1290 In the first report, rates of introduction between 1990 and 1999 were compared to those between
 1291 2000 and 2009. In the second report rates of introduction for 2000–2009 were compared to those of
 1292 2010–2019. Therefore, the results presented in the first and second reports are not directly
 1293 comparable. One pathway of introduction (aesthetic release) has permanent management (2.3%), as
 1294 this pathway is no longer present. Six pathways (13.6%) are effectively managed as there have been
 1295 no recent introductions or as the pathway is well regulated and there have been no illegal
 1296 introductions. However, 27 pathways (61.4%) have either no management or management is
 1297 ineffective as there has been either a minimal change or an increase in the rate of introduction, or as
 1298 there is evidence of illegal introductions or non-compliance. The management effectiveness of 10
 1299 pathways (22.7%) is not known as the data is inadequate. The effectiveness of pathway treatments
 1300 could be estimated for the first time for several pathways, but management appears to be either
 1301 absent or ineffective for all of these pathways (Table S5.13). As this assessment is based on incomplete
 1302 data or data that are not pathway-specific our confidence is low. See Appendix 3 for the data used in
 1303 this assessment and for our confidence in the assessment for each pathway.

1304 **Table S5.13** The pathways of introduction for which management effectiveness could be estimated
 1305 for the first time.

Pathway	Management effectiveness	Details
Stabilisation and barriers	None/ineffective	Bamboo species, including undocumented species, have been imported for purposes such as mine rehabilitation (Canavan et al., 2019)

Pathway	Management effectiveness	Details
Agriculture	None/ineffective	Exploration of plant species for uses such as biofuels and bioenergy has led to the import of various species, including undocumented bamboos (Canavan et al., 2019)
Horticulture	None/ineffective	Regulated species are still being sold at nurseries (Cronin et al., 2017)
Other escape	None/ineffective	Alien and invasive species, many as viable propagules, are being sold as part of the medicinal plant trade (Burness, 2019; Byrne et al., 2017)
Bait contaminant	None/ineffective	Based on data from the DALRRD, non-compliance with regulations that aim to prevent the introduction of contaminants of plant and animal products is high
Food contaminant	None/ineffective	Based on data from the DALRRD, non-compliance with regulations that aim to prevent the introduction of contaminants of plant and animal products is high
Seed contaminant	None/ineffective	Based on data from the DALRRD, non-compliance with regulations that aim to prevent the introduction of contaminants of plant and animal products is high
Timber trade contaminant	None/ineffective	Based on data from the DALRRD, non-compliance with regulations that aim to prevent the introduction of contaminants of plant and animal products is high

1306

1307 **S5.12 Effectiveness of species treatments**

1308 The effectiveness of species treatments has not been assessed due to a lack of information. The
1309 effectiveness of biological control programmes over the past 10 years is due to be reviewed in 2020,
1310 with findings published in 2021. A new approach has been developed to characterise the control
1311 success of biocontrol (Hoffmann et al. 2019). The approach incorporates four different invasion
1312 parameters (the density of plants, the area occupied, standing biomass and the number of seeds
1313 produced) on a nine-point scale, for different regions and habitats. It is hoped that this approach will
1314 assist in describing, succinctly and with greater precision, the outcomes of biological control at a plant
1315 population level. If this is done, then future status reports could adopt this framework as it links to at
1316 least some of the species-level indicators. However, it is still important to have an overall evaluation
1317 of effectiveness of the form used by Klein (2011), i.e. one that relates directly to management needs.

1318 **S5.13 Effectiveness of site treatments**

1319 The records relating to the sites in Figure S5.3 showed that alien plant cover decreased in 43% of the
1320 management units, remained unchanged in 26% of the units, and increased in 31% of the units.

1321 **Box S5.1 The Cape Town Water Fund**

1322 The Cape Town Water Fund is an ambitious plan to address the impacts of invasive trees on the water
1323 supply of Cape Town, Western Cape (Stafford et al. 2018). The project has assessed the returns on
1324 investment that would arise from the protection of ecological infrastructure in the water catchment

1325 areas surrounding Cape Town. The plan notes that, despite ongoing efforts to remove invasive trees
1326 by programmes such as Working for Water, the problem of invasive trees is increasing. The Nature
1327 Conservancy (a United States-based NGO), together with partners from government and the private
1328 sector, commissioned studies to evaluate the impact of nature-based solutions on water supply,
1329 beginning with targeted removals of plant invasions. Their goal was to evaluate whether investments
1330 into catchment restoration through the removal of invasive plants would be cost competitive with
1331 other supply-side solutions. The study estimated that investing ZAR 372 million in seven priority sub-
1332 catchments (54 300 ha) would generate annual gains of 100 billion litres (100 million m³) of water
1333 within thirty years, compared to the business as usual scenario. It was further estimated that invasive
1334 plant removal would yield up to an additional 50 billion litres (50 million m³) within five years, and
1335 would create approximately 350 job opportunities in the first five years of implementation. Catchment
1336 restoration was also estimated to be significantly more cost-effective than other water augmentation
1337 solutions, supplying water at one-tenth the unit cost of alternative options such as desalination,
1338 groundwater exploitation and water recycling. This plan promises to significantly strengthen the
1339 efforts to control invasive trees, and thus protect the vital water catchments that supply Cape Town.
1340 Note that a similar initiative in the same catchment is being funded by WWF (SA), but no details are
1341 available.

1342

1343

Box S5.1 Figure 1 Pine trees invading a water catchment area in the Western Cape

1344 **S5.14 Indicator values**

1345 **Table S5.14** Values for the indicators 12–20. Money spent on species is based on funds allocated to biological control, and eradication projects. All estimates
 1346 are made with a low level of confidence.

Indicator		Value end 2016	Value end 2019
12. Quality of the regulatory framework (input)	12.1 Overall quality	Substantial	Partial
	12.2 Quality assessed for different agencies and for collaboration	Data not available	Data not available
13. Money spent (input)	13.1 Annual government expenditure	ZAR 1100 million	ZAR 1050 million
	13.2 Annual government expenditure on species, pathways and sites	Pathways: No data Species: ZAR 55 million Areas: ZAR 950 million	Pathways: No data Species: ZAR 131.3 million Areas: ZAR 918.7 million
	13.3. Annual government and private sector expenditure on pathways, species and sites	No data	No data
14. Planning coverage (input)	14.1 The proportion of pathways, species, and sites that have a regulatory requirement for a management plan and that have a management plan in place.	79.5% of pathways have plans 9.5% of species have plans 4% of the country is covered by plans	79.5% of pathways have plans 20.8% of species have plans 4.5% of the country is covered by plans
	14.2 As for 14.1 with assessment of quality of management plans	Pathways: No data Species: 80% of species plans adequate; 20% partially adequate Areas: 2% of plans are adequate; 42% are partially adequate; 56% are inadequate	Pathways: No data Species: Not assessed Areas: 7.5% of plans are adequate; 61.1% are partially adequate; 31.4% are inadequate
	14.3 As for 14.2, with priority rankings	Pathways: No data Species: No data Areas: No data	Pathways: No data Species: No data Areas: No data

Indicator		Value end 2016	Value end 2019
15. Pathways treated (output)	15.1 The degree to which the pathways are subjected to a management intervention.	Not known: 0% None: 22.7% Partial: 34.1% Substantial: 0% Complete: 43.2%	Not known: 0% None: 22.7% Partial: 34.1% Substantial: 0% Complete: 43.2%
	15.2 Degree to which vectors within pathways are managed	No data	No data
	15.3 As for 15.2, with assessment of quality of interventions	No data	No data
16. Species treated (output)	16.1 Proportion of regulated species that are being subjected to a management intervention	24.3% of species are treated	34% of species are treated
	16.2 Proportion of regulated species in categories of management coverage.	Complete: 2.7% Substantial: 3.4% Partial: 18.3% None: 0% Not known: 75.6%	Not assessed
	16.3 As for 16.2, with assessment of quality of individual interventions	No data	No data
17. Sites treated (output)	17.1. Proportion of area that needs to be managed and is being managed.	0.36%	Not assessed
	17.2 As for 17.1, with interventions assessed for adequacy.	No data	No data
18. Effectiveness of pathways treatments (outcome)	18.1. Proportion of pathways in control effectiveness categories	Not known: 43.2% None/ineffective: 43.2% Partially effective: 0% Effective: 11.4% Permanent: 2.3% An assessment of the negative impacts of control has not been made.	Not known: 22.7% None/ineffective: 61.4% Partially effective: 0% Effective: 13.6% Permanent: 2.3% An assessment of the negative impacts of control has not been made.
	18.2 Pathways categorised by measurable outcomes AND a formal environmental and social assessment of non-target effects of the interventions	No data	No data
	18.3. Returns on investment for pathway interventions AND non-target impacts as costs	No data	No data

Indicator		Value end 2016	Value end 2019
19. Effectiveness of species treatments (outcome)	19.1. Proportion of species in control effectiveness categories	Not known: 20.4% None/ineffective: 73% Partially effective: 4.9% Effective: 0.9% Permanent: 0.8%	Not assessed
	19.2. Species categorised by measurable outcomes AND a formal environmental and social assessment of non-target effects of the interventions	No data	No data
	19.3. Returns on investment for species interventions	Benefit: cost ratios between 8:1 to 3000:1 for biological control	Not assessed
20. Effectiveness of site treatments (outcome)	20.1. Proportion of sites in control effectiveness categories	Not known: 99.6%	Not assessed
	21.2. Quantitative measure of control on relative invasive abundance or invasive species richness	No data	No data
	21.3. Return on investment expressed as a ratio of the amount spent on control to the value of avoided cost of impact.	Benefit: cost ratios between 0.03 and 0.75	Not assessed

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1351 **Supplementary Material to Chapter 6: Gaps**

1352 The process for identifying the gaps highlighted in Chapter 6 was initiated by the RAC tasking the writing team to identify a small number of key gaps that, if
1353 addressed, would substantially improve the value of the status report. In response to this request, each chapter lead author identified the most important
1354 gap for their section of the report (two gaps were identified for interventions given the scope of the chapter). The gaps thus identified were included in the
1355 draft reports with a specific request for comments, suggestions, and additional gaps. The input received from stakeholders was incorporated and discussed
1356 by the status report team. The final list of six gaps is presented and discussed in Chapter 6 itself.

1357 Separate to this, progress towards addressing the gaps highlighted in the first report was assessed and is presented below (Table S6.1).

1358 **Table S6.1** Progress towards filling the data and information gaps identified in the first report and the consequences of not filling these gaps. The second and
 1359 third columns are as presented in the first report and in italics. Progress was assessed qualitatively as: deteriorated (i.e. things have got worse); none (there
 1360 was no progress); minimal; moderate; substantial; complete; or not applicable.

Indicator	<i>Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report</i>	<i>Proposed solution</i>	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
HIGH-LEVEL (pathways) A. Rate of unregulated introduction of new species	<i>Knowledge of rates of introduction is largely based on observations of alien species post-border, rather than interceptions at border. It is not always possible to determine dates of introduction based on dates of first record. Only data on inputs and not on outputs are recorded. Currently, the Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF) is responsible for most surveillance with a focus on agricultural pests and diseases, and surveillance with respect to environmental concerns is only done consistently at one of the 72 entry points, and then only during certain working hours.</i>	<i>An integrated approach with other authorities that report and monitor the introduction of species at ports of entry is needed. Alignment by the Department of Environmental Affairs (DEA) with the DAFF processes is needed to ensure adequate monitoring and reporting on the rates of introduction on new species, and that relevant interception data with both positive and negative results are curated and included in future reports.</i>	MINIMAL The various authorities involved in monitoring and reporting interceptions at the border still have their own processes and approaches. It is not clear if efforts to align the various processes and ensure adequate monitoring and reporting have been implemented to a degree that allows for co-ordinated data management. A cross-cutting panel to make biosecurity decisions is being formed and this might assist with this.	An uncoordinated approach is likely to be more costly and less effective than a coordinated approach. For example, species that pose environmental threats could be overlooked at ports of entry where inspections only focus on agricultural pests or diseases. Without interception data with both positive and negative results and information on the inspection methods followed, the inspection methods cannot be assessed and improved.

Indicator	Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report	Proposed solution	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
<p>HIGH-LEVEL (species)</p> <p>B. Number of invasive species that have major impacts</p>	<p><i>There are few data on the impacts caused by even the most widespread species, and so this indicator cannot be estimated reliably.</i></p> <p><i>There is generally a dearth of accessible studies documenting impacts of alien species across all taxa.</i></p> <p><i>Studies of the impacts on socio-economic issues (e.g. human and animal health, agriculture, livelihoods, values, and food security) are often entirely missing.</i></p>	<p><i>There is a need for a system of collating information on impact through formal EICAT and SEICAT assessments. The impacts associated with the most widespread and invasive species need to be confirmed and documented. The list might change over time, so procedures to obtain the first list are needed. Studies that document impacts of individual invasive species and/or taxa need to be promoted and funded and in particular to explore taxa other than invasive alien plants.</i></p> <p><i>An integrated and coordinated approach in documenting and undertaking research and management of invasive species with impacts on socio-economic issues is needed.</i></p> <p><i>Efforts with other relevant departments where the impacts of invasive species are relevant at national, provincial and local levels [e.g. DAFF, Department of Health, Department of Water and Sanitation (DWS)] need to be aligned and co-ordinated.</i></p>	<p>MINIMAL</p> <p>155 species have been assessed using the EICAT and SEICAT assessment protocols.</p>	<p>See Chapter 6 “The gravity of the problem with biological invasions must be highlighted if an appropriate policy response is to be elicited. The rationale for government to continue to invest substantial resources in tackling biological invasions rests on the need to reduce the impacts that invasions cause to all sectors of South African society and to the country’s unique biodiversity. Data on impacts are essential if control measures are to be prioritised and to track the effectiveness of interventions (e.g., in terms of increasing the resilience of South African cities, towns, and rural communities to droughts and fires; ensuring agricultural sustainability; and protecting our natural capital for future generations).”</p>
<p>HIGH-LEVEL (sites)</p> <p>C. Extent of area that suffers major impacts from invasions</p>	<p><i>There are some data available on the distribution (occurrence) of invasive alien plants and birds at the scale of quarter degree grid cells, but there is limited or no knowledge about the impacts caused by non-plant taxa.</i></p> <p><i>Even less is known about the abundance of invasions at sites where the relevant alien species occur. The lack of knowledge about (1) the impacts of individual species, and (2) their abundance precludes any sensible estimate of the area that experiences major impacts.</i></p>	<p><i>A systematic approach to documenting the level of non-plant invasions at sites is needed.</i></p> <p><i>Monitoring techniques to estimate the extent of invasions and models to go from this to projected impacts need to be developed.</i></p> <p><i>The extent of invasions at the scale of both biophysical (biomes, catchments or ecosystems), and administrative (provincial or municipal) areas need to be documented.</i></p> <p><i>Remote sensing tools should be used to provide a broad-scale analysis of areas that are heavily invaded.</i></p>	<p>MINIMAL</p> <p>There are several initiatives in place to collect data, but little tangible progress to date (cf. sites chapter)</p>	<p>See Chapter 6 “Without detailed maps at national and local scales estimates of the impact of invasions remain crude, it is not possible to appropriately prioritise interventions across sites, and the ability to ensure interventions can adapt and respond to invasions before they are widespread and damaging is limited.”</p>

Indicator	Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report	Proposed solution	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
<p>HIGH-LEVEL (interventions)</p> <p>D. Level of success in managing invasions</p>	<p><i>The capacity and understanding exists to measure the degree of control achieved by plant biological control, but currently very little can be said about the effectiveness of other forms of management due to a lack of monitoring.</i></p> <p><i>The effectiveness of the Regulations (NEM:BA: Alien and Invasive Species Regulations, 2014) has not been assessed as it is too early to do so.</i></p>	<p><i>Adequate procedures, including goal-setting and monitoring, need to be in place for future assessments.</i></p> <p><i>An integrated and coordinated approach and alignment with other programmes by other government departments and institutions is needed.</i></p> <p><i>Explore options to ensure adequate monitoring data are collected (e.g. clearing contracts are not paid out until there is a documented assessment of performance)</i></p> <p><i>The indicator needs to be assessed at different scales and areas and through simulations to explore how responsive it is to different behaviours.</i></p> <p><i>A system of setting up national or local goals and the strategies to achieve these is needed.</i></p>	<p>MINIMAL</p> <p>The absence of clear goals and monitoring of progress has not been addressed to date. There has been no research on indicator performance yet, and proposals to apply the indicators to particular sites are still in the initiation phase. Similarly there are several research projects designed to assess the impact of particular policies, but these are mostly still in the early stages.</p>	<p>See Chapter 6 “Monitoring of interventions in terms of their outputs and outcomes is essential if their effectiveness is to be assessed, and for management to become adaptive. The effectiveness of interventions cannot be assessed (and improved) unless monitoring and reporting data workflows that result in clearly documented information are in place and made available for scrutiny.”</p>
<p>PATHWAYS</p> <p>1. Introduction pathway prominence</p>	<p><i>Socio-economic information is required to assess introduction pathway prominence. Some of the required data are available from global and local databases. However, for some of the pathways of introduction these data could not be obtained. Unfortunately, these data are often owned by companies or are regarded as sensitive and, therefore, it is often difficult or impossible to obtain the required information. In some instances, large sums of money need to be paid to the companies that own the information to gain access to these data (for an example see Faulkner, Robertson, Rouget, & Wilson, 2017b). Finally, for some pathways it is difficult to obtain or collate relevant socio-economic data, simply because the description of the pathway is imprecise (e.g. ‘other intentional release’).</i></p>	<p><i>To lessen the gaps in our knowledge on the pathways of introduction and dispersal, research into specific pathways is required, particularly for inconspicuous pathways such as e-commerce (Humair, Humair, Kuhn, & Kueffer, 2015). It is important to note that research is currently being undertaken on a number of pathways of introduction, including the pet trade, the traditional medicine trade and the aquarium plant trade. This information needs to be incorporated into subsequent reports.</i></p>	<p>MODERATE</p> <p>There has been significant research on some pathways of introduction (e.g. the pet trade (Nelufule, 2018; Shivambu, 2018) and the medicinal plant trade (Burness, 2019; Byrne, Williams, & Wojtasik, 2017), and on the pathways of introduction for certain taxa (e.g. bamboo (Canavan, Richardson, Le Roux, & Wilson, 2019). The information generated by this research has been incorporated in this report, however, many pathways of introduction remain poorly studied.</p>	<p>Without information on the size or socio-economic importance of the pathways and how their size has changed over time, the relative potential of the pathways to introduce alien taxa cannot be determined. Consequently, the pathways cannot be prioritised for management and the effectiveness of the interventions that are currently in place to manage pathways cannot be assessed.</p>

<p>PATHWAYS</p> <p>2. Introduction rates</p>	<p><i>To assess introduction rates for the pathways, pathway of introduction and date of introduction data for the species introduced to South Africa are required. These data are not available or have not been collated for many alien species, particularly for introduced plants and insects (Faulkner, Spear, Robertson, Rouget, & Wilson, 2015). Additionally, the dataset used in this assessment was collated a few years ago, and so data for very recently introduced species (e.g. the marine amphipod <i>Caprella mutica</i> (Japanese skeleton shrimp) is not included (Peters & Robinson, 2017)). The pathway of introduction data that are available were also in some instances not of sufficient quality or detail to designate pathways of introduction with certainty. Furthermore, the increased level of detail provided by the pathway categorisation scheme adopted by the CBD (CBD, 2014) has led to an increase in uncertainty when designating pathways of introduction (Tsiamis, Cardoso, & Gervasini, 2017). This is because the differences between some of the pathway subcategories are unclear (Tsiamis et al., 2017). Although an effort was made to rate the confidence in the pathway categorisations and in the assessment as a whole, information on the quality and source of the original data (e.g. direct evidence vs assumptions based on species traits or knowledge from other regions) are required to better rate confidence, and these data were often not available.</i></p> <p><i>Few introduction pathways have been researched in detail, but the work that has been done includes research into the aquatic plant trade (Martin & Coetzee, 2011), trade in traditional medicine (Byrne et al., 2017; Wojtasik, 2013), and the unintentional</i></p>	<p><i>The rates of species introduction into, and spread within, South Africa need to be quantified.</i></p> <p><i>One possible extension is to weight pathways according to the consequences of the species introduced, i.e. whether species introduced along a particular pathway led to particularly severe impacts. For example, in the Czech Republic species that were introduced intentionally seem to be more likely to have naturalised and become invasive, but invasive taxa that were accidentally introduced tend to be more widespread and have greater impacts, perhaps because they have been preselected for dispersal and competitive traits (Pyšek, Jarošík, & Pergl, 2011).</i></p>	<p>MODERATE</p> <p>The dataset used in the first report has been updated and integrated where possible with the species list, however, information on the date and pathway of introduction for many introduced species has still not been collated.</p> <p>Recommendations on improvements to the pathway categorisation scheme adopted by the CBD have been published and information has been provided on the interpretation of the categories (Harrower, Scalera, Pagad, Schönrogge, & Roy, 2018). However, the data that are available are often still not of sufficient quality to designate pathways of introduction with certainty.</p> <p>There has been recent research on some pathways of introduction (e.g. on hull fouling (Peters & Robinson, 2017), and on the pathways for certain types of organisms (e.g. parasites of freshwater fish (Weyl et al., 2020), but many pathways of introduction remain poorly studied.</p> <p>Weighting pathways according to the consequences of the introductions is still not possible due to a lack of data on impacts.</p>	<p>Data on the pathways and dates of introduction of alien taxa are vital to determine the relative importance of the pathways for the introduction of alien taxa. Without these data pathways of introduction cannot be prioritised for management and the effectiveness of the interventions that are in place to manage the pathways cannot be assessed.</p>
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Indicator	Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report	Proposed solution	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
	<i>introduction of contaminants on imported plant cuttings (Saccaggi & Pieterse, 2013).</i>			
PATHWAYS 3. Within-country pathway prominence	<i>Limited knowledge on the dispersal of alien species throughout the country from ports of entry.</i>	<i>An assessment of the relative prominence of dispersal pathways within South Africa is needed.</i>	NONE Limited information on the pathways of dispersal still precludes an assessment of the relative prominence of the within-country dispersal pathways. Plans are in place to start data collection.	Information on the size or socio-economic importance of the within-country pathways of dispersal is required to determine the potential of the pathways to facilitate the movement of species within the country. Consequently, without these data the pathways that require management cannot be identified, and the effectiveness of the interventions that are currently in place to manage these pathways cannot be assessed.
PATHWAYS 4. Within-country dispersal rates	<i>Data on within-country dispersal have not been collated for alien species in South Africa. Such information is only available for a few groups of extralimital species [e.g. amphibians (Measey et al., 2017) and fish (Picker & Griffiths, 2011)].</i>	<i>Within-country dispersal rates for the pathways of dispersal should be assessed using data on the pathways and dates of dispersal for introduced species and species that are native to the country but that have been introduced to parts of the country where they are not native (extralimital introductions).</i>	NONE Data on within-country dispersal have not been collated. Plans are in place to start data collection for extralimital species.	Data on how alien and extralimital taxa are dispersing within the country and their dates of dispersal are required to determine the relative importance of the pathways for the within-country dispersal of alien taxa. Without these data the pathways of dispersal that require management cannot be identified, and the effectiveness of the interventions that are in place to manage the pathways cannot be assessed.
SPECIES 5. Number and status of alien species	<i>The numbers of alien terrestrial plant species and vertebrate species are well documented. The number of alien invertebrates, marine species and, especially, microbial species are much less well known. The same applies to introduction status, i.e. alien plant and vertebrate species are relatively well documented compared to other taxa. However, introduction status is not formally recorded anywhere, so this aspect cannot accurately be summarised and updated.</i>	<i>Databases should record introduction status, and the records should be updated regularly.</i>	SUBSTANTIAL The species list has been updated and redesigned to align with Darwin Core (Groom et al. 2019). The source for data is now clearly specified as is the level of confidence in each entry. A workflow has been developed to add new species as they are recorded.	A national registry of alien species would help clarify which species are legally in the country, consolidate information on the status of invasive species, and provide an important reference resource for the biodiversity and broader community. Without this the regulations will be more likely subject to challenges.

Indicator	<i>Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report</i>	<i>Proposed solution</i>	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
SPECIES 6. Extent of alien species	<i>Reliable distribution data are available for terrestrial and freshwater plants and birds, but not for other taxa. This status report was only able to estimate the extent of 835 out of the 2033 species (section 5.2.1).</i>	<i>Databases for terrestrial and freshwater plants and birds should continue to be updated, and more effort will be needed to assemble reliable data on taxa other than terrestrial and freshwater plants and birds.</i>	MINIMAL There is support for various atlas projects, ensuring the long-term sustainability of these is a priority. Much more still needs to be done to integrate these datasets and citizen science platforms.	For 6–8, see high-level indicators B. Number of invasive species that have major impacts and C. Extent of area that suffers major impacts from invasions
SPECIES 7. Abundance of alien species	<i>The Abundance of alien species is very poorly known. For almost all species, there are no assessments of cover or density (for sessile organisms) or of population sizes or biomass (for mobile organisms). There is a mapping exercise under way to estimate the cover of invasive alien plants (Kotzé et al., 2010), but it is limited to about half of the country and to selected taxa, and there are concerns that the methodology is not documented.</i>	<i>The use of remote sensing techniques should be explored. For mobile organisms, distribution and population size data could be used to model abundance, but this would require research.</i>	MINIMAL Some exploratory work has been initiated on remote sensing, and some general guidelines are available on the types of data that need to be collected (e.g. Cheney et al. 2018), but there are still very few tangible data (cf. sites chapter)	

Indicator	Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report	Proposed solution	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
<p>SPECIES</p> <p>8. Impact of alien species</p>	<p><i>For most species, there is almost no documented evidence of impact, and available evidence is mainly anecdotal (e.g. not available as peer reviewed research papers). There are some notable exceptions, for example for Prosopis species (see Box 4.2).</i></p> <p><i>Several taxa are listed at levels other than species (e.g. genus or family), but fundamentally biological invasions result from introduction events resulting in a population-level phenomenon. Impacts at the gene level can be particularly concerning (e.g. the loss of indigenous species through hybridisation), but have rarely been assessed.</i></p>	<p><i>An understanding of impacts of invasive species can be strengthened by new approaches, including assessments of the effects of the species concerned on ecosystem services, ecosystem resilience, human livelihoods, agriculture, and animal and human health.</i></p> <p><i>There is a need for a system of collating information on impact through formal EICAT and SEICAT assessments.</i></p> <p><i>There is a need to promote and fund studies that document impacts of individual invasive species, and in particular to explore species other than invasive alien plants.</i></p> <p><i>There needs to be an integrated and coordinated approach to documenting and undertaking research and management of invasive species with impacts on socio-economic issues, in addition to the biophysical or ecological effects.</i></p> <p><i>Efforts are needed to align the activities of relevant government departments (e.g. the Department of Environmental Affairs, Department of Health, Department of Water and Sanitation, Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries), as invasive species have a variety of impacts across national, provincial and local levels.</i></p> <p><i>There will need to be a substantial on-going investment in impact studies for EICAT and SEICAT to be sufficiently reactive to allow the monitoring of trends on the scale of years rather than decades.</i></p>	<p>MINIMAL</p> <p>Data presented in this report represent a shift from expert assessments of impact towards assessments based on published data (e.g. through EICAT and SEICAT). This process still needs to be completed and aligned with the developing international frameworks in the area.</p> <p>A few studies have indicated impact, but this remains a major gap where detailed research is needed.</p>	
<p>SITES</p> <p>9. Alien species richness</p>	<p><i>There are data on the extent of species that can be used to assess Alien species richness in areas using Geographic Information System (GIS) overlays. These data are much more comprehensive for terrestrial and freshwater plants and for birds than for other taxa.</i></p>	<p><i>South African National Parks, most provincial conservation departments, and some Metros should have information about invasions in their protected areas. These data were not available or accessible at the time of this assessment and will need to be sourced for future reports.</i></p>	<p>MINIMAL</p> <p>There has been good progress for South African National Parks (van Wilgen and Herbst 2017), but not for other conservation agencies.</p>	<p>It will be hard to predict what the likely future threats are at a given site until the alien species that are not currently invasive are known (i.e. this is the species-based invasion debt)</p>

Indicator	Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report	Proposed solution	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
SITES NA. Relative alien species richness	<i>As above, plus there is a need for good spatial data on the distribution of indigenous species.</i>	<i>The processes of documenting distributions of indigenous species would need to be improved.</i>	NA The indicator has been discontinued given the uncertainties in native species richness (Wilson et al. 2018).	NA
SITES 10. Relative invasive abundance	<i>There are no reliable data to assess abundance.</i> <i>There are insufficient data to assign values of cover, biomass or population size to indigenous species, which would be needed if relative abundance is to be estimated.</i>	<i>More research is needed in priority areas to assess relative abundance</i> <i>At a finer scale it can be important to consider abundance in ecologically relevant sub-divisions, e.g. habitats or vegetation types.</i>	MINIMAL The methodology to underpin a national assessment of relative tree cover has been published (Kotzé et al. 2019), but no results are yet available. This should be seen as a priority, as relative abundance will be closely correlated with impact.	For 10–11, see high-level indicators B. Number of invasive species that have major impacts and C. Extent of area that suffers major impacts from invasions
SITES 11. Impact of invasions	<i>There are very few data on the impacts of co-occurring alien species in particular areas. There are a few studies on impacts on water resources at a catchment scale, and on rangeland productivity and biodiversity at a biome scale. These are coarse estimates, as many assumptions had to be made due to a lack of impact studies at a species scale.</i> <i>The choice of what to measure in terms of the impact of invasions will be influential and the importance of different impacts will be context-dependent. A “minor” reduction in biodiversity in a biodiversity hotspot might be much more important than a “massive” reduction elsewhere; similarly providing the cost of an invasion in absolute terms might hide major and profound societal inequities.</i>	<i>More research is required to translate the species-level impact into ecosystem-level impacts, and protocols need to be developed that will allow for joint consideration of environmental and socio-economic impacts when making decisions.</i> <i>There are insufficient data to express the effects of reductions in ecosystem services in economic or social terms (De Lange & Van Wilgen, 2010). There is a need for a conceptual link with the EICAT and SEICAT scheme for species.</i> <i>Reductions in ecosystem services should be placed in the context of how critical those services are in particular areas.</i>	MINIMAL A small number of studies have been conducted since the first report (see Chapter 4). There is a particular need to develop protocols to scale up the implications of studies at local scales to the scale of catchments, protected areas or biomes (e.g. Görgens and van Wilgen 2004).	

Indicator	<i>Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report</i>	<i>Proposed solution</i>	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
<p>INTERVENTIONS (Inputs)</p> <p>12. Quality of regulatory framework</p>	<p><i>The Alien and Invasive Species regulations are amongst the most comprehensive in the world, but are not explicit on pathway measures.</i></p> <p><i>The reason for listing or not listing particular species has not been adequately documented.</i></p>	<p><i>An independent assessment of the regulations would provide valuable insights.</i></p> <p><i>The evidence for including or excluding, adding or removing species from lists should be clearly documented, with both retrospective assessments of the evidence base and a requirement for future changes to be clearly documented.</i></p>	<p>MODERATE</p> <p>The DFFtE have published for public comment a list of species that they intend to add to the list of regulated species. This is being held up due to a legal challenge.</p> <p>A recent publication (Lukey and Hall 2020) noted that the current regulations operate in a policy vacuum, and that a comprehensive evidence-based policy-making process should be instituted as a matter of urgency. Moreover a legal expert assisted with the compilation of this report.</p> <p>In terms of the evidence for listing species, a risk analysis framework has been developed, ASRRP has been established, there is already some progress in producing retrospective risk analyses, and the DFFtE are in the process of establishing an inter-departmental decision making panel on biosecurity.</p>	<p>The absence of a policy, and therefore an absence of a clear policy position on biological invasions in South Africa, means that the organs of state and other stakeholders are not guided in administrative decision-making relating to biological invasions. Parliament also has no guidance when asked to review legislation pertaining to biological invasions.</p> <p>The lack of clarity on policy objectives makes it difficult for relevant organs of state to devise short- and medium-term implementation plans, and to estimate the annual budget required for the implementation of those plans. This, in turn, makes monitoring and reporting difficult.</p> <p>The absence of a policy is also inimical to setting clear indicators against which the quality of the regulations could be measured.</p>

Indicator	Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report	Proposed solution	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
INTERVENTION S (Inputs) 13. Money spent	<i>Data presented in the report are largely only available in terms of the spending by the Department of Environmental Affairs.</i>	<i>An assessment of the contributions from different departments at all spheres of government (national, provincial and local), and from the private sector, is needed.</i>	NONE The amount spent by DFFtE has been updated and is now estimated to be around ZAR 1.2 billion annually. This is lower than what was reported in the first status report, and the difference arises because there is no clear record of how much is spent on biological invasions opposed to other functions funded by NRM. Data on spending by other spheres of government, and by the private sector, are not available.	Without a clear understanding of the costs of the interventions it is impossible to assess their cost effectiveness and thereby whether a particular intervention should be implemented or stopped.
INTERVENTION S (Inputs) 14. Planning coverage	<i>Only 29 site-specific control plans were submitted (Appendix 4) covering ~4.5% of the country. Most of these control plans did not have explicit goals.</i> <i>Other site-specific plans exist, but these have shortcomings. For example, van Wilgen et al. (2017) reported that high-level goals in protected area management plans are not effectively carried forward to 5-year implementation plans or annual plans of operation. As a result, there is a focus on only monitoring inputs and outputs rather than outcomes.</i>	<i>A greater emphasis of stating the goal of management at all levels of planning is required for management effectiveness to be assessed. Goals would need to be quantifiable and time-bound.</i>	MINIMAL An additional 45 management site-specific plans, covering a total of 648 000 hectares have been submitted. Most of the plans were found to be partially adequate but there is still a need to improve the quality of submitted plans. Species-specific control plans are only available for some of the species targeted for eradication; the quality of these plans has not yet been evaluated.	Without plans in place, control measures will be haphazard and it will be very difficult for control to improve. It will also be difficult (impossible) to track and motivate for resources.
INTERVENTION S (Outputs) 15. Pathways treated	<i>Detailed data on the total number of imports or vessels per pathway and the number that have been subjected to a management intervention. Information on the exact procedure followed (e.g. random or targeted inspections, number of ports of entry covered). Assessment of quality of the interventions.</i>	<i>Detailed information from the various Governmental Departments involved on the pathways with control in place, and details on the procedure followed and coverage. Assessments of the quality of the intervention in place for each pathway or groups of similar pathways.</i>	MINIMAL Information was obtained from the DALRRD on inspections performed on agricultural products.	Without detailed information on the interventions in place for each pathway and the procedures followed, the effectiveness of the interventions cannot be assessed.

Indicator	<i>Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report</i>	<i>Proposed solution</i>	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
INTERVENTION S (Outputs) 16. Species treated	<p><i>Currently, most control operations report on the area treated (in the case of plants) or individuals removed (in the case of animals). The data are often not reliable, however, and the quality of treatment is typically not recorded at all (see, for example, Kraaij et al. 2017).</i></p>	<p><i>Monitoring records should include an assessment of the quality and outcome of treatment interventions, accompanied by quality control to assure accuracy.</i></p>	<p>MINIMAL</p> <p>This report provides a list of 237 species that have been the subject of control interventions, with estimated costs for some. The quality and outcomes of control operations are still not assessed (except for some species subjected to biological control). Seven new biological control agents have been released against alien plants. Some additional information on the control of invasive fishes and birds has become available, and there have been some localised successes and some failures. Additional information on the control of invasive plant species is limited to two studies, which support earlier conclusions that (1) biological control can be effective, and (2) that improvements in control efficiency will be needed if the goals of reducing alien plant invasions to maintenance levels are to be achieved.</p>	<p>Without detailed information on the interventions in place for each species and the procedures followed, the effectiveness of the interventions cannot be assessed.</p>

Indicator	Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report	Proposed solution	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
INTERVENTION S (Outputs) 17. Sites treated	<i>There is almost complete lack of monitoring programmes that assess progress towards goals. What monitoring there is has a focus on inputs (money spent, jobs created), and arguably on area treated, although this is uncritical as the quality of treatment is largely ignored.</i>	<p><i>Without the collection of primary monitoring data, future reports will be similarly limited. Changing this will require both training and a change in working practices. The need for such data must be clearly communicated to stakeholders.</i></p> <p><i>There are some specific areas where data can be collated and analysed. For example, it is important that there is an assessment of the scale and impact of herbicides used (Wagner et al., 2017) as well as the effectiveness of herbicide application in terms of quantity and timing.</i></p>	<p>NONE</p> <p>It remains challenging to assess the area treated. Monitoring data from DFFtE's NRM programmes suggest a decrease in area treated since 2014, but this may not be real due to a relaxation of the requirement to record areas treated (van Wilgen et al. 2020c).</p>	<p>Without detailed information on the interventions in place for each site and the procedures followed, the effectiveness of the interventions cannot be assessed.</p>
INTERVENTION S (Outcomes) 18. Effectiveness of pathway treatments	<i>Pathway interventions (regulation, inspection and interception) are intended to slow or halt the rate of new introductions. However, it is challenging to accurately quantify the rates of introductions, and even more so to attribute any changes in rates to a particular intervention.</i>	<p><i>A historical review of the effectiveness of pathway, species and area-based management in South Africa is needed.</i></p> <p><i>For pathways it would be desirable to assess the outcomes of interventions in terms of their cost-effectiveness, and perhaps to explicitly separate efforts pre-border, at-border, and post-border, as different management goals are appropriate at different invasion stages (see Section 2.1). For example, for pathways it is important to get estimates of how much effort, where, and when should be placed in monitoring a given pathways (Bacon et al., 2012, Faulkner et al., 2016).</i></p>	<p>MINIMAL</p> <p>Recent research on pathways of introduction (e.g. Canavan, Richardson, Le Roux, & Wilson, 2019; Cronin, Kaplan, Gaertner, Irlich, & Hoffman, 2017) meant that the effectiveness of the interventions for some pathways could be assessed for the first time.</p> <p>Information was obtained from the DALRRD on the results of inspections performed on agricultural products.</p>	<p>Without information on the procedures followed to manage the pathways, the degree to which these procedures have reduced introduction rates, and their cost-effectiveness, pathway interventions cannot be properly assessed and improved, and the benefits of this approach as opposed to others (e.g. eradication or control of species post-introduction) cannot be determined.</p> <p>See also high-level indicator D. Level of success in managing invasions.</p>

Indicator	Level of knowledge and information gaps for first report	Proposed solution	Progress	Consequence in the gap is not filled
<p>INTERVENTION S (Outcomes)</p> <p>19. Effectiveness of species treatments</p>	<p><i>The effectiveness of biological control of invasive alien plants is well understood. The effectiveness of other control efforts is not understood due to an almost complete lack of monitoring. At a national scale, for terrestrial plants, the South African Plant Invaders Atlas (SAPIA) has provided some indications that control efforts are not succeeding at a national scale (Henderson & Wilson 2017).</i></p>	<p><i>Accurate national-scale monitoring of species populations needs to be improved, especially for taxa other than terrestrial plants and birds.</i></p> <p><i>For plants, a review is needed of existing monitoring efforts (SAPIA and the National Invasive Alien Plant Survey, Kotzé et al. 2010), and the use of other approaches (for example remote sensing), with a view to increasing the effectiveness of monitoring.</i></p> <p><i>It would be useful to conduct comparative studies in which invaded areas with and without the implementation of control measures are compared to assess control effectiveness.</i></p>	<p>NONE</p> <p>The challenges reported in the first report remain. The level of national-scale monitoring has not improved, although information on biocontrol effectiveness continues to be collected.</p> <p>[to be updated to reflect progress with the level of knowledge, not activities]</p>	<p>See high-level indicator D. Level of success in managing invasions.</p>
<p>INTERVENTION S (Outcomes)</p> <p>20. Outcome: Effectiveness of site treatments</p>	<p><i>There is almost a complete lack of assessment of conservation and/or biodiversity outcomes in particular areas.</i></p>	<p><i>An assessment of the value and role of ecological restoration in managing biological invasions and contributing to conservation goals is needed.</i></p>	<p>MINIMAL</p> <p>A few studies have explored the recovery of sites after treatment, but data on the recovery of treated sites are not routinely collected.</p>	<p>See high-level indicator D. Level of success in managing invasions.</p>

1362 **Table S6.2** Key findings of book on biological invasions in South Africa (van Wilgen et al. 2020a)

Key finding	Implications	Relevant Chapters
South Africa is a leader in the field of biological invasions, both in terms of its contributions to scientific understanding of the problem, and in terms of developing and adapting approaches to management.	The quality of information available to compile a report might be expected to be greater in South Africa than in many other countries.	1, 30
South Africa has a relatively small and well-connected ecological community (including academics, researchers embedded in management agencies, managers and policy-makers) who, by-and-large, share common goals.	There is broad agreement on desired outcomes, even if there are differences about the means by which they should or could be achieved.	2, 24, 25, 28
Despite the existence of a set of comprehensive regulations to manage biological invasions, these operate in a policy vacuum.	There is an inability to be able to address many important questions.	18
The process for listing species under national regulations was not transparent and has been contested.	A transparent process that is supported by the best available scientific evidence is needed to support the listing of species.	20
In a few notable cases control measures have been contested, reducing the effectiveness of interventions.	Need processes to ensure stakeholder support for control measures.	6, 11, 21, 22, 24
Biological control remains the most cost-effective and sustainable method for gaining control of alien plant invasions.	The continued targeted, scientific application of biological control is warranted.	3, 4, 19, 21
Other methods of control, although effective at smaller scales, appear not to be effective when assessed at a national scale, although eradication of some species with restricted distributions remains a positive prospect.	There is an urgent need to focus scarce resources on a smaller number of priority areas if control is to be effective.	8, 21, 22, 23
Certain dimensions of the invasion problem have been poorly researched in the past (e.g. the invasion of marine ecosystems, or invasions by pathogens), and the challenges that these invasions will pose in future are not adequately understood.	There will be surprises, and so fundamental research on biological invasions is important in addition to directed applied research.	5, 6, 7, 9, 10
The substantial impacts that invasions can and do have on water resources, rangeland productivity, the ability to control damaging wildfires, and on biodiversity have been confirmed.	Biological invasions constitute a large, although not the largest, threat to biodiversity and the delivery of vital services from South Africa's varied ecosystems.	13, 14, 15, 16, 17
Most policy and management decisions relating to the management of biological invasions are taken within a short-term (1 to 5 year) framework dictated by funding cycles and elections.	There is a need for longer-term thinking that should address the potential outcomes in 200 – 200 years of actions taken now. Taking such an approach may allow for better and more effective interventions in the present day, that could steer the country on a course for better-long-term outcomes.	18, 28, 31

1363 **Chapter:** 1. Biological invasions in South Africa: an overview: van Wilgen et al.; 2. A Brief, Selective History of Researchers and Research Initiatives: van Wilgen; 3. The
1364 biogeography of South African terrestrial plant invasions: Richardson et al.; 4. Invasive alien aquatic plants in South African freshwater ecosystems: Hill et al.; 5. Terrestrial
1365 vertebrates invasion in South Africa: Measey et al.; 6. Alien freshwater fauna in South Africa: Weyl et al.; 7. Alien terrestrial invertebrates in South Africa: Janion-Scheepers

1366 and Griffiths; 8. Biological invasion in South Africa's offshore sub-Antarctic territories: Greve et al.; 9. Coastal invasions: the South African context: Robinson et al.; 10.
1367 Pathogens of vertebrate animals as invasive species: insights from South Africa: Van Helden et al.; 11. Biological Invasions in South Africa's Urban Ecosystems: Potgieter et
1368 al.; 12. South Africa's pathways of introduction and dispersal: Faulkner et al.; 13. The role of environmental factors in promoting and limiting invasions: Wilson et al.; 14.
1369 Biotic interactions as mediators of biological invasions: Le Roux et al.; 15. Impacts of plant invasions on terrestrial water flows in South Africa: Le Maitre et al.; 16. The impacts
1370 of invasive alien plants on rangelands in South Africa: O'Connor and van Wilgen; 17. An evaluation of the impacts of alien species on biodiversity: Zengeya et al.; 18. Biological
1371 invasion policy and legislation development: Lukey and Hall; 19. Biological control against invasive alien plants in South Africa: Hill et al.; 20. Analysing the risk posed by
1372 biological invasions to South Africa: Kumschick et al.; 21. The extent and effectiveness of alien plant control projects in South Africa: van Wilgen et al.; 22. Alien and invasive
1373 animal control projects: Davies et al.; 23. Biological invasions and ecological restoration in South Africa: Holmes et al.; 24. The social dimensions of biological invasions in
1374 South Africa: Shackleton et al.; 25. Education, training and capacity-building: Byrne et al.; 26. South Africa as a donor of naturalised and invasive plants: Pysek et al.; 27. South
1375 Africa as donor of alien animals: Measey et al.; 28. Information flow between researchers and managers: Foxcroft et al.; 29. Biological invasions as a component of global
1376 change research: van Wilgen et al.; 30. South Africa's Centre for Invasion Biology: Richardson et al.; 31. Possible futures of biological invasions in South Africa: Wilson et al.
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1762 **Links to the report and the appendices**

1763 The report itself: "*The status of biological invasions and their management in South Africa in 2019.*"

1764 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947613>

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1766 Appendix 1: List of data sources used.

1767 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947603>

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1769 Appendix 2: The species list.

1770 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947659>

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1772 Appendix 3: Data on the status of pathways.

1773 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947666>

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1775 Appendix 4: Species list change tracker.

1776 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947778>

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1778 Appendix 5: Pathways change tracker.

1779 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947799>

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1781 Appendix 6: Permit database.

1782 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3947810>

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